

PROBONO

D5.1 GBN-DT Requirements Specification (I)

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PROBONO

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DEFINITIONS¹

A Green Building (GB) (new or retrofit) is a building that, in its design, construction and operation, reduces or eliminates negative impacts, and can create positive impacts, on the climate, social, and natural environment. GBs preserve precious natural resources and improve quality of life². Specifically, this means that GBs should be very energy efficient, use extensively the potential of locally available renewable energy, use sustainable materials, and aim for a low environmental impact over the entire life cycle. GBs offer their users and residents a healthy climate and a high quality of stay, they are resilient e.g., to environmental change and contribute to social inclusion.

Green Neighbourhoods aligned with the European Green Deal³, is a set of buildings over a delimited area, at a scale that is smaller than a district, with potential synergies, in particular in the area of energy. A green neighbourhood is a neighbourhood that allows for environmentally friendly, sustainable patterns and behaviours to flourish e.g., bioclimatic architecture, renewable energy, soft and zero-emission mobility etc. Green neighbourhoods are the building blocks of Positive Energy Districts (PEDs)⁴ by implementing key elements of PED energy systems. For example, the exchange of energy between buildings increases the share of local self-supply with climate-neutral energy and system efficiency. They also provide the technical conditions to enable Citizen Energy Communities⁵ and Renewable Energy Communities⁶ to be implemented.

Green Buildings and Neighbourhoods (GBN) in PROBONO are GBs integrated at delimited area or district level with green energy and green mobility management and appropriate infrastructure supported by policies, investments and stakeholders' engagement and behaviours that ensures just transition that maximize the economic and social cobenefits considering a district profile (population size, socio-economic structure, and geographical and climate characteristics). Delivered in the right way, GBN infrastructure is a key enabler of inclusive growth, can improve the accessibility of housing and amenities, reduce poverty and inequality, widen access to jobs and education, make communities more resilient to climate change, and promote public health and wellbeing.

DGNB certification serves as a quality stamp ensuring the state of the building for buyers. The Green Building Council Denmark (2010) established the German certification DGNB meaning 'German Society for Sustainable Buildings'. The Danish version of DGNB was created to obtain a common definition of what sustainability is towards and making it measurable. A consortium of experts was established from all parts of the construction sector. DGNB had to be reshaped for the Danish standards, practice, traditions, and laws but is now available to certify any construction project. They chose DGNB as an innovation-forward and sustainable future guarantee. DGNB diversifies itself by focusing on sustainability and not just the environment. DGNB creates a standardized framework for the construction operations conditions and creates a common language which facilitates communication between professions and helps organize and prioritize the efforts in long and complicated development phases.

¹ Please refer to the last submitted reports for the latest status of the definitions

² <https://www.worldgbc.org/what-green-building>

³ https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

⁴ SET-Plan Action 3.2: https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/setplan_smartcities_implementationplan-2.pdf

⁵ Internal Electricity Market Directive (EU) 2019/944

⁶ Renewable Energy Directive II (EU) 2018/2001

Life cycle assessment (LCA)⁷ is a tool used for the systematic quantitative assessment of each material used, energy flows and environmental impacts of products or processes. LCA assesses various aspects associated with development of a product and its potential impact throughout a product's life (i.e., cradle to grave) from raw material acquisition, processing, manufacturing, use and finally its disposal. In PROBONO, LCA represents the statement of a building's total energy, resource consumption and environmental impact in the manufacture, transport, and replacement of materials and for its operation over its expected life. Social life cycle assessment (S-LCA)⁸ is a method to assess the social and sociological aspects of products, their actual and potential positive as well as negative impacts along the life cycle. Life-cycle costing (LCC)⁹ considers all the costs incurred during the lifetime of the product, work, or service.

⁷ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/16cd2d1d-2216-11e8-ac73-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

⁸ <https://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/starting-life-cycle-thinking/life-cycle-approaches/social-lca/>

⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/lcc.htm>

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
BIM	Building information modelling
BIPV	Building integrated photovoltaic
CA	Consortium Agreement
DHCN	District Heating and Cooling geothermal Network
DoA	Description of Action (annex I of the Grant Agreement)
DOA	Description Of Activities
DT	Digital Twin
EC	European Commission
EC	Energy Community
EMS	Energy Management System
ESG	Environmental, Social and Governance
EV	Electric Vehicle
GA	Grant Agreement
GBMS	Green Building Maintenance System
GBN	Green Building Neighbourhood
GBN-DP	GBN Digital Platform
GBN-DT	GBN Digital Twin
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GIS	Geographical Data Base
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning
LEC	Local Energy Community
LL	Living Lab
PC	Project Coordinator
PMC	Project Management Committee
PO	Project Officer
PS	Project Secretariat
PV	Photo voltaic
QM	Quality Management
REC	Renewable Energy Community
SC	Scientific Coordinator
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SME	Small and medium enterprises
TL	Task Leader
TMT	Technical Management Team
ToC	Table of Contents

Acronym	Description
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

1 Executive summary

This document D5.1 reports the requirements identified until M16 for the development of digital twins, called GBN-DT¹⁰ or DT, for the purpose of Probono living labs (LLs).

This deliverable lists functional requirements expressed by LLs in the form of use cases. The intent is the description of the services which are expected to be provided by the GBN-DTs to the LLs from the user perspective. They are completed with some requirements related to data processing, visualization, and interoperability. The interoperability requirements focus on the interfaces between the GBN-DT and the external systems that need to exchange data or cooperate in a broader sense.

This report includes also for each DT, an inventory of available datasets that will be possibly needed or useful for implementing the identified use cases. These datasets will be provided by the LLs themselves or other entities for example organizations providing open data. In the same way, an initial inventory of digital solutions has been done. These solutions, provided by the LLs or by the Probono work packages, include some applications, systems, models which are envisioned to be integrated or interfaced to the GBN-DTs.

Finally, it incorporates requirements from WP3 for implementing simulation models and from WP6 for calculating KPIs, a data collection that WP4 can provide to be used by DTs as well as requirements related to data security.

This report will be updated in the D5.2 with new findings as the project progresses to finally submit a final version of this document at M 48.

¹⁰ Standing for: “Green Buildings and Neighbourhoods - Digital Twin”

2 Introduction

This report presents the requirements collected as part of the T5.1 GBN DT Requirement and Specification activity until M16. They provide an understanding of the LLs needs for the creation of DTs within PROBONO.

2.1 Mapping PROBONO outputs

This section maps the results reported in D3.1 according to the PROBONO Grant Agreement Task 5.1 description.

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASK			
Task 5.1: GBN DT Requirements Specification and Architecture	ST5.1.1 GBN DT Requirements Analysis and Specification. Specify representative use cases and application scenarios including Social and Behavioral user-centric scenarios that can be addressed through GBN-DT. Specific areas to be addressed:		
	a) Specify inventory of digital solutions (WP3, WP4 and LL descriptions) with data acquisition requirements	“WP3 requirements” chapter and “WP6 KPIs production requirements” chapter. “WP4 data collection” chapter.	
	(b) Identify data collection requirements: sources and types of data	Sections ‘Data – Inventory and requirements’ in chapters 5-11	
	(c) Identify processing requirements (data cleansing, storage, accessing)	Sections ‘Data – Inventory and requirements’ in chapters 5-11 Chapter 16 - WP6 KPIs Chapter 15 - Data security	
	(d) Identify requirements for decision-making tools (simulation, rule-based automation, optimization algorithms)	Sections ‘Decision-making tools – Inventory and requirements’ in chapters 5-11	
	(e) Identify interoperability requirements	Sections ‘DT & external systems & requirements’ in chapters 5-11	This report has focused on identifying systems that will interoperate with DTs.
	(f) Provide a data map across the Living Labs	Sections ‘Data – Inventory and requirements’ in chapters 5-11	
	(g) define the LL DTs expectations.	Chapters 5-11	

	ST5.1.2 GBN-DT Technical Architecture. Define the overall, generic architecture for GBN-DT. The main objective will be the operationalization of the architecture components, to be implemented and integrated driven by industry standards. Reflection will be to solution scalability, computational complexity, and deployment options. Guidelines on GBN-DT implementation will be created.	This component will be integrated in the deliverable D5.2	
DELIVERABLE			
<p>D5.1: GBN-DT Requirements Specification (I)</p> <p>This report formulates the findings of T5.1 and explores step consisting in the requirements capture for DT Specification.</p>			

Table 1: Adherence of D3.1 outputs and work performed to the GA commitments

2.2 Purpose and scope of the document

The objective of this report is to collect and document the requirements for the digital twins (DTs or GBN-DTs in this document) that are being considered for development by the WP5. These DTs will be part of the GBN digital platform (GBN-DP) planned to include all components which will be developed or integrated such as an open knowledge database and the KPI processing framework. More generally, the GBN-DP will provide a structure to the components of GBNs in a format that is possible to interrogate, allowing decision makers to identify the most pertinent information upon request. Specific objectives of WP5 are to (a) perform requirements elicitation for the different stakeholders and for the different GBNs lifecycle phases (b) design and implement the infrastructure supporting the GBN-DP (c) define and construct information and simulation models while ensuring their interoperability & integration (d) create a framework for tools and services development exploiting the GBN-DP, and (e) create a governance, access and security framework for data and services. This GBN-DP is the main objective of the WP5.

This deliverable was produced as part of the activities of Task T5.1 which consists of identifying requirements for GBN-DP, performing their analysis, developing specifications, and defining the generic architecture of GBN-DP. More specially, T5.1 intends to (a) define the LL expectations in terms of DTs, (b) Identify data collection requirements: sources and types of data, (c) Provide a data map across the Living Labs, (d) Identify interoperability requirements, (e) Specify inventory of digital solutions (WP3, WP4 and LL descriptions) with data acquisition requirements,

(f) Identify processing requirements, (g) Identify requirements for decision-making tools (simulation, rule-based automation, optimization algorithms).

2.3 Structure of the document and its relationship with other WPS/Deliverables

Structure of the document

This document is organised as following:

- Chapter 2 includes the purpose of this report and its links with Probono work packages.
- Chapter 3 provides a background on the concept of DT.
- Chapter 4 explains the approach to collect and describe the requirements linked to the developments of the DTs
- Chapters 5-11 provide the requirements from LLs for the DTS, a chapter is created for each DT.
- Chapter 12 lists the requirements provided by WP3.
- Chapter 13 includes a list of data that WP4 can provide to be used by DTs.
- Chapter 14 includes high-level requirements to the production of KPIs defined by WP6.
- Chapter 15 provides requirements linked to the data security within the GBN-DP.

Relation with other Work Packages/Deliverables

The identified links between this deliverable and some work packages or deliverables are outlined below.

WP1 - Macro-Knowledge Base and GBN Framework

- D1.5 provides some overall inputs which can complement the content of this document. Moreover, Brussels use case (BRU – C) should rely on the results of the T1.3 GBN Scenario Generation and Strategic Case Studies.

WP2 - Social and Behavioural Innovations

- D5.1 and WP2 are related in that some of the use cases described in this report are related to human behaviours. In addition, WP2 may have some usability requirements for DTs at some point in the project.

WP3 - PROBONO Smart Green Building Construction and Renovation

- WP3 will provide some innovations for GBN which bring their own digital models (for example: models of 'High Evaporative Green Roof' model, mobility flows and more). These models will be integrated and used by the GBN-DP. D3.1 which contains their description is an input for T5.1 although more precise requirements will have to be provided by WP3 afterwards.

WP4 - Energy Monitoring and Clean Energy Production, Storage and Distribution

- WP4 will create datasets that DTs could use. D5.1 integrates a summary of these datasets.

WP5 - Digitalisation for data driven GBN human-centred design and construction/renovation and operations optimisation

- T5.1 and D5.1 will serve the other tasks of WP5 (T5.2, T5.3, T5.4) by providing requirements, specifications and a generic architecture which should be developed and rolled out. D5.1 is an input document for D5.3, D5.6 and D5.9 and their subsequent versions to design and develop the GBN-DP.

WP6 - Monitoring and evaluation of the project's Living Labs

- WP5 GBN-DP will process the KPIs needed by WP6 for the monitoring and evaluation framework. The first inputs for WP5 have been outlined in D6.1 and WP6 has also provided some generic requirements for the KPI calculation in this report. However, the detailed specifications of each KPIs to be implemented will be given by WP6 in a specific report.

WP7 - Living Labs GBN Implementation

- WP5 and WP7 are linked in the way that WP5 will provide DTs for LLs and WP7 defines the implementation plan of innovations in LLs. D7.1 has given first high-level information for this document.

2.4 Contribution to GBN Concept

To ensure that the scale achieved is at the neighbourhood level and not just at the building level, DTs are key elements in addressing the interactions between multiple buildings, integrating

multiple data sources, facilitating collaboration between stakeholders, being adaptable and flexible, and promote citizen engagement.

Digital twins can simulate and analyse the interactions between multiple buildings within a neighbourhood. This provides a holistic view of the neighbourhood's systems, including energy, water, waste, mobility and communication systems. They will also integrate data from multiple sources, such as weather data, energy consumption data and occupancy data. This requires a robust data management system that can handle large amounts of data and different types of data.

Furthermore, the development of a sustainable neighbourhood requires the collaboration of different stakeholders, including developers, architects, engineers, policy makers and residents. The DTs can be that platform for collaboration and communication between these stakeholders. Citizen engagement is also critical in promoting GBNs – the DTs will provide stakeholders with access to information about the neighbourhood's sustainability metrics and encourage their participation in sustainability initiatives.

This document thus provides the groundwork for the requirements of DTs that not only consider the usual single asset/building, but also enable the integration of complex systems into a supporting DT platform through a system-of-systems approach very similar to the concept of DTs.

3 Digital Twin – Background

Digital twins¹¹ are digital representations of physical systems, based on timely data, which unlock new services, which create value by enabling improved insights that support better decisions actions, leading to better triple bottom-line (People, Planet, Profit) outcomes in the physical world.

What are digital twins?

What distinguishes a digital twin from any other digital model (Sepasgozar, Differentiating Digital Twin from Digital Shadow: Elucidating a Paradigm Shift to Expedite a Smart, Sustainable Built Environment, 2021) is its connection to the physical twin: it gets the information from the physical twin at the appropriate frequency for its use (minute for energy consumption fine tracking, monthly for invoicing purposes for example), and offers the means for the digital twin to act on the physical twin (adjusting heating for example).

Figure 1: Digital Model vs Digital Shadow vs Digital Twin (Kritzinger, 2018)

Digital twins often include a layer of connectors and data (sensing and reflecting the physical twin), creating information that is processed at a sense-making stage using models, AI, etc. and a decision-making stage through reporting, dashboards, APIs and visualization.

Digital Twins are systems, and as such can and have to be interconnected to other systems to leverage their usefulness.

11

<https://www.repository.cam.ac.uk/bitstream/handle/1810/335548/Digital%20Twin%20Journey%20Infographic.pdf?sequence=3&isAllowed=y>

They build on the technologies (IoT, sensors, cloud computing, ontologies, AI, ML) that closely interlink the cyber-physical worlds.

Figure 2: Physical twin and digital twin interactions

Digital twins are important because they offer a working frame to underpin a better relationship with our environment in general. Though today in their infancy, digital twins are becoming ubiquitous and more and more part of our lives.

The key purpose of a digital twin is to enable better decisions faster, creating benefits through financial, environmental or socio-economic value. Based on data from the physical asset or system, a digital twin unlocks value by supporting improved decision making, which creates the opportunity for positive feedback into the physical twin.

DTs and PROBONO

Digital Twins can be used in Probono to reflect, test, assess and use in the digital space, the innovation proposed by PROBONO partners in the physical space. They aim at augmenting and maximise the effects of the different innovations developed by the project, helping to structure them to better replicate them.

Challenges

One of the most important questions before investing time and energy is to properly determine the “Why” behind the strategy. As such, someone interested in developing a digital twin of their systems would want to know the return they will get from the digital twin-enabled services.

The second challenge is technical since DTs integrate a large range of various technologies (e.g., simulation, IoT, AI, big data) that it could be difficult to integrate into a single consistent system. Moreover, a DT should also interoperate with some other IT systems or even with some other digital twins and the question of interoperability is also challenging.

Figure 3: Some technical components of a digital twin

An example of a basic digital twin

A smart heating system can be supported by basic digital twin. The purpose of the system is to deliver a continuous, cost-efficient, level of temperature to its users.

1. The Physical twin would be a building, with for example electric heaters.
2. Data is captured through a sensor, a thermometer, sending a regular flow of measures to the digital twin.
3. The Digital Twin has a model of the behaviour of the physical twin and knows how to calculate the setting of the heater to precisely adjust the temperature of the heater to reach the temperature target without under or overshooting. It can be augmented by external information through weather information through APIs. Dashboards of electricity use and temperature can be made available to the user.
4. Once the new setting of the heater calculated, the intervention is automatically taken, with the DT adjusting the heater setting, in turn impacting the physical twin.

Figure 4: Example of a basic digital twin

4 Methodology

First, it has been decided to **organize the requirement elicitation process around the definition of one digital twin for every living lab** except for Madrid LL which is required two distinct DTs due to two very distinguished physical twins and needs which might not be consolidated into a single digital twin.

Then, the adopted approach to identify and document the candidate requirements for the LLs DTs has been broken down in the following steps:

1. **Description of the physical context** which includes the components that will be replicated in the DT.
2. **Identification of high-level needs** which give the overall purpose of the DT and the business goal for which the DT is expected to be an enabler. To determine the high-level needs, we started an ideation process focusing on needs the LL could achieve, in line with the Green Deal objectives, and meeting PROBONO objective.
3. Then, each high-level need has been divided into **a set of UML use cases**¹². A use case describes what the DT should deliver as service for a human or system user. Each description includes a narrative description, the user and a scenario describing the interactions between the DT and the user. The use cases represent the functional requirements expressed by the LLs for the DTs.

¹² Standardized use case methodology IEC62559-2: Use case methodology - Part 2: Definition of the templates for use cases, actor list and requirements list

4. **A data inventory and associated requirements** has been produced for each DT across the LLs. This inventory lists the data which will be useful for the development of the identified use cases or to be referenced for future needs which are not envisioned yet, in this case, this is a “data lake” approach consisting in getting the data first and defining the usage afterwards. This inventory might be completed with additional requirements related to the identified datasets.
5. Similarly, an **inventory of decision-making and visualization tools has been done**. It refers to the IT tools such as BIM and EMS, simulation models, AI models, algorithms identified by the LLs which will be possibly used or implemented in the GBN-DP to develop the use cases.
6. **Interoperability requirements have been sought** by identifying the external systems which should be connected to the DT with the data which could be exchanged between them, and the protocol needed for this exchange.
7. In addition to this requirement elicitation process with LLs, it has been requested to the work packages WP1-6 to formulate the requirements they have for the GBN-DP.

This process has been supported by a questionnaire to structure the inventories and the requirements requested to the LLs. In this document, only a synthesis of the obtained information has been inserted for the sake of clarity and confidentiality.

At the time of writing, the completed questionnaires are available at this location in the Probono MS Teams folder: *sites/PROBONO/Shared Documents/General/WP5 DT (AKKA) internal/T5.1 GBN-DT_Requirements/Inventories-Requirements*. These questionnaires will be continuously updated during the project.

All this process has been achieved through a series of workshops organised between different stakeholders (LLs, WP5 task leaders, T5.1 partners, partners from other work packages) and led by nominated T5.1 partners who acted as proxies between LLs and the WP5 team. The picture below shows an example of the ideation process adopted in Brussels LL.

Figure 5: Example of a DT Workshop for Brussels LL

5 DUB - Dublin Living Lab

5.1 Living Lab Context

5.1.1 Location

Dún Laoghaire-Rathdown County, DLR, is a coastal suburban town south-east of Dublin city and the traditional port of arrival of cross-channel ferries from Wales. It is located between the outer suburbs of Dublin City and the Dublin mountains; with its 17km of coastline, harbour, attractive towns and villages alongside communities where residents and visitors enjoy some of the best natural amenities in Ireland. It also has the benefit of unparalleled access to public transport, employment opportunities, leisure facilities, education, shopping and an attractive public realm. It is a smart, vibrant county; attractive, inclusive, and accessible to all. Climate action is high on the Council's agenda and elected members have adopted a Climate Change Action Plan setting out ambitious but achievable goals to continue to address climate change and protect our environment for the future.

Figure 6: Dublin LL - Top View of Dún Laoghaire

5.1.2 Physical Twin Details

The Dún Laoghaire use cases are to be applied to the following entities:

- **County Hall:** Sits at the heart of the LL and serves as the center of local government and a civic hub where the public can interact with the Council. The original building, completed in 1879, is a solid masonry, protected structure that is now connected to the former town post office building. Recently an extension in the form of a steel, glass and concrete clad was added as a modern office for the Council staff. These refurbishments have resulted in many different material types being used in construction and earlier retrofit projects. County Hall comprises about 70% Offices and 10% Customer Service

Area which is accessible to the public. There are two floors of underground parking comprising the remaining 20%. Since County Hall comprises two heritage buildings within the envelope of a modern concrete and glass office building it presents a unique challenge, especially in the area of insulation and heat dissipation.

Figure 7: Dublin LL - County Hall view

- Harbor Lodge:** A historical building of the neighbourhood currently undergoing renovation currently in the retrofit construction phase that offers potential to implement technologies for the long term. It has been converted to office space for DLR staff, however, there are challenges with upgrading the building as it is a protected structure. Novel approaches are required to enhance the energy usage profile. Work undertaken in the County Hall, particularly the historic section, will align with the work to be undertaken here.

Lexicon library: County library completed in 2014. Opened in 2015, the Lexicon is a library and cultural center at the heart of Dún Laoghaire. Was built with more modern materials and demonstrates modern energy/building management systems. Wind-capture nodes on the roof drive air currents through the Lexicon.

- Social housing:** A rolling retrofit program on the circa 5,000 DLR social housing units will be carried out in the next 5 years. This work will build on the NZEB101 national Irish project coordinated by UCD researchers, that include a sample of 30 homes located in the DLR neighbourhood in an analysis set of 101 NZEB homes.

- Beaufort is an elderly social housing scheme that went through the unique process of a retrofit while the tenants remained in situ.

Figure 8: Dublin LL - Social housing view

The buildings “County Hall” and “Lexicon library” are mainly dedicated to public reception. The buildings “County Hall”, “Lexicon library”, and “Harbour Lodge” are used by staff and Management workers. Social housing buildings are used by tenants.

County Hall is the main administrative center for Dún Laoghaire Rathdown County. Around 600 staff work here, and it also hosts the Civic Hub which is the 'Customer Care Centre' for the council. In addition, it is also the home of local democracy with a newly established Council Chamber and offices for Elected Members. The 'Housing Desk' is also in County Hall and the combined throughput for the Civic Hub.

5.1.3 Physical Twin post-Probono expected status

The final expected status is slightly different following the GBN building we consider:

- A. County Hall** will stay built as today with the addition of energy assets and other sensors in order to enable digital services (needs to be compliant with “heritage type” building). County Hall will have photovoltaic panels on the roof and battery storage in the basement enabling energy generation and storage. This will be integrated with a system that allows integrated mobility solutions (Mobility Hub) for the County Hall. System will include existing fleet of vehicles as well as exiting EV chargers and it will allow Vehicle to Building to Grid energy load balancing and energy trading utilizing a smart contract based distributed ledger technology. The building will have a two-way connection to the national energy grid.

- B. **Harbour Lodge** will stay built as today with the addition of energy assets and other sensors in order to enable digital services (need to be compliant with “heritage type” building)
- C. **Lexicon library** will stay built as today with the addition of energy assets and other sensors in order to enable digital services
- D. **Social Housing** target status is not yet defined.

5.1.4 Digital Twin High Level Needs requested

This section presents the four high-level needs of the DT linked to the LL of Dublin.

High Level Need	Physical domain	Functional domain
DUB-A Environmental conditions monitoring system	All	Environment management Human behaviour
DUB-B EV grid ecosystem	A Whole County	Energy Management
DUB-C Behaviour and life - work quality	All	Environment management Human behaviour
DUB-D Energy flows monitoring	All	Energy Management

Table 2: Dublin LL - DT High Level Need list

5.2 DUB-A - High Level Need: Environmental conditions monitoring system

5.2.1 Main objective

The main objective for this high-level need “Environmental condition system” is to gather environmental data inside and outside of the physical object.

Data collected by sensors or other sources needs to be managed through the whole life cycle to provide meaningful insights and analytics to the different stakeholders.

The benefits of this high-level need are tied to a better control and understanding of behaviour of inhabitants based on external environmental conditions and internal conditions. Data about internal conditions is collected using sensors. External conditions data is collected from sensors and external services (case of weather data). Secondary focus in this HL is waste management

system. Recycling is mandatory and a UC in this HL would handle recycling data: volumes or weight of each waste type.

Here is the list of the different use cases for the “Environmental conditions system” High-Level Need, that are detailed in the next subsections:

- **DUB-A-UC1:** Monitor external environmental conditions
- **DUB-A-UC2:** Monitor internal environmental conditions
- **DUB-A-UC3:** Manage and monitor HVAC performance
- **DUB-A-UC4:** Observe waste management performance

For all this following UCs, the Facility Manager will take benefits of the proposed tools to improve his data-driven decision making and so reducing negative environmental impact.

5.2.2 DUB-A-UC1: Monitor external environmental conditions

Use Case description

DT will consider and present the external(outside) environmental conditions such as temperature, humidity, wind speed and direction, outside noise, solar radiation, and air quality. By using sensors and data analytics, the digital twin can monitor the real-time conditions of the building and its surroundings. DT or facility manager can adjust the settings of the HVAC system, lighting system, shading devices and ventilation system accordingly. The digital twin can also predict the future environmental conditions based on historical data and weather forecasts, and plan ahead for optimal operation. The digital twin can also provide insights and recommendations for improving the design and maintenance of the building based on its performance history in the context of energy efficiency, sustainability, and enhance the building's resilience to climate change.

User / Actor

All actors can access data while some of actions are only limited to the certain level.

- Facility Manager – can fully access data and manage facilities. Has access to historical and projected data.
- Occupant – can fully access data and can manage limited facilities (setting a temperature in a single room not entire building). Has access to historical and projected data.
- HVAC system – can be programmed to use DT data and manage some of the facilities.

- Public/citizen – can access non-private data, see only aggregated data, and has access to historical and projected data.

User Scenario

These are the user scenarios for this use case:

- **Facility manager**

He is the facility manager of a commercial building that houses several offices and public spaces. He wants to optimize the energy efficiency, comfort and safety of the building and its occupants by using a digital twin software that can simulate its behaviour and performance under different external environmental conditions. Based on digital twin software he monitors and controls the HVAC system, lighting system, shading devices and ventilation system. He can access the digital twin interface from his laptop or smartphone anytime and anywhere. He can view real-time data on external environmental conditions. He can also interact with the digital twin by changing parameters or running simulations to explore different scenarios. For example, he can simulate maximum solar radiation. He can also receive alerts or notifications from the digital twin if there are any issues or anomalies in environmental data, both current and forecast.
- **Occupant**

He is a staff member in one of the office spaces in the building that uses a digital twin software. He wants to enjoy a comfortable and healthy indoor environment while working in his office. He can access the digital twin interface from his laptop or smartphone anytime and anywhere. Because he has fixed location system will only show relevant data for his current location in the building. For example, projection of sun radiation will consider the orientation of his office and windows. He can also view historical and projected data on the environmental conditions of his office and the building. He can also interact with the digital twin by setting a preferred internal environmental condition. The digital twin software will adjust the settings of the HVAC system, lighting system, shading devices and ventilation system accordingly within the limits set by the facility manager. The digital twin software will also provide him with feedback on how his preferences affect his comfort level and environmental impact. He can also receive alerts or notifications from the digital twin if there are any issues or anomalies in his office's operation.
- **HVAC system**

HVAC system is programable solution that can have dynamic triggers that result in action. When weather forecast predicts intensive rain, HVAC system will lower the temperature inside the building thus compensating for increased humidity. At the same time, it will increase ventilation and dehumidification.
- **Public/citizen**

Citizen who is interested in learning more about the environmental performance and impact of the county owned buildings in Dun Laoghaire. He wants to know how these buildings use energy, reduce emissions, and improve indoor air quality.

He can access the digital twin interface from public information kiosk. He can view real-time data on the average temperature, humidity, air quality and lighting level of each participating building in the city. He can also see comparison of different participating buildings or different neighbourhoods of the city based on their environmental performance and impact. The digital twin software will provide him with visualizations and summaries of the data in an easy-to-understand way. The digital twin software will also provide him with information on how the digital twin technology works and what benefits it brings to the building owners, managers, occupants, and society in general.

5.2.3 DUB-A-UC2: Monitor internal environmental conditions

Use Case description

A digital twin feature for internal environmental conditions of a building can help monitor and optimize the temperature, humidity, CO/CO₂, air quality, noise levels, and lighting of the building by using data from connected sensors and devices. The digital twin can also simulate different scenarios and outcomes based on changes in the internal environment or external factors such as weather or occupancy. This can help improve the comfort, safety, and efficiency of the building occupants.

User / Actor

All actors can access data while some of actions are only limited to the certain level.

- Facility Manager – can fully access data and manage facilities. Has access to historical and projected data.
- Occupant – can fully access data and can manage limited facilities (setting a temperature in a single room not entire building). Has access to historical and projected data.
- HVAC system – can be programmed to use DT data and manage some of the facilities.
- Public/citizen – can access non-private data, see only aggregated data, and has access to historical and projected data.

User Scenario

These are the user scenarios for this use case:

- **Facility manager**
He wants to use a digital twin feature for internal environmental conditions of a building to monitor and optimize the temperature, humidity, air quality, noise levels, and lighting in each of the offices (units) in the building by using data from connected sensors and devices. He wants to simulate different scenarios and outcomes based on

changes in the internal environment or external factors such as weather or occupancy. This will help him improve the comfort, safety, and efficiency of the building occupants. He can set thresholds and alerts for each condition so that he can be notified when they are out of range or need attention. He believes that right working conditions can increase satisfaction and productivity. He can also see number of occupants in each office. Some of the offices have precise location of staff and some just aggregated based on privacy settings. He can also see and respond to preferred internal environmental conditions and thresholds (e.g., noise and temperature) set by occupants.

He can view and configure digital twin from his personal computer or smartphone.

- **Occupant**

He wants to use a digital twin feature for internal environmental conditions of a building to monitor and optimize the temperature, humidity, air quality, noise levels, and lighting of his office. He also wants to access historical and projected data to see how the internal environment has changed over time or will change in the future.

He will use his personal computer or smartphone to see a dashboard that shows his the current internal (and external) environmental conditions. He can adjust the settings of each condition. For example, he can change the desired temperature or maximum level of noise in the office.

- **HVAC system**

HVAC system is programable solution that can have dynamic triggers that result in action. Based on input from occupants and facility manager, HVAC system can respond and comply.

- **Public/citizen**

Citizen who is interested in learning more about the environmental performance and impact of the county owned buildings in Dun Laoghaire. He wants to know how these buildings use energy, reduce emissions, and improve indoor air quality.

He can access the digital twin interface from public information kiosk. He can view real-time data on the internal environmental conditions and overall occupancy.

5.2.4 DUB-A-UC3: Manage and monitor HVAC performance

Use Case description

DT can monitor and optimize the performance of its HVAC systems by using sensors and data analytics. The use case also includes window state monitoring as a factor that affects the HVAC performance and indoor air quality. Data from HVAC system include performance and energy consumption. Window state is a feature that is enabled by window sensors. Window state can be binary or linear, depending on sensor type. HVAC system should consider window state to minimize waste of energy: reduce HVAC for an office if the window is open.

User / Actor

All actors can access data while some of actions are only limited to the certain level.

- Facility Manager – can fully access data and manage facilities. Has access to historical and projected data.
- Occupant – can fully access data and can manage limited facilities (setting a temperature in a single room not entire building). Has access to historical and projected data.
- HVAC system – can be programmed to use DT data and manage some of the facilities.

User Scenario

These are the user scenarios for this use case:

- **Facility manager**
He can see a dashboard displaying HVAC state at entire building as well as in each office. Dashboard display performance and state. He can also see state of windows in the building as well as in individual offices (zones). Zone is a single air volume; volumes are separated by walls and doors.
- **Occupant**
He can see a dashboard for the offices he is on. He can see state of HVAC system and state of the windows in the office and zone. He opens the window in the office to let some fresh air in. When window is opened, he can receive notification (on his smartphone) of this event. He is aware that HVAC is paused until window is opened. After a while he closes the window and HVAC resumes operation.
- **HVAC system**
HVAC normally responds to command. In case DT detects open window HVAC system responds with temporary pause of the operation for the affected zone.

5.2.5 DUB-A-UC4: Observe waste management performance

Use Case description

The system displays real-time data on the amount and type of waste generated and disposed by different zones in a building. Amount is measured in volume and/or weight. Digital Twin reports on performance in the terms of reducing general waste and increasing recycled waste. General goal of an entity is to reduce waste in general. System should report on historical data.

User / Actor

All actors can access data while some of actions are only limited to the certain level.

- Facility Manager – can fully access data and manage facilities. Has access to historical and projected data.

User Scenario

These are the user scenarios for this use case:

- **Facility manager**
On his smartphone or personal computer, he can monitor waste production over time. He can select timespan and type of waste he wants to monitor. If he finds that rate of recycling is declining or not sufficient, he can take alternative actions.

5.3 DUB-B - High Level Need: EV grid ecosystem

5.3.1 Main objective

The main objective for this high-level need “EV grid ecosystem” is to create a virtual representation of the physical grid assets and their interactions with electric vehicles (EVs) that can enable real-time monitoring, simulation, optimization and prediction of grid performance, reliability, and resilience.

A digital twin can help grid operators and planners to manage the increasing complexity and variability of EV charging demand, as well as to leverage EVs as flexible grid resources. A digital twin can also support environmental goals by reducing carbon emissions through smart design and operation. DT will consider information about energy flow between EV and charging infrastructure.

The benefits of this high-level need are tied to a better control and understanding of energy flows in EV infrastructure and understanding the use of EV and charging states to optimize charging processes in terms of time and energy efficiency.

Here is the list of the different use cases for this HL, that are detailed in the next subsections:

- **DUB-B-UC1:** Manage and track car park
- **DUB-B-UC2:** Monitor charging stations
- **DUB-B-UC3:** Monitor EV energy flow for EV - both input and output

For all the following UCs, the Facility Managers will take benefits of the proposed tools to improve their data-driven decision making and so reducing negative environmental impact.

5.3.2 DUB-B-UC1: Manage and track car park

Use Case description

The car park is a large facility with several charging stations for electric vehicles. The Facility manager wants to optimize the usage of these charging stations and monitor the charging status of the vehicles to ensure that they are always ready for the next staff member. Using this digital twin, the car park management can monitor who is using the vehicles and when they are being used. They can also monitor the charging status of the vehicles and determine which charging stations are being used the most and which ones are underutilized. Additionally, the digital twin can provide real-time alerts to the car park management in case any issues arise, such as a vehicle experiencing charging problems or a station being out of service.

User / Actor

All actors can access data while some of actions are only limited to the certain level.

- Facility Manager – can fully access data and manage facilities. Has access to historical and projected data.
- Staff member – can fully access data and can manage limited facilities.

User Scenario

These are the user scenarios for this use case:

- **Facility manager**
He logs into the digital twin user interface and views the dashboard that shows the current state of the car park, charging stations, and the EVs.
He notices that there are EV parked without being connected to the EV charger. He can create alarm for such case. He can access log of the drivers and contact and warn of staff member (driver) wrongdoings.
The facility manager reviews the historical data and reports generated by the digital twin and identifies some patterns and trends in parking behaviour and usage. He uses this information to plan and implement some improvements for the car park, such as adding more charging stations, installing solar panels, grid peak shaving, etc.
- **Staff member**
The staff member needs to use an EV from the car park for a work-related trip. He checks the availability and location of the EVs through the digital twin user interface on his smartphone. System will suggest an EV that has enough charge for his entire trip. He can see the remaining charge and other information about the EV on his smartphone or on the native dashboard of the EV. The staff member finishes his work and returns to the car park. He should connect EV to charging infrastructure.

5.3.3 DUB-B-UC2: Monitor charging stations

Use Case description

Dun Laoghaire wants to optimize the energy management and utilization of its multiple charging stations throughout the town and in the car park. The charging stations provide various types of charging (e.g., fast charging, slow charging) and can accommodate different vehicle models. The town uses a digital twin system that collects real-time data from the charging stations and their connected vehicles, such as charging type, current charge level, occupancy (parking sensor), etc.

The digital twin system can also alert the town about any anomalies or faults in the charging stations or their power converters. The digital twin system can also simulate different scenarios and test different strategies for improving the efficiency and reliability of the charging stations.

Digital twin should consider capacity of power grid and simulate grid load and suggest proper balancing strategy.

User / Actor

All actors can access data while some of actions are only limited to the certain level.

- Facility Manager – can fully access data and manage facilities. Has access to historical and projected data.

User Scenario

These are the user scenarios for this use case:

- **Facility manager**
He can view the real-time data and status of each charging station and its connected vehicles on a dashboard. He can adjust the charging parameters and schedules for each charging station or vehicle according to the recommendations from the digital twin system. He can receive alerts and notifications from the digital twin system if there are any anomalies or faults in the charging stations or their power converters. He can run simulations and tests on the digital twin system to evaluate different scenarios and strategies for improving the efficiency and reliability of the charging stations.

5.3.4 DUB-B-UC3: Monitor EV energy flow for EV - both input and output

Use Case description

The user wants to monitor and view the flow of energy into and from the EV at a charging point using a digital twin of the EV and its battery system. EV can be charged at charging point thus representing the input for EV. Next generation EV can also transfer energy back to the grid. Purpose of such system is to balance grid load and shave off energy peak demands.

Digital twin can help to plan and coordinate among electricity generators, distribution system operators and charging infrastructure.

User / Actor

All actors can access data while some of actions are only limited to the certain level.

- Facility Manager – can fully access data and manage facilities. Has access to historical and projected data.

User Scenario

These is the user scenario for this use case:

- **Facility manager**
He can login to the system using his personal computer or smartphone. He can access fleet of EV and zoom into an EV and inspect current energy flow. He can see precise units of energy going in and going out of the EV. Also, he can see history of energy flows for any vehicle. He can set limitations of energy flow to ensure vehicles have sufficient charge for normal operations.

5.4 DUB-C - High Level Need: Behaviour and life - work quality

5.4.1 Main objective

The main objective for this high-level need “Behaviour and life - work quality” is to provide insights into the quality of life and work experience of staff in an office environment. By monitoring staff occupancy, elevator use, incident reporting, staff food intake, use of air purifiers, and plants in the offices, together with data from previous use cases, the digital twin can help identify areas where improvements can be made to enhance the work environment and promote employee well-being.

By collecting and analysing data from various sources, the digital twin can provide a holistic view of the office environment, allowing organizations to identify patterns and trends that can help them optimize their operations and enhance the staff experience. By leveraging the power of data and analytics, the digital twin can provide valuable insights and recommendations that can help organizations create a more supportive and fulfilling work environment.

Here is the list of the different use cases for this HL, that are detailed in the next subsections:

- **DUB-C-UC1:** Analyse and optimize canteen food use
- **DUB-C-UC2:** Monitor occupancy

- **DUB-C-UC3:** Manage incident reporting and track progress
- **DUB-C-UC4:** Record elevator use
- **DUB-C-UC5:** Track environment quality enhancing artefacts.

For all this following UCs, the Facility Manager will take benefits of the proposed tools to improve his data-driven decision making and so reducing negative environmental impact.

5.4.2 DUB-C-UC1: Analyse and optimize canteen food use

Use Case description

The facility manager uses the digital twin of the building to monitor and optimize the food consumption and waste in the canteen. The digital twin provides data on food inventory, demand, quality, and disposal. The facility manager can adjust the food supply and menu based on the data analysis and feedback from the canteen staff. The goal is to reduce food waste, improve staff satisfaction, and save costs.

User / Actor

All actors can access data while some of actions are only limited to the certain level.

- Facility Manager – can fully access data and manage facilities. Has access to historical and projected data.
- Staff member – can fully access data and can manage limited facilities. Has access to historical and projected data.

User Scenario

These are the user scenarios for this use case:

- **Facility manager**
He accesses the canteen food performance feature using its personal computer or a smartphone. The system shows a graphical representation of the food inventory, demand, quality, and waste disposal data for the current day, week, month, or any time range. The facility manager can filter, sort, and compare the data by different criteria such as time, type, source, nutritional composition, ...
The system also provides suggestions and recommendations based on the data analysis and nutritional trends. The facility manager wants to reduce food waste while increasing the quality of food intake of staff. He doesn't decide on actual menu because that is responsibility of subcontractors. But he can, if anomaly is identified, express his concerns to the subcontractor.
- **Staff member**

He accesses the digital twin system using their mobile device or a terminal in the canteen.

The system displays the current food menu and availability for the staff member to choose from. Together with nutritional composition of each menu item. On the same menu staff member is encouraged to use only what he can eat thus reducing food waste. Short statistics of food waste is displayed on the screen. He can see trend (positive or negative) of amount of food waste staff members generate.

5.4.3 DUB-C-UC2: Monitor occupancy

Use Case description

The facility manager uses the digital twin dashboard to view the current and historical occupancy data of different spaces and offices in the building. The manager can filter, sort, and export the data according to various criteria such as date, time, floor, zone, or room type. The manager can also set up alerts and notifications for when certain occupancy thresholds are reached or exceeded. The goal of this use case is to enable the manager to optimize space utilization, energy efficiency, and occupant comfort in the building. Occupancy can suddenly increase if there are events organized in some zones of the building. System should learn from such cases and predict increased occupancy in the future.

User / Actor

All actors can access data while some of actions are only limited to the certain level.

- Facility Manager – can fully access data and manage facilities. Has access to historical and projected data.
- Staff member – can fully access data and can manage limited facilities. Has access to historical and projected data.

User Scenario

These are the user scenarios for this use case:

- **Facility manager**
He wants to monitor the space and office occupancy of his building to optimize space utilization, energy efficiency, and occupant comfort. He logs into the digital twin dashboard on his personal computer and sees a 3D model of his building with color-coded indicators showing the current occupancy level of each floor, zone, and room. He clicks on different areas to see more details such as the number of occupants, the temperature, the humidity, and the air quality. He notices that some rooms are overcrowded while others are underutilized. He decides to adjust the HVAC settings and rearrange some furniture to create more comfortable spaces for his tenants. He

also sets up alerts and notifications for when certain occupancy thresholds are reached or exceeded so he can act quickly if needed.

- **Staff member**

He uses a digital twin system to monitor and manage the space and office occupancy. He wants to find a suitable place to work for the day that meets his preferences and needs. He opens the digital twin app on his smartphone and sees a 3D model of the building with color-coded indicators showing the current occupancy level of each floor, zone, and room. He filters the available spaces by his criteria such as proximity to his team members, availability of power outlets, natural light, and privacy, office equipment, etc. He finds a spot that matches his preferences and makes a reservation using external office reservation system.

5.4.4 DUB-C-UC3: Manage incident reporting and track progress

Use Case description

The facility manager can access report of incident reported that are related to equipment failure (such as ventilation, broken window, faulty faucet etc.) in the digital twin system.

The maintenance staff can update the status and resolution of the incident in the system. The facility manager can track the progress and history of all incidents in the system.

User / Actor

All actors can access data while some of actions are only limited to the certain level.

- Facility Manager – can fully access data and manage facilities. Has access to historical and projected data.
- Staff member – can fully access data and can manage limited facilities. Has access to historical and projected data.
- Maintenance staff – can fully access data and can manage incident states.

User Scenario

These are the user scenarios for this use case:

- **Facility manager**

He logs into the digital twin system every morning to check if there are any new incidents reported by the staff. He sees that there is a new incident related to a faulty faucet in one of the kitchenettes. He clicks on the incident ID and sees the details of the problem, such as location, reporter (person), severity and description. He assigns one of his maintenance staff to fix the faucet and sets a deadline for completion. He then checks the status of other incidents that are in progress or resolved. He can see how long each incident took to resolve and what actions were taken by the

maintenance staff. He can also generate reports on various metrics such as number of incidents per building, average resolution time, most common problems etc. He uses these reports to improve maintenance planning and budgeting.

- **Staff member**

He notices that there is a broken faucet in the kitchenette. He decides to report the incident to the digital twin system. He logs into the system and fills out a form with details of the problem, such as location, severity, and description. He also uploads a photo of the broken window. The system assigns an incident ID and confirms that his report has been received.

He can see the status and resolution of his incident in the system. He can also see who is assigned to fix it and when it will be done. He receives a message from assigned maintenance staff, informing him that he will come to fix the window soon.

He can also see other incidents reported by his colleagues or himself in the past.

- **Maintenance staff**

On his smartphone he receives notifications from the digital twin system whenever he is assigned to fix an incident related to equipment failure. He can see the details of the incident, such as location, severity, description and deadline.

He can also see the contact information of the staff member who reported the incident. He goes to the location of the problem and fixes it as soon as possible. He then updates the status and resolution of the incident in the system. He can see his performance statistics such as number of incidents resolved, average resolution time, feedback ratings etc. He uses these statistics to improve his skills and efficiency.

5.4.5 DUB-C-UC4: Record elevator use

Use Case description

The facility manager uses a digital twin of the building to monitor the frequency and duration of elevator use by different floors and zones. The digital twin provides real-time data and analytics on elevator performance and energy consumption. The facility manager can identify patterns and trends in elevator usage, such as peak hours, busy zones, or frequent users. The facility manager can also set goals and incentives for reducing elevator use, such as displaying health benefits, offering rewards, or sending reminders. The facility manager can track the progress and impact of these interventions on elevator usage and occupant health.

User / Actor

All actors can access data while some of actions are only limited to the certain level.

- Facility Manager – can fully access data and manage facilities. Has access to historical and projected data.
- Staff member – can fully access data and can manage limited facilities. Has access to historical and projected data.

User Scenario

These are the user scenarios for this use case:

- **Facility manager**
He logs into his dashboard and sees that elevator use has increased by 5% in the past week. He notices that most of the elevator trips are between floors 1-3. He also sees that some occupants use the elevator more than twice a day.
He decides to set a goal of reducing elevator use by 10% in one month.
He chooses to display health benefits on each floor near the elevator doors, such as how many calories are burned by taking the stairs or how much CO2 is saved by avoiding the elevator. This is displayed on a terminal (tablet or screen). This screen also has motivational messages to encourage use of stairs.
- **Staff member**
He approaches elevator and notices information terminal and sees health benefit of using the stairs. He decides to use stairs instead.

5.4.6 DUB-C-UC5: Track environment quality enhancing artefacts

Use Case description

Occupant can use a digital twin of a building to view the current environment quality indicators such as air quality, temperature, humidity, etc. The occupant can also see suggestions for objects that can improve the environment quality and their ideal locations based on the digital twin model and simulation. Facility manager can monitor change in environmental quality based on instalment of such objects. Object can be a simple plant or high-tech air purifier

User / Actor

All actors can access data while some of actions are only limited to the certain level.

- Facility Manager – can fully access data and manage facilities. Has access to historical and projected data.
- Staff member – can fully access data and can manage limited facilities. Has access to historical and projected data.

User Scenario

These are the user scenarios for this use case:

- **Facility manager**
He wants to monitor and control the environment quality of different rooms in the building using a digital twin interface so that he can optimize comfort level for the occupants by encouraging instalment of working environment enhancing objects.
- **Staff member**

He wants to view and adjust the environment quality settings of his personal workspace using a digital twin interface so that he can work in a comfortable and healthy environment. He purchases a plant and adds it to the system at exact location. After some time plant withers, so he is obliged to report that to the system, and it is removed from Digital Twin.

5.5 DUB-D - High Level Need: Energy flow monitoring

5.5.1 Main objective

Main objective is to model and optimize the energy consumption and production of a building by using a virtual representation that can simulate the real-time dynamics of energy flows and variables.

A digital twin can help in saving the environment by decarbonizing the energy systems and increasing the use of renewable energy sources. It can also help in improving the performance and reliability of energy operations by detecting faults and anomalies, forecasting maintenance needs, and testing scenarios in a safe environment.

Energy flows can be monitored on various levels where one I certainly at production site (PV). Another data collection point is building energy bill where total can be interpreted. However, energy consumption can be monitored inside a building, for example TV has built in energy monitor that can be an input for digital twin.

Here is the list of the different use cases for this HL, that are detailed in the next subsections:

- **DUB-D-UC1:** Monitor flow of energy, energy cost, and storage
- **DUB-D-UC2:** Track energy consumers
- **DUB-D-UC3:** Track DT to DT energy flow
- **DUB-D-UC4:** Control DT systems remotely for peak avoidance.

For all this following UCs, the Facility Manager will take benefits of the proposed tools to improve his data-driven decision making and so reducing negative environmental impact.

5.5.2 DUB-D-UC1: Monitor flow of energy, energy cost, and storage

Use Case description

This use case allows monitoring the flow of energy, energy cost, and storage for a digital twin of a building. Building has various energy sources like solar, grid power, gas, ... To minimize load on the grid building have battery storage units that store energy to be used in peak times. Together with EV as storage units this can be even further optimized.

Digital twin users can access a dashboard that displays real-time data on the energy production, consumption, cost, and storage levels of the building. The user can also view historical trends and forecasts for these metrics.

User / Actor

All actors can access data while some of actions are only limited to the certain level.

- Facility Manager – can fully access data and manage facilities. Has access to historical and projected data.

User Scenario

These are the user scenarios for this use case:

- **Facility manager**
He wants to monitor current energy flows in the building, He uses a tablet to access a dashboard that displays real-time data on the flow of energy on a various level of the building (digital twin). He can see energy cost based on type of energy.
He wants to see energy input structure, he is curious how much energy is sourced from renewables, system generates a report for him. Based on report he can make energy planning and decisions, thus optimizing the energy efficiency and cost savings of the building.
Building that he manages has battery storage and EV as batter storage. He can see and analyse current energy levels in the storage to minimize load on the grid during peak times. He is in touch with grid representative and can agree on peak times and decide to use stored energy when time is right.

5.5.3 DUB-D-UC2: Track energy consumers

Use Case description

The building manager uses the digital twin of a building to try to track each individual energy consumer in the building and offices. The system attributes each unit to its respective owner and displays the energy consumption data on a dashboard. Each consumer is connected to energy tracking smart sensor that delivers the data to the DT system. The building manager can monitor and optimize the energy efficiency of the building using this information.

User / Actor

All actors can access data while some of actions are only limited to the certain level.

- Facility Manager – can fully access data and manage facilities. Has access to historical and projected data.
- Staff member – can fully access data and can manage limited facilities. Has access to historical and projected data.

User Scenario

These are the user scenarios for this use case:

- **Facility manager**
He logs into the digital twin of the building system using his credentials. He sees a dashboard that shows the energy consumption data of each individual unit in the building and offices. He can filter, sort, and compare the data by different criteria, such as owner, floor, type, time period and so on. He can also see the total energy consumption of the building and how it compares to other buildings in his portfolio. He notices that some units are consuming more energy than expected and decides to investigate further. He clicks on a unit and sees its detailed energy profile, including its appliances, devices, sensors, and settings. He can also see historical trends and patterns of energy usage for that unit. He identifies some possible causes of high energy consumption, such as outdated equipment, faulty wiring, or inefficient settings. He contacts the owner of the unit and suggests some ways to improve their energy efficiency. He also updates his own records and plans for future maintenance and upgrades.
- **Staff member**
As a staff member, he wants to see his energy consumption data on the digital twin of the building system so that he can monitor and reduce his energy usage. He sees his energy consumption data for his unit on a dashboard, he can filter, sort, and compare my data by different criteria, such as appliance, device, sensor, setting, time period and so on. He can see historical trends and patterns of his energy usage. He can see tips and suggestions for improving his energy efficiency.

5.5.4 DUB-D-UC3: Track DT to DT energy flow

Use Case description

This use case demonstrates how two digital twins of buildings can exchange energy that can be sourced by renewable energy sources such as solar panels or battery storage. One digital twin can model the energy production and consumption of its building and transfer the excess energy to another digital twin that needs it. The other digital twin can receive the energy and adjust its

energy demand accordingly. The use case can help optimize the energy efficiency and sustainability of both buildings. Data is retrieved using sensors at energy input and outputs

User / Actor

All actors can access data while some of actions are only limited to the certain level.

- Facility Manager – can fully access data and manage facilities. Has access to historical and projected data.

User Scenario

These are the user scenarios for this use case:

- **Facility manager**
He wants to monitor and control the energy flow between two or more buildings using digital twins, so that he can reduce the energy costs and carbon footprint of his buildings.
He logs in to the dashboard and can monitor real time energy flow and type of it (solar, grid, gas...)

5.5.5 DUB-D-UC4: Control DT systems remotely for peak avoidance

Use Case description

The external energy provider sends a request to the digital twin system of a building to perform an action that will lower its energy usage, such as adjusting the thermostat or turning off some lights. The digital twin system receives the request and executes the action accordingly after it has been approved by facility manager. The digital twin system then sends a confirmation message back to the external energy provider.

User / Actor

All actors can access data while some of actions are only limited to the certain level.

- Facility Manager – can fully access data and manage facilities. Has access to historical and projected data.
- Energy provider – can access current and historical data (read only) and can request energy reducing action.

User Scenario

These are the user scenarios for this use case:

- **Facility manager**

Using personal computer or smartphone he accesses the dashboard where he can receive energy reduction request. He decides to comply by invoking HVAC shutdown and sending a message to all occupants to take a break for 15 minutes and turn off all consumers except essential equipment.

He can monitor drop in energy consumption.

- **Energy provider**

He experiences sudden load that can't be handled properly, using digital twin interface he notices that system energy load can be reduced and decides to send energy reduction request for specified time.

5.6 Data - Inventory and requirements

Linked use cases	Dataset name	Dataset content description	Data provider	Static or dynamic	Dataset availability
DUB-B-UC3 DUB-D	Electric Energy Meter reading	Monthly meter reading	Meters Energy elephant platform	dynamic	yes
DUB-D-UC1	Gas Meter Reading	Monthly meter reading	Meters Energy elephant platform	dynamic	yes
DUB-D-UC1 DUB-B-UC3	Gas and Energy Pricing	Monthly bills	Energy and gas tariffs (yearly)	dynamic	yes
DUB-A-UC3	HVAC	Sensor reading	DLR	dynamic	No, when sensors are installed
DUB-D-UC1	Woodchip	Monthly reading, woodchip weight	Energy elephant	dynamic	yes
DUB-A-UC1 DUB-A-UC2	BMS	Temperature, set point, energy consumption	N/A	dynamic	Not yet
DUB-A-UC1 DUB-A-UC2 DUB-C-UC2	CO2, Humidity, Temperature Occupancy	CO2, Humidity, Temperature Occupancy	Ambisence	dynamic	yes
DUB-B-UC3	EV charging station state	Current charging station status	Multiple providers	dynamic	no
DUB-B-UC3	EV vehicle status	Vehicle data including location, current user and charge status and charge levels		dynamic	no
DUB-A-UC1	Current weather data on precise location and forecast	Sun radiation (sun position in time) Clouds Temperature Humidity Wind Precipitation	weather api	dynamic	yes

Linked use cases	Dataset name	Dataset content description	Data provider	Static or dynamic	Dataset availability
DUB-A-UC1 DUB-A-UC2	Air quality	Google air quality Sensor attached at the outside of the building at various levels (height)	Google and unknown	dynamic	yes
DUB-A-UC1 DUB-A-UC2	Noise level	Sensor readings around the building at various levels and inside of building at various places	DLR	dynamic	No, when sensors are installed
DUB-A-UC2	Lightning level	Sensor readings inside building	DLR	dynamic	No, when sensors are installed
DUB-A-UC3	Windows state	Sensor readings inside building	DLR	dynamic	No, when sensors are installed
DUB-A-UC3 DUB-B-UC3	HVAC source	Energy consumption of HVAC	DLR	dynamic	No
DUB-A-UC4	Waste management report	Report on waste production	DLR	dynamic	No, when procedure or sensors are established
DUB-B-UC1	Car park state	Current charge status and levels and parking location for each vehicle in the fleet	DLR	dynamic	No, when sensors are installed
DUB-B-UC2 DUB-B-UC3	Charging station network	Location and state of our charging network		dynamic	no
DUB-C-UC1	Weekly meal report	Canteen delivers report on meal preparation and consumption also a report on waste produced	DLR (canteen contractor)	dynamic	no
DUB-C-UC2	Person location	Staff use their card for presence and time tracking	DLR (staff management system)	dynamic	yes (partially)
DUB-C-UC2	Presence detection	Staff is usually assigned to particular office or location, where presence/counter sensors are to be installed. Citizens are also included, and they are localized to public service area.	DLR	dynamic	no
DUB-C-UC3	Incident reports	Incidents that are reported by staff	DLR	dynamic	no
DUB-C-UC4	Elevator reading	There are more than one elevator and current elevator state should be visible	DLR	dynamic	no

Linked use cases	Dataset name	Dataset content description	Data provider	Static or dynamic	Dataset availability
DUB-C-UC5	Interior setup report	Map of interior elements like plants and air purifiers.	DLR	dynamic	no

Table 3: Dublin LL - Data inventory

5.7 Decision-making tools – Inventory and requirements

Linked use cases	Tool name	Tool/model description	Tool provider	Type (AI models, Simulation models, BIM, digital twin,...)	Input data	Output data
DUB-A	Suite of Sensors	model for predictive maintenance (given time series for elevator, ventilation, and boiler)	DLR, TPF, STAM	AI models	time series	usage, predicted usage
DUB-B	Suite of Sensors	model for detecting anomalies	DLR, TPF, STAM?	CAD	time series knowing past state	3 states: working/malfunctional/non-working system
DUB-C	Energy Trading	Energy trading system for the EV charging station in County Hall	BovLabs	Energy prediction model	Energy readings, loads etc	Energy savings
DUB-D	Occupancy Monitoring	Occupancy data for County Hall	DLR, Ambisense	Occupancy Data	CO2 Detection	Internal air quality
DUB-D	Energy Retrofit Scenario Testing	Energy generation and usage model	DLR, Mitsubishi	BIM Energy generation and management	kwh, generation, usage	Building efficiency

Table 4: Dublin LL - Decision making tools inventory

5.8 Visualization tools – Inventory and requirements

Linked use cases	Tool name	Tool description	Type	Tool provider
DUB-A-UC4	EnPower - Community module	Dashboard hosted on web application with knowledge and communication management system	web application	STAM
DUB-B	EVCarPark Viewer	Web application that displays a car park state with EV charging station	Web application	Not defined yet
DUB-C-UC4	ElevatorApp	Android app that displays elevator use over time, it encourages staff to use the stairs. It will explain how much energy is saved and calories used. Application is	Web application	Not defined yet

Linked use cases	Tool name	Tool description	Type	Tool provider
		hosted on a tablet that is positioned next to elevator entrance.		
DUB-D	EnergyFlows	Web application that is shown on large screen in the lobby. It visually displays input and output of energy, graphics of consumption/production over time as well as sources and destinations of energy	Web application	Not defined yet
DUB-A	Environmental monitor	Web application that is shown on large screen displaying external and internal environmental conditions in 3D space	Web application	Not defined yet
DUB	Digital twin manager	Complete 3D viewer and manager for entire DT instances.	Preferably web application	Not defined yet

Table 5: Dublin LL - Visualisation tools inventory

5.9 DT & external systems – Interoperability requirements

Linked use cases	Title	Description	Data exchanged	Protocol used
DUB-A, DUB-C, DUB-D	HVAC	HVAC system in the building(s)	Set temperature, flow rates, energy consumption	REST API
DUB-A, DUB-B, DUB-D	Energy provider	Energy provider will not be only source of data but rather an actuator; the case of reducing energy consumption during peak demand	Energy input and output	REST API

Table 6: Dublin LL - external systems

Figure 9: Dublin LL - UC Diagram

AS-IS situation

About county hall, a network of sensors will be deployed to measure this dynamic situation and inform decision making in relation to the retrofit options best suited to meet these needs. This would ultimately allow for the automation of energy management in this dynamic environment.

This table list the different tool used today to provide Energy Monitoring and forecasting need:

Physical Twin Name	AS-IS - DUB-A
County Hall	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ SketchUp (designPH) digital models ▪ 2 LoRa IOT gateway (provide by Cellnex and Cognition an Irish SME) with energy, environmental and occupancy sensors ▪ Dashboards ▪ Energy elephant platform (submetering) ▪ Heat dissipation models (localized in some rooms)
Harbor Lodge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ LoRa IOT gateway (provided by Cellnex and Cognition an Irish SME)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Heat dissipation (localized in some rooms)
Lexicon library	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ LoRa IOT gateway (provided by cellnex and cognition Irish SME) ▪ BMS ▪ Energy elephant platform ▪ Access counters
Social housing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 1100 smart thermostats ▪ Beaufort HVAC system

Table 7: Dublin LL - Tools that could be used for the DT High Level Needs

Note

Deployment of metering and sub-metering devices to Lexicon library and Harbor Lodge leveraging existing LoRa Gateways and city IOT network if possible

5.10 Additional requirements

- **User access control (UAC)**

DT manager should be able to manage visibility of each DT element/object for specific users or group of users. DT manager manages repository of users that have access and their privileges on specific DT element.

Any DT element can have properties that can have various user access levels. For example: “Building waste monitoring” has properties: total volume, volume per waste type. Total volume can be accessed by public while volume per waste type can be accessed only by staff members and facility manager.

- **Layout editor:**

For each DT instance we would like to be able to edit layout of space and elements. Each element can be enabled or disabled. Furthermore, element can be added and removed anytime during DT lifetime.

- **Localization**

Each object in DT should be localized using following rules:

- Precisely (x,y,z)
- Approximated (x,y,z with offset radius = sphere)

- Polyhedron, can be defined during layout editing, examples are:
 - Room level
 - Rooms level
 - Floor level
 - Custom region/zone
 - Entire building level

Please note that UAC should be defined based on abovementioned levels. For example, Staff member could be able to see occupancy per floor, but manager should be able to access precise occupancy.

- **Secure API**

DT API should be secured using latest security standards.

- **Action triggering**

Each DT element/object can have properties where each user can define alert conditions. For example: if temperature at location (x,y,z) reaches 25°C then DT should invoke registered REST request, or email notification.

- **Data prediction**

DT should predict data using standard statistical models as well as AI trained on historical data over all datasets for specific data.

- **Data source**

DT element/object data should be provided by both: DT API, external API calls (by DT, usually periodically).

6 MGP - Madrid Geothermal Plant Living Lab

6.1 Living Lab Context

6.1.1 Location

Madrid Nuevo Norte (MNN) is a part of a public initiative of Madrid City Council aiming to regenerate 300 hectares of land in the North of the Spanish Capital. The project was approved in July 2020 with the modification of the “Madrid City Area Masterplan” to the most innovative, citizen oriented and sustainable urban standards.

Figure 10: Madrid LL - Location of Madrid Nuevo Norte (in white)

Figure 11: Madrid LL - Global distribution of land uses in Madrid Nuevo Norte

Figure 12: Madrid LL – Distribution of uses of the land and building types

The LL area, Las Tablas Oeste (APE.08.21), has common infrastructures to the rest of the areas, Chamartín Station (APR. 05.10), Chamartín Business District (APE.05.30), Malmea-San Roque-Tres Olivos (APE.08.20), that must be planned jointly, such as energy infrastructure, telecommunications, drinking water supply and irrigation, wastewater, and mobility infrastructure, leaving local networks as the sole competencies of each compensation board. However, the 4 areas have independence in their development and will be executed by independent Compensation Boards (Association of owners) and the Madrid City Council with responsibility for carrying out the constructive design of the project and its execution, over the course of the whole process, including all infrastructures, parks and public space.

Figure 13: MGP LL - Geothermal plant information

6.1.2 Physical Twin Composition

The Madrid Nuevo Norte Living Lab is composed of the following elements:

- 2 buildings with different usages:
 - o 50% of offices
 - o 42% of residential
 - o 8% of commercial
- 1 District Heating and Cooling Network
 - o 60-80 geothermal boreholes with a depth of 125-150m
 - o 0,5 MW geothermal module integrated in the public space
 - o Distribution and geothermal pipes
- Solar panels
- 2nd life batteries

6.1.3 Physical Twin users

The Living Lab will provide service to 120 households (more than 300 residents) and more than 1.000 employees.

6.1.4 Physical Twin Current Status

This is about a new construction. The Physical Twin doesn't exist yet. Work is scheduled to start in December 2023.

6.1.5 Physical Twin post-Probono expected status

Figure 14: MGP LL - Map of the geothermal plant

Figure 15: MGP LL - Geothermal plant 3D view and description

The Madrid Living Lab will consist of:

- Construction of the low temperature district heating and cooling (DHCN) geothermal network
- Construction of 2 buildings (not included in the PROBONO budget)

- Urbanization project development in Las Tablas Oeste (not included in the PROBONO budget) coordinated with the geothermal network
- Thermo-activation of the buildings connected to the geothermal network
- Electricity network and 2nd life batteries to compensate the energy used for the geothermal network
- The buildings will include a heat pump in order to increase DHCN temperature for heat water use.

6.1.6 Digital Twin High Level Needs requested

High Level Need	Physical domain	Functional domain
MGP-A Heating requirement forecasting	2 Buildings at room level	Energy Management (Thermal forecasting at room level)
MGP-B DHCN smart management	The buildings and the DHC network	Energy Management (DHCN Decision Support System)
MGP-C User profiling for DHCN data reporting / User empowerment	DHCN	Energy Management Human behaviour (DHCN reporting)

Table 8: MGP LL - DT High Level Need list

Figure 16 shows a conceptual overview of the Madrid geothermal plant digital twin, where three layers can be distinguished: physical world, digital world and high-level services. The digital world is a digital representation of the part of the physical world that is interesting within the Madrid geothermal plant Digital Twin, and the high-level services layer contains the different services that should be offered to different users such as:

- Facility manager or building operator
- Building owner
- Inhabitants and dwelling owners
- Renewable energy community as an entity
- General public (in order to provide information anonymized and aggregated information in order to be aligned with the GDPR)
- ACCIONA’s control system

Figure 16: MGP LL - Conceptual overview of Madrid geothermal plant DT

6.2 MGP-A - High Level Need: Heating requirement forecasting

6.2.1 Main objective

The main objective for this high-level need “Heating energy forecasting” is to forecast the thermal requirements at room level based on data information such as weather, user patterns, static information about the buildings... Only this use-case is treated in this high-level need: forecast thermal requirement to heat rooms.

6.2.2 MGP-A-UC1: Forecast thermal requirement to heat/cold rooms

Use Case description

The main objective of this use case is to forecast the user thermal requirements for the different rooms in the buildings connected to provide to the user proper thermal comfort using less energy as possible and so less cost and less environmental impacts. It is supposed that the temperature is well established if the user does not need to change the thermostat setpoint.

This should be estimated according to weather conditions and user patterns (setpoint changes, occupancy...) using artificial intelligence. AI mechanisms should be used to forecast the temperature for each room 24 hours in advance.

If the information needed by the AI forecasting modules is available through a database/API or hub, direct access to the sensors/actuators would not be needed (it is supposed that the monitoring use cases will gather monitoring data and store it in a kind of database). The information inferred by the AI forecasting modules would be given to the main “actor agent” of the DT (or stored in a database, or offered through an API), that would be the one interacting with the sensors (considering all the information coming from the different modules).

Rooms should be replicated in the DT in this case to gather the information needed by the AI modules to perform their functionality. Weather information (forecasted) is also needed in this case, and maybe static information about the buildings (BIM models LoD300 approximately). Data concerning user habits and set-point changes would be useful too.

User / Actor

The actor “Time” which will start the execution of the use case once a day.

The actor DHCN operation and maintenance entity will use the DT to get the needed information so that they could take decisions (more or less heat/cold) concerning DHCN operation.

Scenario

A possible scenario: one day (e.g. February, 26th, at 9:00 a.m.) the user of one dwelling changes the setpoint of the thermostat from 21 to 22, so the situation is that, for this user, this day, 21°C seems not to be enough so, maybe, if this behaviour occurs more times, the system should learn and give as an output that, on Mondays, at this hour (9:00 a.m.), the temperature in this dwelling or room should be greater.

It is supposed that this use case would be executed every 24 hours, in order to give a 24-hour forecast.

6.3 MGP-B - High Level Need: DHCN smart management

6.3.1 Main objective

The main objective of this high-level need is to carry out the proper actions concerning optimal DHCN operation and maintenance based on the inputs coming from AI forecasting modules and other inputs that would be needed.

This DT replicates the DHCN in order to calculate all the KPIs needed to help the DHCN operators on the decision-making process.

No physical interaction is needed in the scope of this high-level need (it is supposed that the monitored information will be stored in a database, so this use cases will access it, not the physical devices).

Here is the list of the three use cases for this High-Level Need, that are detailed in the next subsections:

- **MGP-B-UC1** Calculate KPI values needed by the decision support system
- **MGP-B-UC2** Provide KPI optimisation guidelines
- **MGP-B-UC3** Help decision making to manage DHCN.

6.3.2 MGP-B-UC1: Calculate KPI value needed by the DHCN decision support system

Use Case description

The DT will provide the needed KPIs to guide the decision-making process concerning the operation and maintenance of the DHCN.

First list of identified KPIs to be calculated within this use case (and then, used in the following use cases):

- Ground temperature profile [°C] (for 1-2 boreholes)
- Seasonal thermal balance in the ground
- Geothermal power for each borehole
- % of energy generated by the ground for each energy thermal unit (heat) produced
- % of energy generated by the ground for each energy thermal unit (cold) produced
- Seasonal coefficient of performance (SCOP) (coefficient of performance averaged over the length of the heating season)
- Seasonal energy efficiency ratio (SEER) (concerning cooling)
- Average temperature of the exchanges with the ground (average among outputs and inputs) (ground source exchange average)
- Average usage temperature (both for heating and cooling)
- Average of PV consumed by each Heat Pump (and % of the whole electricity consumed that comes from PV)

User / Actor

The use cases linked to this high-level need are always “in operation”, and maybe it is the “actor time” that would start a particular action (the systems check, periodically, if thermal setpoints are being satisfied; if not, actions should be taken).

In most of the use cases, the use case will be started by an actor “Time”, but we can distinguish other actors such as:

- Facilities manager

Scenario example

When it is time of calculation, the use case will take the formula for each KPI and, based on the values of the measurements linked with the formula, it will calculate the value for the KPI. No interaction with the user is done at this moment. The user that starts the use case is the actor Time (periodically), and the values of the KPIs should be stored in order to make them available for the rest of use cases.

6.3.3 MGP-B-UC2 Provide KPI optimisation guidelines

Use Case description

This use case will help the actor “DHCN manager” to receive information on how to optimize the values of the KPIs. Based on the formulas used to calculate the KPIs, information on how to optimize its values will be given (e.g. if the formula of a KPI consists on a division, the value of the KPI will be greater if we make the dividend lower, and it will be lower if the dividend is greater).

User / Actor

The actor that will usually start this use case is the “DHCN manager” and/or, if needed, the actor Time it is desirable to have “pop up” recommendations, not requested by the user.

Scenario example

For the KPIs whose formulas are based on a division, the system can inform the manager that, in order to make greater the value for those KPIs, the value of the divider should be lower and/or the dividend greater. By contrast, if the objective is to make the value of the KPI lower, the divider should be greater and/or the dividend lower.

6.3.4 MGP-B-UC3: Help decision making to manage DHCN

Use Case description

This use case is related to assist the decision-making process in order to help the “DHCN manager” to optimally manage the DHCN. Based on the values of the KPIs and maybe also based

on monitoring values i.e. measurements, not only KPIs, suggestions on how to manage the DHCN should be offered to the person in charge of managing the DHCN. Once the KPIs have been decided, suggestions based on their values should be generated, and this information should be used in the scope of this DHCN in order to help the manager of the DHCN facilities.

User / Actor

This use case will interact with the DHCN manager.

Scenario:

If the pressure of the circuit is lower than the average value within the last X hours/days (the most common way of detecting that something is getting “wrong” is comparing the current values with the “averages ones”), then the system could send a message informing that, maybe, the sensor that is measuring this value has been broken or there is a leakage in the system. ’

6.4 MGP-C - High Level Need: User profiling for DHCN data reporting / user empowerment

6.4.1 Main objective

The main objective of this DT high level need is to offer information about economic and energy performance of the DHCN (information as a whole for the renewable energy community, particularized information for individual user or general information for the general public but, in this case, information should be anonymized in order to be aligned with the GDPR). One of the main aims of giving information to the users is to empower them and make them aware of the situation (consumption, performance...) of the facilities in every moment. Different levels of information (different dashboards) should be shown based on the role of the user is asking for them.

Both the DHCN and the buildings should be replicated in the DT, but just in order to gather information about its operation.

In this high-level need, no interaction with physical twin components is needed, because it is supposed that the information would be already available through a database or data hub.

As aforementioned, GDPR should be always considered.

Here is the list of the different use cases for the “Energy Monitoring and forecasting” High-Level Need, that are detailed in the next subsections:

- **MGP-C-UC1** Visualize and report KPIs
- **MGP-C-UC2** Monitor historical (and current) data reporting (for different actors)
- **MGP-C-UC3** Provide recommendations about energy consumption.

6.4.2 MGP-C-UC1: Visualize and report KPIs based on user profile

Use Case description

KPI visualization and reporting for different actors, different information and in a different way should be shown based on the actor who is asking for it. Different KPIs could be shown here such as KPIs used within the KPI-driven decision support system (see MGP-B-UC3), assessment KPIs (see the use cases described within WP6), comfort KPIs (e.g. PMV, PPD) ...

Apart from the visualization of KPIs using dashboards (including appropriate graphs, filtering controls and so on), the possibility of generating reports containing information from the dashboards should be also offered.

User / Actor

Main actors: DHCN manager, building operator, building owner, inhabitants and dwelling owners, renewable energy community as a whole and general public.

6.4.3 MGP-C-UC2: Visualize and report monitoring data based on user profile

Use Case description

In this use case, the DT will provide the different users with reports and dashboards containing historical monitoring data and maybe also real/current monitoring data, if needed. Different information (and in a different way) should be provided based on the actor who is asking for it.

Apart from the visualization of monitoring data using dashboards including appropriate graphs, filtering controls and so on, the possibility of generating reports containing information from the dashboards should be also offered.

User / Actor

Main actors: DHCN manager, building operator, building owner, inhabitants and dwelling owners, and renewable energy community as a whole. GDPR should be always considered.

6.4.4 MGP-C-UC3: Provide recommendations about energy consumption

Use Case description

Recommendations related to energy consumption reduction (and also reducing the energy bill) will be generated and sent to the user in the scope of this use case. Both “general” and dedicated recommendations could be offered (e.g.- “General” suggestions: try not to open the windows if it is cold outside. “Dedicated” suggestions should be created based on KPI values if possible, and if it makes sense to do it.

User / Actor

Main actors: DHCN manager, building operator, building owner, inhabitants and dwelling owners, renewable energy community.

Maybe this use case is not interesting to the public taking into account that the recommendations will be focused on the facilities available in this living lab, but if a general approach wants to be published for the general public it, it would be interesting.

6.5 Data - Inventory and requirements

This section provides the data sets to be used within the DT of Madrid geothermal plant. These datasets should be collected and stored in the DT, some of them will be created by the DT.

Linked use cases	Dataset name	Dataset content description	Data provider	Static or dynamic	Dataset availability
MGP-A-UC1	User patterns	Information about user patterns based on thermal setpoint changes, occupancy provided by a monitoring system.	Not defined yet.	dynamic	Not available yet (buildings not selected nor constructed)
MGP	Forecasted user patterns	Forecast of user patterns generated by an AI thermal forecast component that it will be developed based on values of the dataset 'User patterns' (including thermal setpoint changes, occupancy, schedule information if applicable). To be detailed this in collaboration with Javier Dorao (DCN).	Probono WP5 DT	dynamic	Not defined yet
MGP-A-UC1	Weather forecast data	External weather forecast service	Not defined yet	dynamic	Not defined yet

Linked use cases	Dataset name	Dataset content description	Data provider	Static or dynamic	Dataset availability
MGP-A-UC1, MGP-B, MGP-C	Building information	BIMs: a) one for the two buildings to be developed b) another for the geothermal plant from IDOM and including among other things DHCN structure and design.	-IDOM for DHCN BIM -not defined for building BIM	static	a) DHCN BIM already available from IDOM b) Building BIM not available at this moment
MGP-A-UC1	Building/room monitoring data	Monitoring data concerning buildings and rooms, and useful for the AI forecasting module	Not defined yet	dynamic	Not available
MGP-B, MGP-C	Current status of the DHCN	Monitoring data providing current status of the DHCN.	ECOFORST Scada and IDOM Trend system	dynamic	Not available yet. Data will be available once DHCN was constructed and deployed.
MGP-B, MGP-C	Current status of the buildings	Monitoring data about buildings generated by sensors and actuators	Not determined yet	dynamic	Not available yet
MGP-B, MGP-C	Electricity price forecasting	Electricity price forecasting	External service from a provider not defined yet	dynamic	Not available yet.
MGP-B	KPI optimization guidelines	Information on how to optimize KPIs which basically concern DHCN behavior. It will be generated in the scope of use case 3.2. CARTIF, in charge of creating the decision support system based on KPIS, will define it	CARTIF	dynamic	Not available yet. It will be available when CARTIF starts the development of the decision support system based on KPIS.
MGP-B-UC1, MGP-C	Calculated KPIs	The needed KPIs to guide the decision-making process concerning the operation and maintenance of the DHCN. Examples of variables: Seasonal energy efficiency ratio (SEER) concerning cooling, % of the whole electricity consumed that comes from PV,... Some variables will be directly measured from monitoring systems provided by IDOM/ECOFORST, but more "complex" KPIs (with formulas) should be computed by the WP5 DT.	IDOM/ECOFORST/Probono DT	dynamic	Not available yet

Linked use cases	Dataset name	Dataset content description	Data provider	Static or dynamic	Dataset availability
MGP	DHCN Monitored Data - Ground loop system	The data concerns the Ground loop system based on 60-80 boreholes (For each of the loops), for example, the electricity consumption of the pumps, the flow rate, the energy exchanged, etc.	Monitoring from IDOM TREND system and ECOFOREST SCADA	dynamic	Not available yet (available once DHCN will be constructed and deployed)
MGP	DHCN Monitored Data - Heat Pump system / Geothermal plant	The data concerns the Heat Pump system/Geothermal plant (For each of the Heat pumps), for example: Electricity consumption/Pumps, Evaporator side: Flow, Evaporator side: Temperature supply / return, Condenser side: Flow, Condenser side: Temperature supply / return, Condenser side: Energy...	Monitoring from IDOM TREND system and ECOFOREST SCADA	dynamic	Not available yet (available once DHCN will be constructed and deployed)
MGP	DHCN Monitored Data - Heating and cooling distribution network (Pipes).	The dataset concerns the Heating and cooling distribution network (Pipes) including variables such as: Pumps electricity consumption, Flow, Temperatures supply/return, Energy Provided.	Monitoring from IDOM TREND system and ECOFOREST SCADA	dynamic	Not available yet (available once DHCN will be constructed and deployed)
MGP	DHCN Monitored Data - Information about valves opening/status, pumps status	DHCN Monitored Data - Information about valves opening/status, pumps status	Monitoring from IDOM TREND system and ECOFOREST SCADA	dynamic	Not available yet (available once DHCN will be constructed and deployed)
MGP	DHCN Monitored Data - Evaluation of levels of Seasonal Performance Factor (SPF)	DHCN Monitored Data - Evaluation of levels of Seasonal Performance Factor (SPF)	Monitoring from IDOM TREND system and ECOFOREST SCADA	dynamic	Not available yet (available once DHCN will be constructed and deployed)
MGP	DHCN Monitored Data - Storage systems (Heating/Cooling).	The dataset concerns Storage systems (Heating/Cooling) with variables such as cooling buffer tank, heating buffer tank, DHW buffer tank, buffer tank electric consumption.	Monitoring from IDOM TREND system and ECOFOREST SCADA	dynamic	Not available yet (available once DHCN will be constructed and deployed)
MGP	Building information	Building information (for building or for substation) such as: Electricity consumption, Flow, Temperatures supply/return, Thermo-activation: cooling/heating demand...	ECOFORES or IDOM monitoring systems - to be confirmed	dynamic	Not available yet

Table 9: MGP LL - Data inventory

6.6 Decision-making tools – Inventory and requirements

Req ID	Requirement description	Tool provider	Input data	Output data
MGP-REQ-DSS-1	Forecast the thermal demand on each room/dwelling.	To be determined	To be determined	To be determined

Table 10: MGP LL - Decision making tool requirement

6.7 Visualization tools – Inventory and requirements

The identified visualization tool in this living lab is:

Linked use cases	Tool name	Tool description	Type	Tool provider
MGP	Autodesk BIM 360	Visualization of geometry and elements of the Madrid geothermal plant	BIM visualization tool	Idom

Table 11: MGP LL - Visualization tool inventory

The initial identified requirements for the visualization are the following ones:

Id	Title	Description
MGP-RQ-VIZ-1	Dataset visualization	The DT shall allow user to visualize the content of most all the datasets described in the inventory section. Notes: The specific way to show the data will be defined and decided in the coming months
MGP-RQ-VIZ-2	Data filtering	The data visualization capability shall allow the user to filter the data according to some criteria. For example, users being able to specify the dates on which they want the information, or being able to choose the part of the plant they want to see data from...
MGP-RQ-VIZ-3	Data displaying based on user role	The displaying of data shall be done according to the role of the users. For example, more detailed information will be shown to the energy facilities manager than to the owners, because it is supposed that the owners do not have detailed knowledge about the “internal parts” of the geothermal plant and the DHCN.
MGP-RQ-VIZ-4	KPIs displaying in BIM system	Calculated KPIs shall be displayed in the BIM system

Table 12: MGP LL - Visualization requirements

6.8 DT & external systems – Interoperability requirements

The external systems that it might be needed to interface with the digital list are listed below in the table and shown in the schema.

Linked use cases	Title	Description
MGP	Scada system	This system will be provided by Ecoforest to monitor and control the Ecoforest devices installed in the DHCN.
MGP	Trend system	This system will be from Idom to manage & monitor the DHCN.
MGP	DHCN BIM	BIM of DHCN
MGP	Building BIM	BIM of buildings connected to the DHCN
MGP	Building BMS system	Building management system of buildings connected to the DHCN
MGP	Forecasted Weather system	System providing forecast weather
MGP	Weather station	It will provide real-time weather data.
MGP	Electricity price forecasting	External services providing actual and forecast energy prices

Table 13: MGP LL - External systems linked to the DT

Figure 17: MGP LL - Systems Interconnexion

7 MDC - Madrid Destruction/Construction Living Lab

7.1 Living Lab Context

7.1.1 Location

The Living Lab in Madrid is part of the city’s urban development Madrid Nuevo Norte (MNN), more specifically Las Tablas Oeste. Within PROBONO, the area will be host to the integration of technologies developed in the project, following the principles of Green Building Neighbourhood (GBN), such as digital twin for construction and materials, LCA, new materials developed with different components from demolition integrated GBN buildings and infrastructural works for a geothermal plant and roads.

The infrastructure and buildings that exist currently in the area will be demolished to receive the new urban planning project infrastructure.

Figure 18: Madrid LL - Madrid Nuevo Norte, Las Tablas Oeste

Figure 19: Madrid LL - Las Tablas Oeste

7.1.2 Physical Twin Composition

The physical twin could be both the buildings in the area that will be demolished and the future buildings and infrastructure that will be built. Moreover, DCN will build a Construction and Demolition Waste (C&DW) treatment plant inside their urban development project that could be considered as a Physical Twin. This processing plant will be subject to some of the high-level needs monitoring in terms of processing times and amount of materials received as input and delivered as output, and information about their location and building characteristics should also be considered.

7.1.3 Physical Twin users

New buildings are not constructed yet. However, for the Construction and Demolition digital twin, the users will be the DCN, as Project Developer and owner, the Recycling Plant operators and construction companies will be involved in the logistics processes.

7.1.4 Physical Twin Current Status

Today, the perimeter of the GBN is on its initial state with building, infrastructure and equipment to be demolished and the recycling plant is yet to be built.

7.1.5 Physical Twin post-Probono expected status

It is expected to get:

- Fully demolished buildings in the existing pilot site.
- Fully operative recycling plant for construction and demolition materials.
- Material from the demolition to be remanufactured on site
- New material from the remanufacturing process ready to be used for the new urban development.

7.1.6 Digital Twin High Level Needs requested

To support and extend the use of demolition materials in the eco-structures that will be developed in WP3, Madrid LL wants to implement an innovative use of DTs to track, monitor and assess the material use, and embodied emissions of the whole construction process life cycle, including the deconstruction phase of the existing buildings in MNN. The high-level needs and services envisaged for this DT are describe in the next table.

High Level Need	Physical domain	Functional domain
MDC-A Track material workflow from demolition, treatment, and reuse	Parts of Neighbourhood existing buildings (demolition), and future buildings.	Material Management (Construction / Deconstruction)
MDC-B Track environmental impacts related to the material upcycling	Parts of Neighbourhood existing buildings (demolition), and future buildings.	Material Management (Construction / Deconstruction & Upcycling)
MDC-C Database for utilization of secondary raw materials	Parts of Neighbourhood existing buildings (demolition), and future buildings.	Material Management (Database: recycled material from demolition)
MDC-D Monitor environmental impacts of demolition activities	Parts of neighbourhood existing buildings (demolition).	Environment management (Ecosystem protection & Air quality management)

Table 14: MDC LL - DT High Level Need list

7.2 MDC-A - High Level Need: Track material workflow from demolition, treatment, and reuse

7.2.1 Main objective

DCN (Distrito Castellana Norte) will develop a treatment plant directly on the future urban development site for processing construction and demolition waste coming from the works of the entire area, including the Madrid LL. The demolition works of the existing infrastructure will be carried out by different companies, which will later have the right for reclaiming the reprocessed fractions for reusing in their new constructions.

Therefore, the first high-level need is to manage the material flow from construction and demolition waste (C&DW) entering the treatment plant, and the processed materials that come out, considering all stakeholders involved, the material fractions and their quality.

The starting point will be a tool already developed by DCN to register the exiting material during the demolition phase, within a GIS system and BIM Model that includes inventory of the existing buildings and infrastructures to be demolished, and the typology and volume of waste materials available for their recycling and reuse.

The traceability of the material flow and recycling processes will guarantee a transparent process for DCN and the companies involved in the demolition activities, including the separation and classification of the recycled material for its reuse by the contractors in the new buildings and infrastructure. Besides, it is expected to maximise the amount of on-site recycled material and make a new process for re-use material from demolition workplace.

For DCN, the process also means minimising extra costs for recycling regarding transportation of material, taxes and also the use of new raw materials for the construction.

7.2.2 MDC-A-UC1: Track material flow in the C&DW treatment plant

Use Case description

In this logistics use case, the DT will provide developer information about the amount of demolition material which comes in and out of the demolition recycling treatment plan, and who is the Contractor responsible for each fraction. So, users will benefit from accurate information about the waste material coming into the treatment plant, and the resulting recycled material coming out. The information will support the assignment of the amount of recycled material to each contractor involved in the process with a transparent process.

The expected output information of this use case is a list of recycled materials, with information about their amount and classification. This information will serve as an input for use cases MDC-B and MDC-C.

User / Actor

These are the actors involved on this scenario: Property Developer (DCN), Construction companies, Recycling Plant Operators.

User Scenario

Figure 20: MDC LL - Demolition scenario steps

STEP 1: Schedule Demolition Material Delivery

- The Construction Company "X" wished to demolish a certain building or infrastructure and checks in the DT the Status of Storage Capacity of the Material Recycling Plant – in relation to the space and quantity of material already stored.
- The DT dashboard displays the Status of Storage Capacity, and a box for the Construction Company "X" to insert the amount of material it wishes to bring, and the DT calculates the dates when the recycling plant is available to receive and process the material.
- The Construction Company "X" selects the "Calendar option" of the DT dashboard and selects a date and time to schedule the delivery of the material.
- To finalise the scheduling process, the construction company needs to select in the GIS map or BIM viewer the location of the demolished building or infrastructure.
- The DT blocks the selected date and updates the calendar information and BIM information.
- At the end of the STEP 1, the Construction Company "X", DCN and the Recycling Plant Operator will receive an email with the update and the summary of information.

STEP 2: Demolition Material Reception

- At the scheduled date and time, the Construction Company "X" brings demolition materials to the Recycling Plant.

- The Recycling Plant Operator at the reception inserts an update into the DT about the amount of material delivered to the plant, linking to the responsible Construction Company.
- The DT links the data with GIS tool/BIM Model developed by DCN, regarding schedule information.
- The DT registers the material fraction that will be assigned to the responsible Contractor after waste processing and corrects the amount in case it does not coincide with the amount inserted by the construction company at the scheduling step.
- The Property Developer and responsible Contractor receive an update email with a report about the material to be processed and the estimated resulting fractions and timeline information (when will this material be available). The same information will be updated and displayed in the DT – BIM viewer and graphs.

STEP 3: POST RECYCLING

- The Recycling Plant Operator inserts into the DT dashboard the amount of material that resulted from the recycling process, with detailed information about the types of material, and their quantity and quality.
- With this manually input information, the DT calculates the fractions that corresponds to the responsible Construction Company “X” and updates the dashboard information – list of materials and visual graphs.
- The DT sends an update via e-mail to DCN and Construction Company “X” saying that the recycling process is finished and the corresponding information about the material this company can claim.
- DT classifies the recycled material list according to type and quality.
- The information is saved in the data base of the DT as an inventory of material available at the plant. This information is restricted to the Plant operators and DCN.

STEP4: MATERIAL CLAIM

When it’s time that the Construction Company “x” will need to claim their recycled material fractions to use in their new building, the user can access the DT dashboard to visualise the amount of material they are entitled to, and their availability, with the aid of visual graphs.

(ALTERNATIVE) In the case the construction company needs additional amount, it can consult for availability and costs for buying more than it produced.

Once the amount of material is set, the Construction Company can schedule the material collection at the plant, in a calendar link provided by the DT.

After the collection of material is complete at the scheduled date and time, and Recycling Plant Operator updates the information on the DT to get new status of material availability and storage capacity. This calculation is done by the DT.

DCN, Construction Company “x” and Recycling Plant operator get an email update with the new status.

General Notes:

Communication between DT and users should happen in the dashboard – with visual aids and possibility of consultations, and email updates.

Emails should be sent whenever there is a change of status, e.g., when material is received, when recycled material is available, when storage capacity is full (the plant is closed to receive new materials), when storage capacity is available and open to receive materials, etc.

The three different users of this use case have different access to information according to their user typology – DCN and Recycling Operation Plant have unlimited access, and construction companies can only see and modify information about their own projects.

7.3 MDC-B - High Level Need: Track environmental impacts related to the material upcycling

7.3.1 Main objective

The main objective is to track, monitor and assess the embodied emissions of the entire life cycle of the building, including data from demolition/deconstruction and construction phases. This will complete the buildings and neighbourhood life cycle decarbonisation assessment and control as, usually, only design and operation phases are addressed.

The DT can be used to collect, register, monitor and assess the materials’ data from the initial demolition phase, to design, construction, maintenance, and finally future deconstruction, following cradle-to-grave principles, while assessing the building material and components embodied emissions of the whole building life cycle. This would support data-driven decision making from design to deconstruction phases, and a new materials data hub could be developed, closing the loop of certain materials inside the LL Madrid.

DCN already has a tool in place to predict the amount of material resulting in the demolition phase, and it will be enhanced and extended to the rest of the neighbourhood’s life cycle linking the waste materials data with Madrid Nuevo Norte new building components and infrastructure data, resultant from their recycling, via BIM representations. The DT will be completed with the BIM-based data of the new materials and components of the new neighbourhood (data captured during construction and updated during maintenance) to be able to assess the global material use and embedded emissions during the whole life cycle.

The calculation of avoided environmental impact by upcycling C&DW and reutilizing it as secondary raw materials could support the decision towards resource efficiency design of new building components.

7.3.2 7.3.2 MDC-B-UC1: Calculate avoided CO2 emissions of material life cycle

Use Case description

In this use case related to the environmental impact domain; the DT will allow the Contractor/Designer to compare the embodied emissions of a traditional building component with a new one that uses upcycled material, to be able to report to the construction promoter (DCN) on the life cycle performance of the building, regarding the materials decisions.

For calculating the avoided CO2 emissions, the Digital Twin should carry a dataset with Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) of the commercially available products to be compared with the EPD of recycled materials. In case the latter is not available, the designer should perform an LCA of the recycled material following the ISO standards for each product category rules (PCR).

On the other hand, the environmental impacts of the entire building should be calculated with the use of a LCA tool, and this result should be possible to be linked to the DT platform, either automatically or manually.

In this use case, the designer will have benefits from Data-based information of deconstruction/demolition phases to complement all the stages of the entire life cycle of a new building element, which is relevant information and part of the contractual reports required by the construction promoter (DCN).

User / Actor

The users involved in this use case are the Property Developer (DCN) and Construction companies that wish to build their new buildings in the Madrid Nuevo Norte urban development.

User Scenario

STEP 0: LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT

Prior to the use of the DT to calculate potential avoided emissions in their projects, the Construction Companies (project designers) should perform an LCA at a chosen software

including two scenarios: using standard materials, and using upcycled version of the same material, following ISO standards.

The system will use as one of the inputs, the list of recycled materials coming from the use case MDC-A.

The DT should have incorporated in its dashboard the requirements set by the Property Developer regarding the sustainability goals and LCA information in each stage.

STEP 1: REPORTING LCA

- The construction companies insert the values regarding the LCA performed into the DT following the dashboard requirements (boxes designated to fill in with specific information).
- The DT organises and presents the different reports of sustainability to be presented to DCN in tendering processes.
- The Construction Company is able to filter and select which information should be displayed in the report, and the way it is visualised (graphs, tables, etc.)
- The Construction Company is also able to export the information to an Excel file for other purposes.

STEP 2: COMPARING DIFFERENT MATERIALS

- In case when the construction company would like to compare different scenarios (e.g., use a upcycled material), after choosing the typology of material to be used in the project, the designer searches in the DT platform the environmental impacts for different solutions – market or recycled versions of the material.
- With a filtering option, the DT shows different EPDs of various construction materials.
- The user selects different options and asks the DT to compare the different scenarios regarding the CO2 emissions and/or other indicators of the Life Cycle Assessment.
- The DT displays comparative scenarios of the materials, with graphical information about the comparison results, allowing the user to make a decision based on the databased information.

7.4 MDC-C - High Level Need: Database for utilization of secondary raw materials

7.4.1 Main objective

The overall objective is to promote the efficient (re)use of existing material resources from demolition and deconstruction phases to control and reduce the neighbourhood embodied emissions. The high-level need for this DT service is to create a material data hub with information about possible new uses of recycled material from demolition, according to their characteristics and existing building standards. The information repository should contain, for example, the classification of products/materials related to the recyclability and content/quality of recycled raw materials, and possibilities of application of new recycled materials.

The material data hub could support data-driven decision-making in the life cycle of new buildings, with the use of existing material resources (demolition and deconstruction phases) and optimal selection of these new components for the design, construction, and maintenance phases. This information will benefit directly WP3, in which ACCIONA will recover C&DW to develop low carbon concrete mixes to be used in concrete building structures and pavements for the Madrid LL.

With this DT function/service, the design process should be able to maximize the use of recycled materials from C&DW treated on site. The starting point is the tool already developed for MNN that classifies existing materials to provide the designers with a guide for deconstruction, treatment, and reuse whenever possible.

7.4.2 MDC-C-UC1: Select new building component material

Use Case description

In this use case related to environmental impact domain, the DT will provide the designers with information from the material data hub to select secondary raw materials for their project. This information is crossed with the specifications and technical requirements for the different uses of the material coming from the normative. This way, the user benefits from data-based information about the contents and potential uses regarding the secondary raw material coming from the processed demolition waste.

User / Actor

The users involved in this use case are the Property Developer (DCN) and Construction companies (designer and structural engineer) that wish to build their new buildings in the Madrid Nuevo Norte urban development.

User Scenario

The system will use as one of the inputs, the list of recycled materials coming from the use case MDC-A.

STEP 1: SELECTION OF MATERIAL IN THE DT MATERIAL HUB

- The Designer/Structure Engineer needs to select the materials for their new building components with lower environmental impacts.
- In the designated link in the DT dashboard, the Designer/Structure Engineer searches for the material composition of recycled materials. The DT provides the options of searching in a bar, where the user can write the key word, and a scroll down menu of the available material list coming from Use Case MDC-A.
- The user selects a material, and the DT shows information about the material concerning its composition, and a guideline with design recommendations for its use, and their environmental embodied impacts.
- The Designer/Structure Engineer makes a decision with the data-based information whether the materials listed are suitable for the intended use or not – always according to technical specifications.

As an alternative, the user can make an inverse process.

STEP 1b: SELECTION OF MATERIAL IN THE DT MATERIAL HUB 2

- The Designer/Structure Engineer selects in the DT dashboard which type of use is intended for the project (e.g., filling, structural concrete, pavement).
- The DT shows a list of materials that can be used for that end with their entire information sheet, containing classification and technical characteristics.
- The Designer/Structure Engineer makes a decision with the data-based information whether the materials listed are suitable for the intended use or not – always according to technical specifications.

STEP 2: MATERIAL CLAIM

- In case the material presented in the DT is coming from the DCN Recycling plant, the user must check for the availability and proceed with the steps of material claim and collection from use case MDC-A.

7.5 MDC-D - High Level Need: Monitor environmental impacts of demolition activities

7.5.1 Main objective

The objective of the high-level need is to assess the air quality during deconstruction and demolition activities with the use of mapping technology (LiDAR) to measure particulate matter in the air, the presence of contaminants, and their concentration. The data collection equipment allows analysing the propagating behaviour of the aerosols from the demolition in their vertical and horizontal extent.

The presence of aerosols coming from the demolition can cause immediate impacts on the air quality and in human health. Having this data, confronted with meteorological data, can provide a data-driven decision-making tool to control and reduce the neighbourhood embodied emissions. For example, the demolition activities can be planned to avoid days that are extremely windy.

The data collected with LiDAR by the partner USC (Universidad de Santiago de Compostela) on site will be also used to compare and validate existing air quality measurements from satellites. In addition, this DT function could be later replicated for the construction phase of the new building in the area, extending the information to other life cycle stages.

7.5.2 MDC-D-UC1: Plan demolition activity

Use Case description

In this use case, the Contractor/Project manager will check in the Digital Twin the local conditions to plan a demolition, based on the calculated information of weather forecast and aerosols propagation behaviour, based on the data collected by the LiDAR. The main goal is to avoid days that are extremely windy, in which the impacts on the air pollution are more significant. Thus, the DT will indicate for the user if the date planned for the demolition activity is adequate or not.

Optionally, this function can be linked to MDC-A, in which the DT will indicate the storage capacity of the local treatment plant, so that the construction companies know if they can deliver the demolished material to the plant.

User / Actor

This use case involves the following user: Construction companies (project manager). The domain is about Environmental impact and air quality. The user benefits from Data based information about the weather conditions and particulate matter behaviour from demolition activity.

User Scenario

This is the user scenario for this use case:

1. The weather centre sends weather data to the DT
2. The DT, using an algorithm developed by USC, computes weather conditions which are not favourable for demolition activities
3. The DT sends an alert, in the form of an email or text message to project manager
4. Project manager makes informed decision about the schedule of the demolition activity to reduce environmental impacts to the local air quality. The DT will also provide a set of near-real-time and historical environmental information in the neighbourhood of the LL site.

7.6 Data - Inventory and requirements

7.6.1 MDC-A - Track material workflow from demolition, treatment, and reuse

For this use case, the data inventory needs should allow the DT to calculate and assign amount of processed material for each stakeholder involved. This decision shall be made according to the amount and types of material brought in the recycling plant, the schedule of the deconstruction and construction works, available storage space at the plant, and material demand for new buildings and infrastructure.

- Existing buildings and infrastructure: DCN tool, based on Geographical Data Base (GIS system) and BIM models, with information about existing buildings and infrastructure to be demolished, including materials compositions.
- BIM Model (existing buildings and future buildings): Information about of demolition plan, with schedules, building elements and materials expected, and BIM model of the building and infrastructure projects of the district that will be built.
- Actors ID: List of construction companies involved in the of demolition of existing structure and subsequent reuse of material.
- Timeline of recycling process: Information about the process of recycling process, with a timeline of activities since the entry point of demolition waste until the output of recycled materials and products.

- Timeline of projects: Schedule of the construction of new buildings and infrastructure, to plan the assignment of resources and the storage of materials at the recycling plant.
- Space allocation: Specific plot of the recycling plant with building information regarding storage capacity of recycled materials.
- Percentage of salvaged materials: Relation of recycled materials coming out of the process with the input amount from the demolition - to be calculated by DT.
- Material categories: List of material categories that comes in and out of the processing plant.
- List of raw materials: List of input materials from demolition and its compositions - to be registered at the reception of recycling treatment plant. This information will be input for use cases MDC-B and MDC-C.
- List of recycled materials: List of output materials from processing plant in DCN and its compositions - to be registered at the end of recycling treatment process.
- Destination of the recycled materials: the use of the upcycling materials in the new buildings of the LL or in other buildings in MNN (because of timelines and storage space)

7.6.2 MDC-B - Track environmental impacts related to the material upcycling

For this use case, the data inventory needs should allow the DT to calculate the CO2 emissions of different variants of a type of material, to allow the designer/contractor to define and report on the chosen option, that should be the one with the best sustainability performance along the building life cycle.

- BIM Model - Existing buildings: Project information about the new buildings.
- Bill of Materials: Inventory list of building elements and materials.
- List of DCN sustainability requirements for new buildings.
- List of recycled materials: List of output materials from processing plant in DCN and its compositions (output of MDC-A).
- Carbon emissions for recycled material - construction and deconstruction phases: LCA - Carbon emissions of material or products using secondary raw materials (recycled)
- Carbon emissions for standard material - construction and deconstruction phases: LCA - Carbon emissions of material or products using raw materials (standard).

- Recycling Plant location: Specific plot of the recycling plant for assessing the transport in the LCA.
- List of material and products EPDs.

7.6.3 MDC-C - Database for utilization of secondary raw materials

For this use case, the data inventory needs should allow the DT to provide a list of secondary raw materials coming from recycling plant, with its composition, specification, and possible applications in construction.

- List of recycled materials: List of output materials from processing plant in DCN and its compositions (output of MDC-A).
- Material repository: information about the classification of products/materials and content/quality of recycled raw materials, result of demolition and recycling processes.
- Technical specifications: Technical information about material usage for pavements and structural concrete, according to the normative
- Timeline (Boundary conditions): Schedule of the recycling process and the construction of new buildings and infrastructure, to plan the assignment of resources and the storage of materials at the recycling plant.
- Space allocation (Boundary conditions): Storage capacity of recycling plant.
- BIM Model (existing buildings and future buildings): Project information about the new buildings.

7.6.4 MDC-D - Monitor environmental impacts of demolition activities

For this use case, the data inventory needs should allow the DT to provide information for decision making, regarding demolition activities, considering meteorological information.

- Air quality: Satellite-derived air pollutants and aerosols.
- Meteorological data: Environmental data
- Timeline of project (demolition plan): Schedule of demolition of different buildings and infrastructure

- BIM Model (existing building): information about of demolition plan, with schedules, building elements and materials expected, and BIM model of the building and infrastructure projects of the district that will be built.
- Company ID: List of construction companies involved in the of demolition of existing structure.

7.7 Decision-making tools – Inventory and requirements

MDC-B: LCA tool: Commercial tool to perform Life Cycle Assessment with their own database.

MDC-D: ERDDAP server provides an extensible RESTful web service API for data and metadata distribution. Through this middleware, USC will distribute meteorological, climate and air quality data to the PROBONO project.

For the use case of Deconstruction and Construction, with the dataset provided, the DT should be able to:

- Calculate and assign amount of processed material for stakeholders involved.
- Calculates avoided emissions, according to the composition of selected materials in all life cycle phases.
- Provide a list of secondary raw materials coming from recycling plant, with its composition, specification, and possible applications in construction.
- Provide information for planning demolition activities, considering meteorological information.

7.8 Visualization tools – Inventory and requirements

Since, the overall objective is that construction companies can make informed decision about the demolition of existing buildings and infrastructure, and later the construction of their new projects. This DT should be one **unique dashboard**, and the different use cases described above represent the various functionalities that can be accessed through different tabs that open new windows. Thus, the most important information to appear in their dashboards should be the schedule of their activities (retrieved from dataset) and the weather conditions (MDC-D).

At the moment of registration to this DT, each user will fill in with their profile information, which will grant them different levels of access to the information.

The different changes of status and alerts should be sent by email from the DT to the users.

Each functionality should display different visualization options:

- 3D viewer: For DCN to visualise the status of demolition and construction of the urban development project.
- Gantt chart: for the different schedules of the DT.
- Bar charts with colours: Capacity status of the recycling plant, amount of material brought in and already claimed by each construction company, etc.
- List of materials: factsheets with materials and their characteristics.

All Use Cases:

- GIS tool provided by DCN, BIM models with design information.
- Schedule and timelines of demolition and construction phases – Gantt chart

MDC-D:

- Online Viewer provided by USC. Web tool to dynamically visualize maps and time series. The proposed viewer relies on open-source technologies (e.g., Leaflet) and connects to interoperable middleware to display and provide access to geospatial data. It provides a dynamic interface that allow users to overlay different vector and raster layers, and display time series datasets. Its design supports rapid development and customization for multipurpose applications.

Figure 21: MDC LL - Draft of the online viewer

The online viewer is based on an existing operational interface which has been developed by USC. The design would require customization to fit the specific requirements and data types of PROBONO.

7.9 DT & external systems – Interoperability requirements

It is envisioned that the DT should be interfaced with these systems:

- **Meteorological Information system:** It provides meteorological parameters related to air quality during demolition activities. Data will be communicated through interoperable middleware from USC in a variety of formats and standards (e.g. netCDF, WMS).
- **Material Repository:** It will give list of secondary raw materials coming from recycling plant, with its composition, specification, and possible applications in construction.
- **BIM:** This is BIM Model of the area, with information about existing buildings and infrastructure to be demolished, and future buildings and infrastructure to be constructed, including the local treatment plant that is planned for the area. Information about the schedule of activities.
- **GIS:** This system is provided by DCN, based on Geographical Data Base (GIS system), with information about existing buildings and infrastructure to be demolished, including materials compositions.

8 PTO - Porto Living Lab

8.1 Living Lab Context

8.1.1 Location

The Porto Living Lab, also called “Sonae Campus” is located on Maia City, inside the Porto Metropolitan Area. The “Sonae Campus” is the headquarter of Sonae in Portugal.

Figure 22: Porto LL - Top View of Sonae’s Campus

8.1.2 Physical Twin Details

The Physical Twin is the existing “Sonae Campus” which contains the following building and equipment composition:

- 60% Logistic (Warehouse)
- 30% Offices
- 10% Industry and Storage

Currently, 3200 employees and contractors work on the Sonae Campus.

8.1.3 Physical Twin post-Probono expected status

No new construction or major renovation are planned on the physical twin within the Probono project. The Physical Twin will receive some modifications to optimize the elements mainly related to energy production/consumption/storage optimization and CO2 emissions reduction.

But more than basic energy management and environmental performance improvement, Sonae envisions to develop the conditions for a more energy efficient corporate campus coupled with several social innovations and biodiversity initiatives, in order to become a worldwide reference in sustainable domains, and be able to inspire a collective change:

- **Renewable Energy Community (REC)**, engaging the companies of the campus, either consumers, producers, or prosumers in order to create a REC with easy access to green energy, reducing CO2 emissions, and improving the usability, adaptability and integrity of the different solutions and innovations that will be tested. High potential of exploitation to other campuses.
- **Innovation Tech Hub**, providing the community with the best future green energy generation tools and innovative solutions to test and develop new emerging technologies. Innovation tech hub includes all the new energetic and key energy equipment such as solar panel, interconnexion equipment, battery and charging station.

8.1.4 Digital Twin High Level Needs requested

There are 3 high-level needs envisioned for the digital twin of Porto LL which are sorted by priority, the highest priority being at the top of the table below.

High Level Need	Physical domain	Functional domain
PTO-A Influence users' behaviour in their energy consumption	The Sonae campus: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All Campus areas - Electrical network entrance point 	Energy Management Human behaviour
PTO-B Monitor innovation tech-hub	The Innovation Tech-hub constructed within Probono <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Innovation tech hub building and related equipment 	Energy Management
PTO-C Simulate modifications in energy system for energy community optimization	The Innovation Tech-hub constructed within Probono	Energy Management

Table 15: Porto LL - DT High Level Need list

8.2 PTO-A - High Level Need: Influence users' behaviour in their energy consumption

8.2.1 Main objective

The main objective of this Digital Twin High-Level need is to influence the users' behaviour in the campus, by giving them the necessary information to make the best possible decisions in terms of energy utilization.

The idea is that, by receiving inputs from the consumption and production of energy within the campus, there will be a tool (or set of tools) that shares the information to the users, so that energy conservation can be promoted and also the peaks of consumption can occur within the schedule more beneficial for the community and for the physical twin.

This will also promote the production of energy from renewable sources within the GBN, reducing the CO2 footprint and thus contributing to the corporate targets within Sonae Group and to the Sonae Campus in particular. The campus users will also be more conscious of the company commitment to the environment as well as they will feel more involved on that action towards sustainability.

The information produced by the Digital Twin can reach the users in the form of alerts/push-up notifications via an app, an internal website or, for instance, checking it every day on monitors strategically located on places that everyone passes on the campus before going to their workplace.

The digital twin incorporates several streams of information regarding the energy consumption and production within the campus. A portion of this information comes from the physical twins and some of it is already centralized.

Here is the list of the different use cases for the "Influence users' behaviour in their energy consumption" High-Level Need, that are detailed in the next subsections:

- **PTO-A-UC1** Inform users about energy usage
- **PTO-A-UC2** Provide users with recommendations for energy consumption

8.2.2 PTO-A-UC1: Inform users about energy usage

Use Case description

In this use case related to Energy Conservation and Efficient Consumption, the DT will provide users with information about energy usage (consumption/production) of the campus based on data collected at different levels so that they will significantly increase their awareness of how they could consume energy, especially in the form of electricity. As a result, it will be clear for the users what the best times are during the day to consume energy and consequently they can adjust their behaviour. Among the provided information, the DT will forecast future consumption peak or lack of energy production on the campus. Moreover, the exploitation team of the campus will have access of these information and in return, they could alert the users, so they could adapt their behaviour to avoid or mitigate the forecasted events. Finally, by adjusting their energy consumption, the worker will contribute to a better management of the energy consumption throughout the Campus, the increase of renewable usage and the access to cheaper energy for EV charging, for example.

User / Actor

Standard Workers which are currently around 3000 workers on Sonae Campus that are potentially concerned by this use case.

8.2.3 PTO-A-UC2: Provide recommendations about energy consumption

In order to optimize the campus energy system, the DT will compute some recommendations for the energy usage. For example, it could calculate the best charging time for users who own an EV and want to charge their vehicle at the campus. It could also be the computation of recommended setpoint of the HVAC systems of the campus based on weather forecast. Another example is recommendations on which devices should be used or avoided by end-users at a given time. The DT makes that information available to user's applications.

User / Actor

Potentially, any campus users could benefit of this best practices.

User Scenarios

Scenario A – Best charging time

1. The worker, who uses an electrical vehicle, receives in advance the information about best charging time for the next days, so it can choose the most convenient for him.
2. Another possibility is when he arrives at the headquarter, he receives a notification on an app or via e-mail providing the best time to charge today.

Scenario B – HVAC setpoint recommendation

1. The Weather centre sends weather data to the DT and the information of the best time to produce electricity
2. The DT computes best temperature setpoint in function of the weather and the power available for HVAC – for a specific building/area
3. The DT makes the information available to an internal website or some user applications
4. The building manager consults the information and adjusts the set-point accordingly the information received

8.3 PTO-B - High Level Need: Monitor the innovations tech-hub

8.3.1 Main objective

This high-level need is related to the centralization of all the technological innovations that will make part of the tech-hub dimension of the Living Lab: solar2vehicle, v2g, green h2 production, BIPV, 2nd life batteries, Phase-change Materials, and solar heating for industrial processes. Indeed, having just only user interface with all the technologies will facilitate their management and utilization as well as the retrieve of all data. This is also closer of what will be energy mixture of the future, with a lot of diversified sources and consumers acting in a local dimension.

The high-level need is composed of the following use cases:

- **PTO-B-UC1** Monitor the tech-hub innovations
- **PTO-B-UC2** Detect performance issue and failure

8.3.2 PTO-B-UC1: Monitor the tech-hub innovations

Use Case description

The DT will provide users with all significant data related to the tech-hub innovations in one place. Such data could be historic or real-time and related to e.g.: devices status, energy production, maintenance schedule and more. The centralization of data in one place will facilitate the understanding of all the tech-hub implementation and provide solid basis for operational decisions. Moreover, it will provide important and comprehensive information for further replications of similar projects or equipment implementations by the companies that are exploring those innovations.

The DT will collect different data sources of the tech-hub and relevant external data sources avoiding users the manual operations of data cleaning, downloading, transforming...

User / Actor

Users are 1) the operational staff in charge of the maintenance and 2) the construction project developer.

Operational staff will benefit from the DT to facilitate the operational tasks regarding the maintenance of the different equipment. It will help them to detect energy issue across the tech hub and project developer to design and scale-up similar solutions.

8.3.3 PTO-B-UC2: Detect performance issue and failure

Use Case description

The DT will detect potential performance issues and failures of tech-hub devices about energy by identifying significant differences between measured data and simulated theoretical data. It results that the DT will detect energy anomalies in this GBN. The DT will provide the users with information so that it can start investigations into causes of the poor performance or failure. Finally, the DT will facilitate the user to maintain the different equipment on site.

User / Actor

The Team in charge of the operational management of the campus to detect failure and under-performance issues.

8.4 PTO-C - High Level Need: Simulate modifications in energy system for energy community optimization

8.4.1 Main objective

The high-level objective is to enable the assessment of the future GBN evolution about energy systems by simulating its potential modifications such as the:

- adding of new device for example: charging station, electrical bike station, HVAC system...
- integration of a new electrical production unit
- update of device characteristics composing the existing tech hub, e.g., battery capacity, solar panel performance...
- removing of existing devices

Thus, it is possible to test the impact of some future devices on the consumption and energetic performance.

Besides, this allows the identification of the physical twin parts or components which can be optimized from the energy performance perspective. This can be zone or device that use more electricity than others. Eventually, stakeholders can take decision about future physical twin upgrades.

8.4.2 PTO-C-UC1: Simulate changes in the energy system

Use Case description

In this use case related to design phase, the DT will enable the team in charge of the future GBN development to simulate modifications in the tech-hub electric system. It could be the update of characteristics of some existing components, the adding of new ones or the removing of some.

User / Actor

Main actor is the Business development team/project developer in charge of the Campus evolution.

Linked use cases	Dataset name	Dataset content description	Data provider	Static or dynamic	Dataset availability
	1H 1I 1J 1K - Cantina 1K - AP1 1K - AP2 1K - APA 4A	Monthly electricity consumption	Capwatt	Dynamic	To be confirmed
	PV - 4A	Accumulated electricity production from PV	Capwatt	Dynamic	To be confirmed
		Power from PV	Capwatt	Dynamic	To be confirmed
		Peak installed power (Pp)	Capwatt	Static	To be confirmed
	PV - CARPORT - P11	Accumulated electricity production from PV	Capwatt	Dynamic	To be confirmed
		Power from PV	Capwatt	Dynamic	To be confirmed
		Peak installed power (Pp)	Capwatt	Static	To be confirmed
	PV - Mini-generation	Accumulated electricity production from a small PV plant located at the Campus	Capwatt	Dynamic	To be confirmed
		Power from a small PV plant located at the Campus	Capwatt	Dynamic	To be confirmed
		Peak installed power (Pp)	Capwatt	Static	To be confirmed
	Energy Storage System	Accumulated charged Energy by the system	Capwatt	Dynamic	To be confirmed
		Accumulated discharged Energy by the system	Capwatt	Dynamic	To be confirmed
		Power consumption in Charging mode (Real-time)	Capwatt	Dynamic	To be confirmed
		Power production in Discharging mode (Real-time)	Capwatt	Dynamic	To be confirmed
		Installed Power from storage system	Capwatt	Static	To be confirmed
		Installed Capacity from storage system	Capwatt	Static	To be confirmed
	EV HUBs	Charging Power of EV UC	To be confirmed	Dynamic	To be confirmed
		Energy consumed by EV UC	To be confirmed	Dynamic	To be confirmed
	Weather Data	Incident solar radiation in the PV	Capwatt	Dynamic	Yes
		Ambient temperature	Capwatt	Dynamic	Yes
	Electricity market price	Hourly electricity market price in Portugal (Forecast for the next day)	OMIE	Dynamic	Yes
	Lote2	Electricity consumption of the building	Elergone	Dynamic	Yes
		Time series of the PV generation	Elergone	Dynamic	Yes

Linked use cases	Dataset name	Dataset content description	Data provider	Static or dynamic	Dataset availability
	PV - Maia (Lote 2)	Peak installed power (Pp)	Elergone	Static	Yes
PTO-B-UC1 PTO-B-UC2 PTO-C-UC1	Innovations Data - Electrolyser	Rate of hydrogen production	Capwatt	Dynamic	No
		Energy consumed by the electrolyser	Capwatt	Dynamic	No
		Working Power of the electrolyser	Capwatt	Dynamic	No
	Innovations Data - BIPV	Accumulated electricity production from BIPV to implement in the Campus	Capwatt	Dynamic	No
		Power from BIPV to implement in the Campus	Capwatt	Dynamic	No
		Peak installed power (Pp)	Capwatt	Static	No
		Accumulated Electricity production from Bi-facial PV to implement in the Campus	Capwatt	Dynamic	No
		Power from Bi-facial PV to implement in the Campus	Capwatt	Dynamic	No
		Peak installed power (Pp)	Capwatt	Static	No
		Peak installed power (Pp)	Capwatt	Static	No
	Innovations Data - 2nd life Storage	Accumulated charged Energy by the system	Capwatt	Dynamic	No
		Accumulated discharged Energy by the system	Capwatt	Dynamic	No
		Power consumption in Charging mode	Capwatt	Dynamic	No
		Power production in Discharging mode	Capwatt	Dynamic	No
		Installed Power from storage system	Capwatt	Static	No
		Installed Capacity from storage system	Capwatt	Static	No
	Innovations Data - V2G	Power of the V2G solution to implement at the Campus	Capwatt	Dynamic	No
	Innovations Data - SHIP	SHIP (Solar Heat for Industrial Processes) technology to implement in the Campus	Capwatt	Unknown	No
	Innovations Data	Solar2V	Capwatt	Unknown	No
	Innovations Data - Smart EV Hub	Electricity consumption of the EV HUB chargers	Elergone	Dynamic	Yes
		Flex periods	Elergone	Dynamic	No
		Increase of self-consumption	Elergone	Dynamic	No
		Occupancy pattern	Elergone	Dynamic	Yes
Innovations Data - PCM at warehouse	Electricity consumption of the cooling system	Elergone	Dynamic	No	
	Energy saving due to PCMs	Elergone	Dynamic	No	
	Increase of self-consumption	Elergone	Dynamic	No	
	Bill reduction due to PCMs	Elergone	Dynamic	No	

Table 16: Porto LL - Data inventory

8.6 Decision-making tools – Inventory and requirements

We can note two kinds of decision-making tools:

- For end user information and interaction: Currently, there is no specific IT tools which informs workers on the Campus about the energy consumption and how energy is produced or managed. Although several communications are regularly made within the group to show the commitment to renewable energy and green practices, for example information of the installation of more photovoltaic sites and EV chargers. There is no living/real-time information.
- For facility manager simulation, evolution and evaluation tools. There is still nothing in place about this simulation capability. A part of the information is already gathered but only from an operational point-of-view. The managers, who are responsible for the correct function of the support infrastructure of the campus, already uses data to analyse trends and adjust behaviour but not in an integrated way.

8.7 Visualization tools – Inventory and requirements

It is expected that all data are displayed in a single tool to show and identify their interactions. For example, in the high-level need “PTO-B – Monitoring the innovations tech-hub”, the user needs to see correlations between all these data. The ability to display links between electricity production, battery level and Campus consumption is important to achieve this high-level need.

LL could deploy monitors at the entrance of some building to present information about energy usage and recommendations on energy consumption and develop a Mobile App to notify campus' users with information about energy usage and recommendations on energy consumption provided by the DT.

8.8 DT & external systems – Interoperability requirements

It is envisioned that the DT should be interfaced with these systems:

- **Building Energy data system:** IOT Gateway or database to provide energy data such as: Electricity Power Consumption of the different buildings, power production from energy storage system, ...
- **Electricity market price system:** providing hHourly electricity market price in Portugal (Forecast for the next day)
- **EV Hub Energy data system:** System from Elergone to provide energy data related to the EV HUB and the PCM system

9 BRU - Brussels Living Lab

9.1 Living Lab Context

9.1.1 Location

The Brussels Living Lab is located at Chaussee de Wavre 1789 (50.815770,4.429450) the Auderghem Commune, in the southeast corner of the Brussels-Capital Region, Belgium. The Living Lab main and only building is De l'Autre Côté de l'Ecole (ACE) school building, home to a school. Auderghem, one of the Brussels-Capital region's 19 communes, is situated in the Woluwe valley and at the entrance to the Sonian Forest. One third of its surface area of 10.52 km² bathes in green beauty. From 2017 figures, Auderghem has 33,313 inhabitants representing close to three percent of Brussels' regional population.

In Brussels, the capital city of Belgium, and seat of important European institutions, the climate is sub-oceanic, humid and rainy. The climate is influenced by the close proximity of the Atlantic Ocean and North Sea, with decently warm summers and cold, close to freezing temperature, winters. The wind blows frequently, and can be rather intense, especially in wintertime. Brussels does not get an abundance of sun, especially in the winter months. On average Brussels counts of around 1,600 sunshine hours annually. Brussels has an annual average of 2096 heating degree days (HDDs) and 60 cooling degree days (CDDs).

The LL sits in a high-intensity traffic zone, the commune being one of the outer belts of Brussels.

Figure 24: Brussels LL - Views of ACE school (delimited in yellow)

9.1.2 Physical Twin Composition

The core element is the existing ACE school, which represents 11856m², of which 7000m² are heated, 550 students and 60 staff. It is collocated in a shared building (in the image above, the school is circled in yellow). The building is characterized by an atrium. The ground floor and the other 4 floors are arranged in such a way as to have a void on the atrium.

9.1.3 Physical Twin users

The users-stakeholders comprise the school communities, 60 school staff, 550 students and parents / guardians of the students. In particular, the energy manager and infrastructure managers of the school could be relays for technical considerations. Other stakeholders include the suppliers of funding, the legal/regulatory framework actors.

9.1.4 Physical Twin Current Status

As mentioned above, the LL is an already-built asset, which is a school collocated in a wider building. The LL, i.e. the school, does not exist in isolation from its neighbourhood. It sits in a wider ecosystem or GBN that could be defined in terms of different boundaries, as per D1.1 “GBN Analysis tools and decision support system” (in terms of social, jurisdictional and other (technical, resilience, risk etc.), impacts, ...) which in turn could cover as a first approximation the geography of provenance of the students and staff. The Physical Twin in turn could take both the LL and the GBN perimeter.

9.1.5 Physical Twin Purpose

This chapter was prepared based on previously shared WP7 “Living Labs GBN Implementation” documents, as well as a workshop held on June 21st 2022 afternoon, online. During this workshop, we asked the participants to describe their understanding of the purpose of the LL. As a school, the social drivers are key in the purpose, in shaping the citizens of the world of tomorrow, and as a place to acquire soft/hard skills to integrate into society. ACE indicated a role of the school in raising awareness of tomorrow’s problems as part of the school mission.

Apart from the technical considerations, we would like to propose Brussels Digital Twin to focus on identifying, growing, and promoting social-economical behaviour drivers.

9.1.6 Vision and challenge to be addressed in PROBONO

In addition to the renovation of infrastructure as describe above, ACE has a key role within the Living Lab Cluster in which it is a part, alongside Aarhus University Campus, Denmark and SONAE Sustainable campus, Porto. This is for the business & socio-economic aspects and tasks of the Living Lab Cluster. Here, ACE will play an active role in showing the positive impact of data-driven knowledge on sustainability decision-making and how to maximise business and social innovation by influencing behaviour. As an integral part of the cluster of Living Labs the Brussels Living Lab aims to support evidence-based decisions as to the business, socio-economic and environmental value to benefit establishing a Green Neighbourhood from the clustering of diverse and standalone buildings. As an education provider in the heart of a vibrant commune the Brussels Living Lab will have a special focus on Citizen & Stakeholder Engagement and behaviours.

In its project management, the Brussels Living Lab will add an important communication and awareness raising component aimed at teachers, students and the wider stakeholder group in

the community. This will at least take the form of exhibitions at school during all phases of the project (first presenting the consumption metrics, then the solutions chosen, impact measures, etc.). Given the pedagogical functioning of the school, both teachers and pupils will be able to take up these subjects in order to develop a didactic project, both for scientific fields (relating to technical aspects) and social fields (relating to the creation of synergies and changes in behaviour). Finally, the project will also have an echo chamber through the teachers' diary and the weekly newspaper sent to parents. In total, this represents a direct audience of almost 2000 people immediately connected to the school and Commune.

9.1.7 Physical Twin post-Probono expected status

As described in the GA, the interventions' ambitions (Innovations and Expected Results) are as follows. In parallel with the technology and construction innovations set out for the ACE renovation works mentioned above, ACE will, in parallel with the other LL Cluster locations at Aarhus and Porto, identify and map a baseline of its business and socio-economic aspects for the management, use and operation of the building. This includes but is not limited to: Facilities Management, sustainable procurement, circular economy approaches and the behaviours and use of the building by staff, pupils, and visitors alike. From this, ACE and PROBONO will determine the 4 levels of maturity of each of these functions, both individually and collectively, and the impact they have on sustainability relative to the target indicators for achieving a Green Building. Then, working in tandem with the renovation plans and innovations to be carried out, co-create, and test a set of business and social innovations that enhance and optimise sustainability outcomes to achieve a more joined-up, whole ecosystem and user centric approach to the building's management, operation, function and use, supporting its transition toward a green building. From its established baseline and plans, ACE will work with the core Auderghem PROBONO partners – Serco, Willis and VIAS and Advisory Board member AIG, to identify and test the social, commercial, policy, financing and data-driven technical innovations and drivers needed within Auderghem, to provide stimulus and be a catalyst for the clustering and collaboration of different buildings to develop a scope for a Green Neighbourhood.

Engagement with the wider group of stakeholders to include the Commune, other non-residential and commercial stakeholders as well as residential developments and citizens groups will take place in parallel. Heterogenous data derived from the ACE renovation, such as its building's energy and carbon performance, integrated with data outputs and findings from the testing and evaluation of the renovation innovations, will, through a set of data and decision-making tools, support evidence-informed decisions as to the business, socio-economic and

environmental value and benefits of establishing a Green Neighbourhood from the clustering of diverse and standalone buildings.

9.1.8 Digital Twin High-Level Needs requested

The first identified needs focused on enabling an energy community and the second one focused on preparing for a safer, cleaner, mobility tomorrow, with an increased prevalence of soft mobility. Forms of soft mobility include walking, cycling, skateboarding, or running.

High Level Need	Physical domain	Functional domain
A: Monitor, manage and optimize LL Energy systems	Building: LL	Energy Management
B: Provide a hosting platform for the GBN Energy Community, and connect it to other energy communities	GBN	Energy Management
C: Evaluate the GBN evolution and new designs in terms of mobility	GBN	Mobility

Table 17: Brussels LL - DT High Level Need list

9.1.9 The Energy context

As defined by the EU, energy communities¹³ aim at organizing collective and citizen-driven energy actions that help pave the way for a clean energy transition, while moving citizens to the fore. They contribute to increasing public acceptance of renewable energy projects and make it easier to attract private investments in the clean energy transition. At the same time, they have the potential to provide direct benefits to citizens by increasing energy efficiency, lowering their electricity bills and creating local job opportunities. They will produce, consume, store and sell renewable energy will also help advance energy efficiency in households, support the use of renewable energy and at the same time contribute to fighting poverty through reduced energy consumption and lower supply tariffs.

¹³ https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/markets-and-consumers/energy-communities_en

Enabling energy communities has been identified as a high-level need for the Brussels Living Lab. The DT could support them at different scales:

- **A building scale**, focusing on the school energy performances.
- **An intermediary-scale**, at the GBN level (intermediate between local and global) focusing in particular on the energy space.
- An immediate **global scale** for the project would be a DT connecting the GBNS and Energy Communities centred on the project's Living Labs.

The benefits for the LL of this would be to allow the LL to reduce its energy footprint, optimising its energy generation potential (impacting additional revenue), while multiplying its energy-optimisation efforts by engaging with its neighbourhood.

The primary target is energy consumption. This impacts in turn socio-economic development, air quality, circular economy principles, etc as can be tracked by WP6 "Monitoring and evaluation of the project's Living Labs".

The DT can interact with the physical twin, including the energy (gas, electricity, and heat network) networks, through sensors and actuators both in energy production and consumption. A specific point of attention for GBNS will be around ensuring that Digital Twins are used in a manner to accomplish a just transition, enabled for example by a "Green AI" (Yigitcanlar, Mehmood, & Corchado, 2021), for example including human wellbeing at the core of the enabled services (Zaballos, Briones, Massa, Centelles, & Caballero, 2020).

9.2 BRU-A - High-Level Need: Monitor, manage and optimize LL Energy systems

9.2.1 Main objective

Once energy production and metering systems are in place and connected, the LL (school building) can have an operational dashboard to monitor its energy performance, providing for example benchmarks so as to help the actor assess its situation, and identifying optimization opportunities. The DT will aim at capturing the reality of a built asset, its behaviours, parameters, and characteristics to help influence the energy behaviour of the system (Agouzoul, et al., 2021).

School staff, in particular coming from the utilities management team, will have access to an operational dashboard to monitor school energy performance.

The two first use cases focus on supporting and augmenting the energy management systems of a living lab or smart building, aiming at providing an "autonomous management system

requires specialized tasks, such as monitoring, analysis, and decision-making tasks for reaching objectives in the environment, like improve the energy efficiency” (Aguilar, Garces-Jimenez, R-Moreno, & Garcia, 2021).

9.2.2 BRU-A-UC1: Detect consumption anomalies

Use Case description

Digital twins can support the detection of building anomaly detection, especially developed in the Facility Management space (Xie, Lu, Parlikad, & Schooling, 2020). In this use case, related to “Energy Conservation and Efficient Consumption “domain, the DT will identify unexpected energy consumption, possibly indicating a fault in the LL energy systems, electrical and heating equipment still on, or an equipment overconsuming because faulty. This allows timely maintenance of equipment as well as efficient operations of the LL. The DT will use smart meters, meteorological and maintenance data, as well as a model of energy consumption, to ensure that the energy consumption patterns are aligned with expected behaviours (Henzel, Wrobel, Fice, & Sikora, 2022). With a proper metering and information system, it also enables linking specific equipment to consumption, and this way provides a feedback loop for a more efficient use of energy.

By providing the right information at the right moment, the DT contributes to a better management of the energy consumption throughout the LL. It also allows users to identify required preventative maintenance operations, reducing downtime and the on-site experience of both staff and students.

This use case concerns the following energy systems of the LL:

- Electricity
- Gas
- where applicable, heat/cold networks

User / Actor

This could be the LL energy manager, the maintenance team but can also be another actor with an interest in making the LL as energy efficient as possible. This might change as the tools and solutions evolve.

User Scenario

- The Energy Manager logs into the LL digital twin dashboard. This dashboard shows the usual pattern of energy consumption of the school (based on historical data, along with environmental data, maintenance data, and meters reading, as well as others), corrected depending on external conditions (weather – for example temperatures, humidity, light, ...), and/or number of classrooms opened at a given time, between others.
- The Energy Manager sees an unexpected peak in energy consumption, which differs from the past week, which had very similar environmental conditions (same weather, same use of the school).
- The Energy Manager locates the system at fault and identify for example that unused equipment is kept turned on, due to a faulty thermostat or sensor.
- The Energy Manager turns it off, and, if needed, assess the need for preventative maintenance.

9.2.3 BRU-A-UC2: Detect production anomalies

Use Case description

Another type of anomaly detection (Lu, Xie, Parlikad, & Schooling, 2020) can focus on energy production, which in the case of this LL only focuses on photovoltaic electricity generation at this stage of the project. In this use case related to energy production domain, the DT will detect production anomalies of electrical production provided by the PVs of the LL. It possibly indicates for instance a fault in the systems, broken PV panels or their misalignment.

The DT will use meteorological and asset management, operation and maintenance data (such as the production meters data, PV production models, maintenance data so to know if solar panels are under maintenance or disconnected, solar illumination from the roof sensors), as well as a model of energy production, to ensure that the energy production patterns are aligned with the expected production. The DT will also be connected to the physical equipment through its sensors and digital systems, usually delivered by the equipment suppliers.

In general, the use of smart systems to raise energy inefficiencies using for example Machine Learning, is part of the SOTA (Talei, Benhaddou, Gamarra, Benbrahim, & Essaaidi, 2021), in this case of applied to the specific case of HVAC systems and aiming at better maintenance and

energy usage reduction, and can be expended to wider digital twin based framework for green building maintenance system (DT-GBMS) (Wang, Hu, Zhang, & Hu, 2020).

By proactively and smartly monitoring the energy production systems, the DT will allow the operator of the energy production systems to assess the efficiency of the systems in-time, and online. It allows them to operate the system as efficiently as possible, and to schedule preventative maintenance when necessary, optimizing both maintenance cost and downtime.

User / Actor

This could be:

- LL energy manager
- any actor with an interest in making the LL as energy efficient as possible.

These actors and their number are yet to be confirmed.

User Scenario

- The Energy Manager logs into the dashboard displayed by the DT.
- The Energy Manager sees an unexpected drop in energy production, which differs from the past week, which had seen very similar environmental conditions.
- The Energy Manager locates the panel in question and note that it has been inadvertently covered by workers.
- The Energy Manager and maintenance team put the solar panel back in operation.

9.2.4 BRU-A-UC3: Build energy model for the school equipment usage

Use Case description

In this use case related to energy efficiency, the DT will create models of the LL energy-consuming equipment such as ventilation, lighting, heating, lifts, ... based on the school room usage, and other relevant metrics, such as energy, to predict energy consumption from the current conditions. From the meters reading as well as possibly disaggregated consumption data, the LL can build a model of the school consumption, based on its main consumer constituents, and variables impacting the consumption (sun, weather, temperature inside and in the classrooms, if students use a room, ...) from which usage scenarios can be constructed. The proposed scenarios will focus on the general minimization of energy consumption, the

reduction of the consumption peak and consequently the energy cost and carbon emissions for the school. These models will be based on historical data and provide the bases for a digital twin of the school energy behaviour. The models will be updated on a regular basis from the actual data captured by the DT sensors mentioned above.

In the description of a scenario, the DT will provide electrical and possibly gas consumption, as well as PV production forecasts of the school, and the associated aggregated costs. In case of positive energy, the electric amount which could be potentially sold will be indicated. This forms the part of a new service around energy management (Onile, Machlev, Petlenkov, Levron, & Belikov, 2021). A corresponding KPI could be energy use compared to modelled theoretical energy consumption.

DT user can set some parameters such as students' timetable, solar panel maintenance/cleaning operations, HVAC schedule program (start time/ target temp/stop time ...). It results that the DT will compute a global scenario with a forecast of predicted energy consumption as well as a visualisation of the school KPIs (energy equipment setting updates, rooms temperatures, consumption, import or sales of energy and corresponding cost as well as incomes). This will help manager to choose the best settings for the energy systems.

User will benefit from this use case to take operational (investment, operation and maintenance) data-driven decisions on the basis of proven models. They also capture knowledge to be disseminated to strengthen investment decisions.

User / Actor

Energy Manager: Manage energy production, consumption setting and energy sales. By getting the different energy peak forecast, he can optimize the GBN energy systems settings

Energy Community Member: Each member who is interested in knowing the school energy performance can try different setting for personal interest or studies. The models themselves could be shared with the wider energy community.

User Scenario

- The User logs into the dashboard.
- The Energy Manager compares the simulation of the energy performance taking into account relevant information from the nearest meteorological station (outside temperature, solar radiation, humidity etc.) to the actual consumption of the LL.

- The Energy Manager is for example able to optimize the use of HVAC system as well as the lighting behaviour.

9.3 BRU-B - High-Level Need: Provide a hosting platform for the GBN Energy Community, and connect it to other energy communities

9.3.1 Main objective

The initial high-level need has been focusing on the building scale, for the living lab itself. It is proposed in this second high-level need to explore a wider approach, shifting from a specific building to a wider neighbourhood, be it a GBN or an Energy Community (or both). This type of change of scale is required to start enabling a system of systems approach, linking building, to campus and further out cities (Lu, et al., 2020).

The lack of available energy community related information has been identified as one of the main blockers to growing energy communities. Once the LL-scale (building scale) DT is put in place in the previous high-level need (Brussels UC1 to UC3), the DT can further be extended so to be used as a one-stop shop. This platform will help enable and build a Local Energy Community (LEC), providing information to the wider GBN through a single platform, and acting as a the “social network” of the LEC.

9.3.2 BRU-B-UC1: Provide an information platform to the Energy community

Use Case description

Recognizing that information often falls short of participants expectations, the DT will aim at offering users sets of information to support the activities of the energy community, mostly electricity, but also different types of renewable energy and about storage systems. The provided information by the DT to the energy community are the following ones, listed as both community-management (social network) related information as well as technical information (platform).

The social aspects would be covered, for example, with:

- Best practices to setup an energy community
- Engagement and replication manuals

The platform would also aggregate and consolidate:

- Energy data of the Local Energy Community (LEC) (for example including energy costs, production and consumption metering, ...) as well as to the LL
- Provide “Cognitive DTs” of participants (Adu-Kankam & Camarinha-Matos, Modelling Mutual Influence Towards Sustainable Energy Consumption, 2022)¹⁴, which are agent-based models model technical systems coupled with cognitive capabilities of the systems agents.
- ESG data of the LL to back the school sustainability reporting
- Benchmarks for the assets in the Energy Community following initial situation and selection of the benchmark solutions for optimization.
- Help with the selection of right IoTs devices and technologies for the Energy Community members (Adu-Kankam & Camarinha-Matos, A Framework for the Integration of IoT Components into the Household Digital Twins for Energy Communities, 2022)
- General and possibly detailed description of the EC energy systems and participants
- Curation of technical and behavioural tools for improving Energy Communities (Cuneo, et al., 2021), such as published shared practices by the country of the LL
- Provide a database and storage/information management system concerning Energy performance audits and recommendations,
- Provide the EC members with an energy performance benchmark with other EC members, as well as national performance standards

The LEC Energy Community will start with the Brussels LL, possibly augmented as a first step with the co-tenants of the LL buildings. An EC could then grow from this base, for example with local social housing data, SMEs, local businesses, ...

Moreover, this platform can encompass the mobility sector. It can be used to capture mobility information and connect it to the energy community to holistically optimize energy use. This can be benefit to the Energy Community, but also indicate where to put EV chargers, and where and how to best charge EVs, while keeping a possibility to use them as temporary storage for the energy community (Razmjoo, et al., 2021). This task links to the BRU-C high level need about

¹⁴ <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-431X/12/2/39>

mobility, and feeds on the data provided by the Mobility DT (for example charging points capacity and location, traffic data, weather data, urban GIS data, demographics of the GBN, ...).

User / Actor

Energy Community Member: Each member can access to best practices that optimize their GBN energy systems usage.

Prospective community member: Existing community member will have a platform accepting the member data, and connected to other community members, so to provide the user with demonstrated best practices

Students: improve their knowledge of energy and best practice to impact their energy behaviours, leading to more aware actions and decreased energy usage.

Local decision maker: increase confidence in impacts on ESG indicators, of energy-related investment measures.

User Scenario

Scenario 1:

- The user logs on the platform to get to learn more about their local energy community.
- It provides them with a view of the Local Energy Community mission, the members of their community, how they perform and what were the benefits they got from the community.
- The user can get a clear view and understanding of the impact of cost efficiency (monetary, can also include CO2 emissions) of energy saving/sharing measures.

Scenario 2:

- A LEC member logs on to the platform to get more involved with his energy community.
- The DT shows the energy performance (energy rating displayed as red-amber-green A-B-C energy audits) of the Energy Community, and displays his performance compared to his neighbours. If a neighbour demonstrates a better energy performance, he can contact them to learn about the actions they implemented and deploy them himself.

9.3.3 BRU-B-UC2: Demonstrate and provide financial return of the investment

Use Case description

The DT will give the financial decision maker a clear view of financial incentives and return on investment of given improvement operations. Accessing historical data demonstrates the impact of an intervention on energy performance.

For example, the EC platform has captured the historical data of the EC members' energy consumption baseline, before any intervention. After an improvement intervention (typically installation of new equipment), the DT captures post intervention energy consumption patterns, and is able to infer the corresponding energy savings.

This way, the platform can learn of the improvement of energy use as part of the post-measure implementation tracking, hence performance of an asset.

This data can be used to build a business case for energy performance measures and provide a real-world example case to back the decision to invest. The decision can be taken by individual as well as organizations. The use case benefit consists in increasing confidence in the value for money and impacts on energy-related investment measure.

User / Actor

- Local decision maker
- External decision maker: The energy community perimeter in this case could be energy entities (businesses, housing, tertiary services, ...) connected to the LL, ideally encompassing the students' homes.

User Scenario

- An energy community member logs on the platform to get to further engage with the energy community and help guide investment choices, to buy equipment to optimize and minimize energy consumption.
- The member has access to past operational data that demonstrate a clear ROI of previous investment, not only at a building level but on the wider community, with rippling effects, by piloting new technologies and demonstrate their efficiency at a building scale, for dissemination afterwards at the EC scale.

- It also allows the member as an energy community member to test interventions technology (with impacts on investments) digitally before a decision is made, so that they can be confident in taking a decision, and to share it back with the EC.

9.3.4 BRU-B-UC3: Demonstrate energy-policy impacts to citizens through serious games

As a note, this type of use case builds on the T1.3 GBN Scenario Generation and Strategic Case Studies, with the proposed focus of T1.3 on both Energy and Mobility. This UC is therefore to be investigated in close collaboration with the T1.3, focusing on the rapid scenario generation and evaluation of KPIs, on the one end, and the ST1.3.2 production of the high-level scenario and four case studies for each LL.

Use Case description

The objective of this use case is to help anyone/everyone understand the reason and impacts of measures/policies, to reassure the GBN inhabitants that decisions were the right ones. It puts the “serious gamer” in the shoes of a policy maker and help them understand the decision impacts (Sepasgozar, Digital Twin and Web-Based Virtual Gaming Technologies for Online Education: A Case of Construction Management and Engineering, 2020). It can take a form as simple as a presentation with several slides demonstrating the impacts of measures compared to a baseline of doing nothing, to getting a focused SimCity ready to play with. The serious game approach is increasing being adopted¹⁵ (Olszewski, 2018), which used social education for sustainable development in parallel of creating a virtual model of a city, capturing its spatial, economic, social and legal and running different “versions” of a city.

This serious game can in practice be a set of pre-defined/computed scenarios, that can be explored by the gamer via an interactive dashboard. The gamer then sees the results of their choice (investment policy, regulation, energy mix, ...) on the game indicators (carbon emissions, costs and budgets, users satisfaction, ...).

The game is backed by the real data from baseline and post-implementation measurements, hence reflecting real-life behaviours of the GBN depending on the player’s choice.

¹⁵ The Concept and Development of a Serious Game „Alter Eco” as Part of Creating a Digital Twin of a Smart City, 10.1007/978-3-030-34644-7_40.

User / Actor

The primary users are **the local civil society member** of the GBN, or a **community member**, including **GBN decision-maker**. This wider public will have access to the DT to better understand energy policies and how decisions impact the performance of a GBN.

In the context of the REC, the “**energy community manager**” could be the LL energy manager but could be any actor(s) nominated / chosen by the energy community. Number to be confirmed. The end-user would be any member of the energy community.

The energy community perimeter in this case could be energy entities (businesses, housing, tertiary services, ...) connected to the LL, ideally encompassing the students’ homes.

User Scenario

- A civil society member hops on the platform: she is not a Local decision maker but she is interested in energy-related policy and governance, and wants to understand how the GBN energy management works.
- The platform allows her, like a SimCity of the past, to stress test energy policy ideas and run different scenarios on her neighbourhood, to understand the impacts of these scenarios.

9.3.5 BRU-B-UC4: Interconnect several DTs from several GBNs on the city to make one large-scale DT to allow data exchange

Use Case description

The previous step enables the creation of a local energy community, at the GBN scale (meso-scale).

The step taken by the current use case is to enable the interconnection of Energy Communities (as a system of systems), connecting initiatives undertaken in different places (for example part of different GBNs) together. Interoperability will allow the different DTs (for GBNs and/or LLs) to share information and to be integrated into a wider, global DT, result of a DT network.

To create this network of DTs, the EC DT will be able to be a driving node of the network, proposing for example standards for data exchanges, access to the tools underpinning the platform (UC1/2/3), and ultimately enabling the interconnection of two EC DTs. This can be backed by using open standards, APIs, and an open-data approach.

User / Actor

The primary actors for this are the energy community member, who wants to learn from other energy communities, and the Energy community manager/leader, who will lead realizing the benefits of accessing a larger community of energy communities.

User Scenario

- A member of the local Energy community (LEC) is enthusiastic about the growth and development of his energy community: he has met great people willing to put effort to save the planet while saving money, putting social transformation in action. Still, he has heard other energy communities exist and he wants to learn from them. Because they are sharing their energy community knowledge with other ECs, he can readily access communities similar to his LEC, in particular those where schools are helping accelerate the change in their communities.
- He then discovers that a neighbouring school is initiating an energy community on its own: might be worth paying them a visit to share his LEC's experience with them.

9.4 BRU-C - High-Level Need: Evaluate the GBN evolution and new designs in terms of mobility

9.4.1 Main objective

During the stakeholder workshop, transforming mobility has been identified as another high-level need for the Brussels DT, even if this was not readily identified in the initial Probono project description. This impacts in turn safety and security, social development, health and air quality. As opposed to the previous high-level needs for the LL, this high-level need focuses on a DT at purely GBN level. Moreover, where the GBN energy use cases described above were owned by different entities and organizations, the mobility network does fall under a city remit.

The benefits for the LL of this need to support the transformation into a safer, healthier, more liveable neighbourhood. It would impact the LL in terms of safety, security and health of the GBN inhabitants (e.g., students and staff members etc.). However, its more significant use for the LL would be to a catalyst for the GBN transformation.

As such, it has been identified that the DT basically needs “static” information (detailed in the following “Inventory and requirement” section, for example geographical information systems (GIS) data of the road networks including cycling public transportation, and pedestrian infrastructure, traffic flows, public transportation accessibility, road descriptions (width, lanes, materials, length, etc) ...). and would not always need to connect with the physical twin through live sensors or actuators. However, after determining the baseline technological feasibility of the use case, the use of sensors could emerge as a possibility. This task will be undertaken in close collaboration with the mobility partners, particularly IRTSX and VIAS, to be sure that their knowledge, expertise and know-how is fully integrated in this DT use case. One will note that the accountable organization for urban mobility will be city-scale, who will own the DT use.

For the Digital Twin, a single use case was covered during the initial high-level needs capture phase. It is expected that the DT will help decision makers and mobility experts assess the impact of change (technical or behavioural) on mobility patterns, to optimise for safety, quality of life of the LL users (eg air quality), and energy consumption as well as the GBN inhabitants.

9.4.2 BRU-C-UC1: Find the best mobility scenario and their impacts

As a note, this type of use case builds on the T1.3 GBN Scenario Generation and Strategic Case Studies, with the proposed focus of T1.3 on both Energy and Mobility. This UC is therefore to be developed in close collaboration with the T1.3, focusing on the rapid scenario generation and evaluation of KPIs, on the one end, and the ST1.3.2 production of the high-level scenario and four case studies for each LL.

Use Case description

The DT objective is to simulate the different active and micro-mobility scenarios around the school, and allows running simulations of transport alternatives, to quantify the impact on quality of life (security, time of travel, quality of air, health, energy consumption) of the GBN inhabitant, based on a model yet to be determined.

This objective would be achieved by the multimodal transportation / mobility models that can be developed by the project transportation partners, to which is added the data of the physical mobility networks (roads, cycling lanes, pedestrian lanes, crossing,) along with demographics / users' information, and overarching macrolevel transportation information (emission per type of transportation mode, air quality impact of mobility solutions, ...). As such, this use case description will be refined for the next deliverable if it is selected to be part of the implemented

DTs, as the project will have a clearer view of the transportations models inventories, provided by technical partners, LLs, or possibly sister projects and open-source initiatives.

The DT is used to assess the different mobility patterns, alternatives, and their impacts on the GBN inhabitants quality of life, to identify solutions that make GBN the most pleasant while preserving the mobility requirements. The output of the DT would be scenarios visualisation related to safety and access of the GBN inhabitants (e.g. replacing car lanes by cycling lanes and sidewalks, defining alternative access routes, infrastructural changes to stimulate active transport modes), describing the interaction and flow of the different road users (e.g. 100 bikes / hour on a cycling lane), which in turn can derive improvement for air quality and/or CO2 emissions, as well as changes in mean times in transportation (e.g. time for a student to reach the school).

For example, the models could demonstrate the immediate and SDG impacts of urban and mobility options, such as by transforming a road in a pedestrian street, or by introducing public transportation options (eg optimization of public transportation, by revisiting bus stops locations and schedules, particularly interesting in a school context). Moreover, this series of models could be used to propose parking space optimization, EV and bike charging points locations, and urban modifications for example to increase the safety of a street for active and micro-mobility (e.g. electric scooters, electric bicycles) users and pedestrians.

In practice, this tool can take the form of an interactive fiction, practically a series of choices, that demonstrate the impact of the choice of the player-user on the GBN sustainability indicators compared to a baseline on interactive panels.

The perimeter of this use case would be the GBN, that is the LL and its neighbourhood. The use case based on mobility is a natural social platform which can play key role in facilitating the integration of urban reality and development through sustainable collaboration.

User / Actor

The user will be a decision maker or a team working on mobility (urban planners / mobility providers, cities decision makers¹⁶...). Another beneficiary of the DT could be the Energy community described earlier, as transportation represents energy, and because of the similarities in opportunities for scenario testing / serious games. Last but

¹⁶ <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-03199715/document>

not least, a possible user would be a prospective urban planner. When running simulations of transport alternatives to better and confidently quantify the impact of the GBN inhabitants quality of life (safety and security, time of travel, quality of air, ...).

User Scenario

The Brussels LL is at the crossroads of two major roads and a lot of traffic passes by which impacts the quality of the GBN and LL. I want to run a test to see if creating a parking for micro-mobility modes at local businesses parking spaces and suggesting alternative access point for BLL could help reduce the interaction between pedestrian and the traffic in the GBN and increase safety for all. After all, there are major crossings, and the kids are not always cautious using their electrical steps!

9.5 Data – Inventory and requirements

9.5.1 Shared datasets

Linked use cases	Dataset name	Dataset content description	Data provider	Static or dynamic	Dataset availability
BRU	Classroom plans	Plans with name classrooms	ACE	static	Yes
BRU	Works programme	Presentation of the planned renovation works	ACE	static	Yes
BRU	Photos of technical elements	Pictures of technical elements being renovated	ACE	static	Yes
BRU	Plans and programme of the school	Different plans, table with surfaces...	ACE	static	Yes
BRU-A	3D model of the school	Architectural and CAD drawings of the buildings	Anerdgy	dynamic	Yes – on OnShape (browser-based CAD platform for sharing and visualizing BIM elements)
BRU-A	3D model of the school	Results of the Anerdgy optioneering: geometrical representation (or BIM model) of the school's roof in the different configuration of the PV panels.	Anerdgy	static	Yes – on OnShape (browser-based CAD platform for sharing and visualizing BIM elements)

Table 18: Brussels LL - Shared datasets on high level needs

9.5.2 Energy monitoring and management is based on data related to:

In the data inventory here, we are looking at a description of the different systems in the LL, in particular:

- Energy data (all utilities) – meters in particular. To be aligned further with the different suppliers/technology providers. This can include water, gas, electricity as meter reading.
- Possible operational data from the school: environmental data such as humidity, luminosity, pressure low and high CO2 levels, unstable off-coil temperatures, lower than expected air temperatures, sensors for doors and windows, data usage from the school classroom occupancy planning, faulty energy consumption meters, VOC sensors, data from the maintenance systems (GED¹⁷ systems) ... This comes for example from smart monitoring devices for lighting and ventilation. There could be data coming from users' surveys (teachers, students, staff, ...)
- At the GBN level, data required could be open-data sets from the Commune, data captured in the energy community portal, data coming from user energy consumptions, as well as network models for the mobility high level need.

Linked use cases	Dataset name	Dataset content description	Data provider	Static or dynamic	Dataset availability
BRU-A	Anerdgy Report for BXL	Audit and report of the Anerdgy finding regarding energy performance. Anerdgy, a PROBONO partner, does not only develop renewable energy production systems, but integrates them into global development projects that combine functionality, design and energy.	Anerdgy	static	<u>Yes</u>
BRU-A	Electric Energy Meter reading	Once the meters are installed, meters reading will be made available through the TPF platform.	Not yet identified	dynamic	Not confirmed
BRU-A	Energy Audit	An energy audit of the LL (QuickScan report) providing energy saving recommendations.	Anerdgy	Static	<u>Yes</u>
BRU-A	Estimated cost/m2 for PV installation and yield	High level values of the CAPEX for PV panels installation.	Anerdgy	static	<u>Yes</u>
BRU-A	Meteorological data	Meteorological data	Different weather	dynamic	Yes

¹⁷ Gestion Electronique de Documents

Linked use cases	Dataset name	Dataset content description	Data provider	Static or dynamic	Dataset availability
			forecast sources for these data		
BRU-A	Operational dataset	Humidity	TelcoServ / AdaptIt (TBC)	dynamic	Not confirmed
BRU-A	Operational dataset	Luminosity	TelcoServ / AdaptIt (TBC)	dynamic	Not confirmed
BRU-A	Operational dataset	Pressure	TelcoServ / AdaptIt (TBC)	dynamic	Not confirmed
BRU-A	Operational dataset	CO2 level	TelcoServ / AdaptIt (TBC)	dynamic	Not confirmed
BRU-A	Operational dataset	Voltage measurement	TelcoServ / AdaptIt (TBC)	dynamic	Not confirmed
BRU-A	Operational dataset	Current use measurement	TelcoServ / AdaptIt (TBC)	dynamic	Not confirmed
BRU-A	Operational dataset	Doors sensor status – if deemed relevant	TelcoServ / AdaptIt (TBC) (if hall sensor for example)	dynamic	Not confirmed
BRU-A	Operational dataset	Windows sensor status – if deemed relevant	TelcoServ / AdaptIt (TBC) (if hall sensor for example)	dynamic	Not confirmed
BRU-A	Operational dataset	data usage from classroom occupancy planning to indicate which classroom is used and when	Not yet identified	Dynamic / static	Not confirmed
BRU-A	Operational dataset	Presence sensors	TelcoServ / AdaptIt (TBC)	dynamic	Not confirmed
BRU-A	Operational dataset	VOC sensors measured data	TelcoServ / AdaptIt (TBC)	dynamic	Not confirmed
BRU-A	Operational dataset	Data from maintenance systems (GED systems)	Not yet identified	Usually dynamic, refreshed daily	Not confirmed
BRU-A	Rain data	Heavy precipitation statistics (KOSTRA- DWD) provide information on the probability of occurrence of heavy rain of various durations in Germany (as a proxy for Belgium).	Online	dynamic	Online
BRU-A	Solar potential	Description of the solar irradiation potential	https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/pvgis-online-tool/en	Static	Purchased datasets usually, with sources available through others.

Linked use cases	Dataset name	Dataset content description	Data provider	Static or dynamic	Dataset availability
BRU-A	Timetables	Students' timetable,	GBN staff	Static, refreshed weekly	Not confirmed
BRU-A	Timetables	Solar panel maintenance/cleaning operations, linked to the GED systems	Not yet identified	Usually dynamic, refreshed daily	To be sent by PV equipment maintainer.
BRU-A	Timetables	HVAC schedule program (start time/ target temp/stop time)	Not yet identified	Ideally dynamic	Not confirmed
BRU-A	Electricity usage 2022	Energy use per month, single row, electricity use of the LL	SharePoint, Elec_ACE.xlsx	static	Yes
BRU-A	Gas usage 2022	Gas use per month, single row, electricity	Gas_ACE.xlsx	static	High level historical data
BRU-A	Gas usage 2021/22	Excel with gas use of the school	ACE	static	Yes
BRU-A	Energy invoices	Energy usage invoices detailing energy consumption of the building	ACE	Static	Yes
BRU-A-UC1	Estimated Energy demand	Output of the Anergdy model for energy demand.	Anergdy	Static	<u>Yes</u>
BRU-A-UC1	Past period energy demands	Processed data of the past energy data.	Anergdy	Static	<u>Yes</u>
BRU-A-UC2	Actual Photovoltaic electricity production	API providing access to the actual production of the PV installation	Not yet identified	Dynamic	The connection to the dataset will be made available by the PV suppliers once the PV panels are made available
BRU-A-UC2	Estimated Photovoltaic electricity production	Study from Anergdy on the possible yield of the PV installation	Anergdy	Static	<u>Yes</u>
BRU-A-UC3	Gas and Energy Pricing	Energy provider (ENGIE possibly) to share the prices of energy, at least on a monthly basis or through the invoice	Energy and gas tariffs (yearly)	Dynamic (monthly)	Yes To be captured through invoices
BRU-C	Map of the GBN neighbourhood in terms of mobility	Map and geospatial information of the mobility networks as well as ground use.	Open data	Dynamic (live data from OSM for example)	Yes, through OpenStreetMap and/or other maps providers

Linked use cases	Dataset name	Dataset content description	Data provider	Static or dynamic	Dataset availability
BRU-B	General GBN data	Charging points capacity and location, traffic data, weather data, urban GIS data, demographics of the GBN	Not yet identified	Accessed as required	Not confirmed, could be through OpenStreetMap and/or other maps providers
BRU-B-UC1	Energy data of the Local Energy Community (LEC)	Energy data coming from the energy community members, covering energy costs, production and consumption metering, ...	Not yet identified	Either through live metering for some members, or	Not confirmed yet, to be identified as the GBN stakeholder engagement progresses.
BRU-B-UC1	EC Energy Data - Production	EC members production data	To be sent by EC members	Same as above	Same as above
BRU-B-UC1	EC Energy Data - Consumption	EC members consumption data	To be sent by EC members	Same as above	Same as above
BRU-B-UC3	Energy Consumption History	Consumption data made available in monthly invoicing or audit reports 2019-2022 on electricity and gas	Some shared by Anergdy.	static	Some on the SharePoint.

Table 19: Brussels LL - Energy monitoring and management datasets

9.5.3 Mobility related datasets

Linked use cases	Dataset name	Dataset content description	Data provider	Static or dynamic	Dataset availability
BRU-C	Accidents numbers and causes at GBN	Accidents numbers and causes at GBN, as well as supportive information	VIAS (to be confirmed)	Static / updated monthly	To be confirmed by VIAS
BRU-C	Availability, accessibility, and usage of public and shared transport modes	Density in peak hours and in general, operators of these public transport, pricing distribution, utility in peak hours	Not yet identified	static	Availability not yet confirmed. Possible use of open datasets. See below for specific datasets. Required by BRU-C-UC1 models (LEAD)
BRU-C	Brussels mobility data	The https://data.mobility.brussels portal contains a set of open data related to mobility in the Brussels-Capital Region. A cartographic interface is available to view the data directly. Information can also be found on the mobility portal.	Open data	static	Yes https://www.transportdata.be/dataset/brussels-mobility-data

Linked use cases	Dataset name	Dataset description	content	Data provider	Static or dynamic	Dataset availability
BRU-C	Transportation Network topology	The dataset covers the different mobility networks around the school and in the Brussels GBN. These can be geospatial networks representations, for example exported of OSM by OSMnx. Required by BRU-C-UC1 models (LEAD)		Open data, possibly completed by more precise information	static	OSM for network: OpenStreetMap api through osmnx for example, or open data : https://www.transportdata.be/dataset/belgian-road-network-top10vector
BRU-C	Brussels pedestrian network	Local geospatial information of the pedestrian network.		Open data	static	Yes https://www.transportdata.be/dataset/brussels-pedestrian-network
BRU-C	Bus stops close to schools	Local geospatial information of the public transportation assets.		Open data	static	Yes https://opendata.bruxelles.be/explore/dataset/busscolaires/information/
BRU-C	EV Charger location	Local geospatial information of the EV charging infrastructure.		Open data	static	Yes https://opendata.bruxelles.be/explore/dataset/bornes-de-recharge-pour-voitures-electriques/information/
BRU-C	Facilities data in mobility	Parking distribution and pricing - commune & in de direct vicinity of the school, Number of public and private EV chargers, number of public parking spots, Cycling infrastructure		Not yet identified	static	Availability not yet confirmed. Possible use of open datasets. Required by BRU-C-UC1 models (LEAD)
BRU-C	Macro level data	Macro level data (demographics, zoning)		Not yet identified - some detailed below as part of the open datasets	static	Availability not yet confirmed. Possible use of open datasets. Required by BRU-C-UC1 models (LEAD)
BRU-C	Mobility static information (plan)	“static” information (geographical information systems (GIS) data of the networks, including roads, cycling lanes, traffic lights, road descriptions (width, lanes, materials, length, etc) ...		Not yet identified - some detailed below as part of the open datasets	static	Availability not yet confirmed. Possible use of open datasets. Required by BRU-C-UC1 models (LEAD)

Linked use cases	Dataset name	Dataset description	content	Data provider	Static or dynamic	Dataset availability
BRU-C	Population daily mobility patterns and challenges	Details of travel to school and back to home: including time, mode, distance etc.		Not yet identified	static	Availability not yet confirmed. Possible use of open datasets. Required by BRU-C-UC1 models (LEAD)
BRU-C	Public parking in BXL	Details of car park spaces and facilities, geospatial information.		Open data	static	YES https://opendata.bruxelles.be/explore/dataset/bruxelles_parkings_publics/information/
BRU-C	Transit vehicles specs	Density in peak hours and in general, operators of these public transport, pricing distribution, utility in peak hours		Not yet identified	static	Availability not yet confirmed. Possible use of open datasets. Required by BRU-C-UC1 models (LEAD)
BRU-C	Weather conditions at GBN	Weather APIs		Not yet identified	static	Already described in the energy table. Required by BRU-C-UC1 models (LEAD)

Table 20: Brussels LL - Mobility related datasets

9.6 Decision-making tools – Inventory and requirements

Tool name	Tool/model description	Tool provider	Input data	Output data
MATSim agent-based simulation framework (ETH, TUB, IRTSX)	MATSim is a general-purpose multiagent transport simulation framework. It consists of a traffic simulation component, which simulates the movements of people and vehicles in detail on a fine-grained road network, and a behavioural component which simulates various decisions such as mode choices in response to the observed traffic conditions in the transport system. It is hence able to study the impact of new logistics solutions on the local population in terms of emissions, noise, and congestion (for all of which analysis extensions are available) and to observe the complex interplay in terms of adapted travel behaviour given the novel elements in the transport network IRTSX and INLECOM have local technical expertise for MATSim +	IRTSX Proposition to connect with "MOBI VUB" PhD student - (Jingjun Li: https://ethz.ch/content/dam/ethz/special-interest/baug/ivt/ivt-dam/events/2022/05/31/presentations/Li_EtAl_MUM_2022.pdf - we are currently also doing some research using the model related to transport emissions for Brussels Low Emission Zone (https://lez.brussels/mytax/#).)	Network topology, households data (sociodemographic attributes), population's daily mobility patterns, facilities data in the mobility data, public transport schedule, transit vehicles specification. In LEAD, IRTSX also included a simulation according to the freight delivery demand (but it is less popular and re-used than the main version of MATSim including	All the urban passengers' trips (including mode and distance) made by vehicles in the fleet, congestion information, all mobility plans of agents (passengers in the simulation). If LEAD's freight extension is used then the results include congestion according to freight and trips of delivery fleet.

Tool name	Tool/model description	Tool provider	Input data	Output data
	COPERT solution to run the simulation for BLL mobility use case. The mobility use-case would possibly be focused on policy level (e.g. making the roads in the school neighbourhood more pedestrian street/bike street and checking the impact on the neighbourhood on air quality, emission and safety). The realistic use case would be defined around the BLL and neighborhood after collecting high-level info around BLL (to do VIAS and presenting a use case in follow-up meeting on 17th February).		only mobility patterns)	
COPERT (EMISIA)	Computer Program to calculate Emissions from Road Traffic – COPERT is the EU standard vehicle emissions calculator. It calculates emissions and energy consumption for a specific country or region. The model includes expressions for cold start and evaporative emissions and accounts as far as possible for national variations in such parameters as vehicle parking duration, vehicle age, driving patterns, fuel composition, and climate. Emissions are estimated using average speed-dependent factors for hot emissions.	IRTSX (reused)	Temperature and humidity data, traffic estimates, vehicle types used, activity per vehicle type, number of vehicles	Total energy consumption and estimated air pollution metric (CO2, PM2.5, NO2, VOC)
Simulation of Urban Mobility (SUMO)	SUMO is a free and open-source traffic simulation suite. It is available since 2001 and allows modelling of intermodal traffic systems - including road vehicles, public transport and pedestrians. Included with SUMO is a wealth of supporting tools which automate core tasks for the creation, the execution and evaluation of traffic simulations, such as network import, route calculations, visualization and emission calculation. SUMO can be enhanced with custom models and provides various APIs to remotely control the simulation.	IRTSX (reused)	Road network data, vehicle weights/density (lane and road based), O/D matrix, travel time, new safety parameter integration	Travel time, flow capacity ratio, lane peak traffic density, vehicle pedestrian interaction,
EnPower Platform Anomaly detection	- Anomaly detection for PV based on HDBSCAN	STAM	PV --> solar radiation, energy production	Anomalies

Tool name	Tool/model description	Tool provider	Input data	Output data
EnPower Platform Anomaly detection	- Anomaly detection for HVAC based on HDBSCAN	STAM	HVAC --> Energy consumption, T entering, T exiting	anomalies
EnPower Platform Scheduler	- Comfort based energy optimizer providing optimal load scheduling for next 7 days	STAM	Technical features of the different electrical loads, indoor temperature (time series), outdoor temperature (time series), electrical loads for all thermal appliances (time-series), physical feature of controlled area (size, geometry, windows, etc), user constraints	Optimal load scheduling for next 7 days
NovaDM	Decision Support System for renovation activities - NovaDM . Use to be confirmed	Aarhus	List of equipments, and maintenance operations	Decisions for renovation scenarios
RoofBot	This solution is not public yet but can be built further for more international projects. It is a semi-automated tool to create roofs designs (greening, terrasses,..)	Anerdgy	Geometric design of the living lab.	Possible designs for roof
Smart Mobility Planner	The 4 Belgian public transport companies have joined forces to create an intermodal travel planner. SMOP integrates real-time data from mobility operators De Lijn, Tec, Stib and SNCB as well as other service providers into a single interface, which provides the best route for its users. The data of the Smart Mobility Planner is accessible via an open-source, multimodal WebApp (bus, train, streetcar, metro and bike). In the future, new partners and new features could be added. https://www.transportdata.be/dataset/smart-mobility-planner	external	Mobility network data	Decision focusing of optimizing the choice of networks for the most efficient route
Sensors MQTT Server	Provide back the sensors data through an API through a TelcoServ-managed server - real-time data 24/7.	TelcoServ / AdaptIt (TBC)	These are sensors, measures come	Digitalized measures of the environmental

Tool name	Tool/model description	Tool provider	Input data	Output data
			from the physical world	parameters to be captured.
Demand and Response platform	STAM and TPF propose a joint tool based on TPF and STAM solutions.	TPF & STAM	Metering devices and recipies	Optimization of the most efficient GBN usage
Enectiva	<p>Enectiva is a web-based energy information and control system provided as SaaS that is used to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitor and readout energy meters or any other data source • Calculate and analyze costs and energy consumption it in statistics • Provide Building Management Solutions via Control units • Evaluate automatically consumptions and cost via notifications • Generate and automate energy invoices, reports and delivered charts 	Coming from TPF. Stored on the project SharePoint.	<p>Invoices</p> <p>Description of the physical systems (eg HVAC)</p> <p>Sensors data</p>	<p>Building management scenarios</p> <p>Invoices</p> <p>Energy information reporting and dashboards</p>

Table 21: Brussels LL - Decision making tools inventory

9.7 Visualization tools – Inventory and requirements

No specific visualization tools have been identified. Other tools that could be used include:

- Dashboards (PowerBI or others)
- Maps visualisations, Dashboard (might be)
- Maps visualisations
- EnPower – a Dashboard hosted on web application with knowledge and communication management system for energy community
- Rhino/Grasshopper: Grasshopper is a visual programming language and environment that runs within the Rhinoceros 3D computer-aided design (CAD) application. Grasshopper include parametric modelling structure, architecture or building energy consumption.

9.8 DT & external systems – Interoperability requirements

Interface/integration of decision-making tools:

Interoperability Requirements	Concerned tool	Description
BRU-INTER-REQ-1	MATSim agent-based simulation framework	This tool shall be either interfaced from a partner instance, or integrated in the DT, depending on partners capacity.
BRU-INTER-REQ-2	COPERT (EMISIA)	This tool shall be either interfaced from a partner instance, or integrated in the DT, depending on partners capacity.
BRU-INTER-REQ-3	Simulation of Urban Mobility (SUMO)	This tool shall be either interfaced from a partner instance, or integrated in the DT, depending on partners capacity.
BRU-INTER-REQ-4	EnPower Platform - Anomaly detection	This tool shall be Interfaced to the DT, connection through REST APIs to the technical partner instance
BRU-INTER-REQ-5	EnPower Platform - Anomaly detection	This tool shall be Interfaced to the DT, connection through REST APIs to the technical partner instance
BRU-INTER-REQ-6	EnPower Platform - Scheduler	This tool shall be Interfaced to the DT, connection through REST APIs to the technical partner instance
BRU-INTER-REQ-7	NovaDM	This tool shall be integrated in the DT.
BRU-INTER-REQ-8	RoofBot	This tool shall be Interfaced to the DT, connection through REST APIs to the technical partner instance
BRU-INTER-REQ-9	Smart Mobility Planner	This tool shall be integrated in the DT.
BRU-INTER-REQ-10	Sensors MQTT Server	This tool shall be interfaced with the sensors server / provider (TelcoServ)
BRU-INTER-REQ-11	Demand and Response platform	This tool shall be Interfaced to the DT, connection through REST APIs to the technical partner instance
BRU-INTER-REQ-12	Enectiva	This tool shall be Interfaced to the DT, connection through REST APIs to the technical partner instance
BRU-INTER-REQ-13	faireBXLsamen Platform	faireBXLsamen is an IT collaborative engagement tools developed by Brussels municipality ¹⁸ which includes participatory processes for school stakeholders.

¹⁸ <https://fairebruxellessamen.be/?locale=fr> <https://fairebruxellessamen.be/?locale=fr>

		The opportunity and the feasibility of the connection between this tool and the DT should be studied.
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Table 22: Brussels LL - Interoperability requirements

10 AAR - Aarhus University Living Lab

10.1 Living Lab Context

10.1.1 Location

This area of Aarhus University was previously the site of an old hospital and is now being renovated to become the location of a number of AU buildings. There are roughly 20 buildings in the University City. A few of them will be selected as part of the AU LL in collaboration with the building owner organization, FEAS. Figure 25 illustrates a map showing where University City (Universitetsbyen) is located in relation to other AU sites, and the two living lab buildings (with The Kitchen 1.0 shown for further context).

Table 23 below summarises the two AU living lab buildings, their building number in the University City, the current intended new function of the living lab, and building phase.

The Kitchen 1.0 is located in building 1770 in the University City. The Kitchen 2.0 is located in buildings 23 and 24 in the University City. BSS is located in building 1850 in the University City.

Building(s)	Building no.	Function	Phase	DT Role
The Kitchen 2.0	23, 24	Refurbishment / renovation	Early sketches	DT for renovation
Business school (BSS)	1850	Refurbishment / renovation	Tender phase	DT for renovation

Table 23: Aarhus LL - Summary of two lab buildings of Aarhus University

Figure 25: Aarhus LL - Location of University City (within the red dashed line), and the two buildings in the University City: The Kitchen 2.0 and BSS.

10.1.2 Physical Twin Composition

- The kitchen

The Kitchen is a start-up hub to facilitate network between innovators, researchers, investors, and companies. The Kitchen concept includes a café, mixed-up meeting and working areas for staff and start-ups, bathroom facilities, and a large mixed-use room that is used to host more than 50 events annually, such as inspirational and professional talks, networking and social events, investor events, workshops, and pitch sessions.

- The AU School of Business and Social Sciences

The AU School of Business and Social Sciences (BSS) is one of the largest schools of business and social sciences in Europe. The entire department, 37.000 m², is moving into the University City by 2025. The new BSS is a mix of old hospital buildings that are undergoing deep refurbishment, some of the old hospital buildings are demolished in order to create underground parking and therefore new buildings are mixed with the renovated buildings.

10.1.3 Physical Twin users

There are two main buildings that are involved in Probono:

- The kitchen, where users are innovators, researchers, investors, and companies.
- The AU School of Business and Social Sciences where users are mainly the students and the university staff.

10.1.4 Physical Twin Current Status

- The kitchen

The Kitchen 1.0 is currently in use and the operation will move to the Kitchen 2 when the building is renovated and operational. Kitchen 1 has building permit until 2025 and will eventually be demolished and make room for a student house complex. The Kitchen 2.0 is in the early sketch phase of design.

The current Kitchen building (referred to as The Kitchen 1.0) is acting as a trial run of the start-up hub concept that took advantage of an area of the University City that was not being utilized. The Kitchen 1.0 was designed and operated by Gustaf Lohm (co-PI in Probono, affiliated with AU). It opened in 2019 and is set to be demolished after 2025.

Figure 26 presents photos of the exterior of the current buildings to be renovated. Figure 27 presents photos of the interior of the boiler room, and Figure 28 presents photos of the interior of the former laundry facility. Figure 29 presents visualisations of the designed interior renovation of the boiler room.

Figure 26: Aarhus LL - Exterior of building 24 on the University City site, future Kitchen 2.0

Figure 27: Aarhus LL - Interior of building 24 on the University City site, future Kitchen 2.0

Figure 28: Aarhus LL - Current interior of building 23 (the laundry facility), future Kitchen 2.0

- The AU School of Business and Social Sciences

BSS is in the tender phase of the design. The AU School of Business and Social Sciences (BSS) is one of the largest schools of business and social sciences in Europe.

10.1.5 Physical Twin post-Probono expected status

The next iteration, referred to as The Kitchen 2.0, will occupy a new building, and is being designed and developed based on lessons learnt from The Kitchen 1.0. The newly renovated building is a boiler room and laundry facility for the former hospital.

The Kitchen 2.0 is currently in the design stage. It is a deep renovation project that is converting an old hospital boiler room (building #24) and laundry facility (building #23) into the start-up hub.

Figure 29: Aarhus LL - Visualizations of the designed interior of building 24, future Kitchen 2.0

The BSS will be relocated to the University City in 2025. The BSS project is a 37.000sqm deep refurbishment currently in the tender phase. The new building will consist of six floors. Figure 30 and Figure 31 present visualisations of two rooms in the newly designed BSS.

Figure 30: Aarhus LL - Visualization of the covered courtyard area at BSS, with glass roofing, indoor plants and wood strip design features

Figure 31: Aarhus LL - Visualization of the BSS large hall

10.1.6 Digital Twin High Level Needs requested

The concept for the AU LL is to deploy “virtual sensors” into the as-designed BIM model of The Kitchen 2.0 and BSS and run simulations and static analyses to predict key performance indicator values. A key novelty of the AU LL is the focus on qualitative, human-centred indicators pertaining to occupant experience, such as thermal comfort, a sense of privacy, air quality, appropriate aromas, view out quality, wayfinding orientation and so on. Once the buildings become operational, the predictions will be compared with reality, and the outcome of the comparison will be used to generate new knowledge for future designs and subsequent renovation and reconfiguration stages of The Kitchen 2.0 and BSS. The goal of this LL is to apply all the use cases to both physical twins starting with the kitchen.

This section presents the two high-level needs of the DT linked to the LL of Aarhus.

High Level Need	Physical domain	Functional domain
Ensuring that the final design will meet their necessary criteria	Kitchen 2.0 and BSS	Building Design
Generating new knowledge on whether design rationale and intention was accurate	Kitchen 2.0 and BSS	Building Design

Table 24: Aarhus LL - DT High Level Need list

10.2 AAR-A - High Level Need: Ensure that final design meet the required criteria for a sustainable building

10.2.1 Main objective

The primary benefit to the AU LL is ensuring that the final design of The Kitchen 2.0 and BSS will meet their necessary criteria in terms of occupant experience according to DGNB gold, environment impacts (CO₂, energy) and financial cost¹⁹. Indeed, other AU buildings that have recently undergone renovation have performed poorly in terms of occupant experience, which contributed to a failure to meet their predicted CO₂ and energy usage targets. This is the major novelty and value that is currently missing from the living lab. To achieve these “high level” benefits, the AU LL will additionally benefit from consultation, collaboration, and co-creation with Probono experts in addressing questions such as:

- What (virtual and real) sensors should be used to gather the required data from the building in the operational phase?
- Where should sensors be placed?
- How should the (low abstraction level) sensor readings be interpreted to get (high abstraction level) information on occupant experience?
- How can qualitative, subjective occupant experience be evaluated from a building design?
- How can different design options be compared in terms the intersectional impact on occupant experience, environment (energy and CO₂) and financial cost?
- How can the choice of reusing materials (e.g., brickwork) be quantified in terms of LCA, i.e., upcycling?
- Should upcycling be incorporated into the design of The Kitchen 2.0 and BSS?

In this high-level need, four use cases will be presented:

- **AAR-A-UC1:** Provide rapid feedback on LCA metrics at an early design stage
- **AAR-A-UC2:** Provide feedback on human-centred "soft" criteria at early design stage
- **AAR-A-UC3:** Provide feedback on human-centered criteria to engineer (e.g. HVAC, fire safety, statics specialist) when updating the design.
- **AAR-A-UC4:** Provide automated DGNB-specific assessment during design space exploration.

¹⁹ The university is undergoing a major construction and renovation programme called Campus 2.0. The University City is just one site within the Campus 2.0 programme, and The Kitchen 2.0 and BSS projects comprise 2-3 buildings out of around 20 with University City.

10.2.2 AAR-A-UC1: Provide rapid feedback on LCA metrics at an early design stage

Use Case description

The design team (including architects) is in the early design stage of designing The Kitchen 2.0 and BSS buildings, and needs information on the estimated CO2 footprint, energy consumption, and other LCA metrics. Two problems are as follows:

- The designs of the current Kitchen 2.0 and BSS buildings currently lack many specific details, such as the specific materials of various building components, their exact geometries, and so on.
- There is a relatively high degree of uncertainty in how those missing details will be filled in as the design continues to develop. For example, in the current design a slab is assigned a particular geometry and volume, but the designer knows that this shape will certainly be “tweaked” and changed later, but it’s difficult to say concretely. This makes it difficult to estimate the final LCA score of the current design.

The following figure is an example of the level of design that The Kitchen 2.0 is in:

Figure 32: Aarhus LL - Example of the level of design that The Kitchen 2.0

The design team needs information on:

- design sensitivity: which (small) changes have a disproportionately large impact on LCA metrics
- what kinds of changes to particular building components are (1) feasible, sensible, plausible and (2) likely.

The Probono decision support tool includes Consequential LCA calculations (how CO2, energy usage etc. change in response to possible decisions), adapted to make estimates on early-stage designs.

This includes a new “sustainability opportunity metric” for identifying “hot spots”,²⁰ (Kamari & Schultz, 2022) aspects in the design where changes are likely and can have a drastic impact on

²⁰ Details of our preliminary work on this are published in the conference paper:
Kamari, A. and Schultz C. “How can LCA inform early-stage design to meet Danish regulations?”

LCA metrics. LCA metrics should be calculated quickly (in the order of fractions of a second) so that the metric estimates are updated in real time as the design explores alternative design decisions.

This information should be presented visually, by colour coding building elements. Ideally this would be integrated directly into a BIM-based design tool such as Revit, although the main software module responsible for calculating the metrics is developed as an independent external software tool that can (in principle) be “plugged in” to other BIM design tools or used as a stand-alone command-line tool.

The following figures illustrate our current prototypes implemented in the BIM tool Revit.

Figure 33: Aarhus LL - Gradient visualization using sustainability opportunity mode (green)

Figure 34: Aarhus LL - Sustainability risk mode (red)

$\alpha = 70\%$	$\alpha = 50\%$	$\alpha = 30\%$	$\alpha = 20\%$

Table 25: Aarhus LL - Threshold cut-off with four α values in sustainability opportunity mode

User / Actor

- Architects:

The sustainability opportunity metric., in proc. 14th European Conference on Product & Process Modelling (ECPM 2022), 2022

- Domain / Scope: Building Design
- Benefit: Instant feedback on LCA impacts at a relatively early design stage.

User Scenario

1. The architect is working on their current design in Revit
2. They click a button “Activate: sustainability opportunity metric” (implemented as a custom plug-in)
3. The visualization of their 3D BIM appears in a colour coded form (as illustrated in above figures)
4. A floating panel contains options for selecting one from a set of sustainability opportunity metrics, and displaying a more detailed textual read-out of the analysis
5. The designer makes changes to their design in Revit, and the colours are updated automatically (within less than a second) in response to the design change
6. The architect untoggles the “Activate sustainability opportunity metric” button to return to the standard Revit visualisation.

10.2.3 AAR-A-UC2: Provide feedback on human-centred "soft" criteria at early design stage

Use Case description

A key problem is that, currently, there is no automated analysis for judging "soft" human-centred criteria. When exploring the design space, the design team should get feedback on which human-centred criteria are (potentially) impacted based on certain design decisions.

Assessment should be visible, transparent and traceable so that the architect understands the underlying logic of the human-centred assessment, including source research literature. That is, the assessments made should always be evidence-based.

Similar to AAR-A-UC1, the design team accesses this information directly in their BIM design tool, although the main engine is an independent external tool. The following figure gives an example in the BIM tool ArchiCAD.

Figure 35: Aarhus LL - ArchiCAD tool with illustration of human centered criteria analysis.

The illustration emphasizes two layers of qualitative analysis:

- the “lower level” qualitative experiences that are inferred directly from components and geometry of a building, e.g. “The room colour appearance is cool”, “The room has a lot of perimeter emphasis”, etc.
- the “higher level” overall subjective impression that an occupant is predicted to experience (e.g. moderately pleasant, spacious, clear, public, ...), inferred from the combination of inferred “lower level” experiences

Observe in the illustration that the user can “expand” each item in the lower level to reveal the underlying logic used to infer each qualitative experience, e.g. “The room has lots of perimeter emphasis” is inferred from “Ambient illumination is bright”, etc. What is missing from the illustration is yet a further level of “expansion” of the leaf nodes that refers to research and studies on which the definitions are based.

The above illustrated example employs a real set of studies from the lighting design community, namely Flynn and Cuttle. In a series of studies, Flynn (with various co-authors) determined the combination of “lower level” components that contribute to a set of “higher level” impressions presented in the following table (for example see (Flynn & Spencer , 1977):²¹):

²¹ Flynn, J. E., & Spencer, T. J. (1977). *The effects of light source color on user impression and satisfaction*. *Journal of the Illuminating Engineering Society*, 6(3), 167-179.

	Clarity	Spaciousness	Relaxation	Intimacy	Pleasantness
<i>Ambient Illumination</i>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (bright)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (low in occupancy area)	
<i>Room colour temperature</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (cool)		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (warm)		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (warm)
<i>Perimeter emphasis</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (some)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (uniform)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (nonuniform)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (high brightness)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<i>Work surface illumination</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (bright, uniform)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (bright, uniform, central)			

Table 26: Examples of combinations of “lower level” components that contribute to a set of “higher level” impressions (Flynn & Spencer, 1977).

Cuttle²² (Cuttle, 2008) specified ways of defining “lower level” qualitative experiences in a coarse way that suits the uncertainty at early design stages, for example:

Perceived difference	Illuminance ratio
<i>Noticeable</i>	1.5 : 1
<i>Distinct</i>	3 : 1
<i>Strong</i>	10 : 1
<i>Emphatic</i>	40 : 1

Table 27: Example of defining qualitative experiences for Illuminance ratio (Cuttle, 2008).

Ambient illumination	Eye Illuminance
Lowest level for reasonable colour discrimination	10 lx
Dim appearance	30 lx
Lowest level for ‘acceptably bright’ appearance	100 lx
Bright appearance	300 lx
Distinctly bright appearance	1000 lx

Table 28: Example of defining qualitative experiences for Eye Illuminance (Cuttle, 2008).

Schultz et al.²³ (Schultz, Amor, Lobb, & Guesgen, 2009) aligned and formalized the systems of Flynn and Cuttle, and implemented prototype reasoning engines that applied this logic on BIM models.

²² Cuttle, C. (2008). *Lighting by design*. Routledge.

²³ Schultz, C. P., Amor, R., Lobb, B., & Guesgen, H. W. (2009). *Qualitative design support for engineering and architecture*. *Advanced Engineering Informatics*, 23(1), 68-80.

Schultz, C. P., Amor, R., Guesgen, H. W., & Lobb, B. (2007). *A Decision Support Software Tool for Reasoning about the Subjective Impressions of a Lighting Installation*. In *CIB Twenty-fourth W78 Conference: Bringing ITC Knowledge to Work*.

The interpretations are brought into the BIM model in the form of new objects called “spatial artefacts”, i.e. regions of empty space that are semantically rich in terms of occupant experience. The following figure illustrates three building model extracts with spatial artefacts that capture human-centred information pertaining to visibility (and view out quality), and health and safety.

<p>(a) occupant visibility space (red region), investigating privacy and visual access to outdoors.</p>	<p>(b) washbasin functional space (blue region) intersects door operational space (red region), investigating health and safety.</p>	<p>(c) hazards (steep ramps) on paths (red line) computed from wheelchair movements spaces around the multi-story residential complex.</p>

Table 29: Building model extracts with spatial artefacts that capture human-centered information about visibility, health and safety (Schultz, Amor, Lobb, & Guesgen, 2009).

For Probono, this will focus on the area of air quality and thermal comfort. Predictions on air flow will be accomplished using ITA INNOVA CFD simulator and layered qualitative interpretations of the numerical air flow (simulated) data will be formalized based on psychology, ergonomics and architecture research analogous to the lighting design example above.

We refer to BIM models that are extended with spatial artefacts as ProBIM models.

User / Actor

- Architect:
 - o Domain / Scope: Building design
 - o Benefit: Evidence-based feedback on human-centred aspects at a relatively early design stage.

User Scenario

1. The architect is working on their current design in Revit
2. They click a button “human-centred analysis” (implemented as a custom plug-in)
3. The reasoning engine computes new spatial artefacts pertaining to air quality
4. The spatial artefacts appear in the 3D BIM software as semi-transparent coloured spaces (resulting in a ProBIM model)
5. The architect clicks on one of these spaces and a floating window appears with the logic, as illustrated in the ArchiCAD figure above
6. Another floating panel provides the architect with options, e.g. which spatial artefacts to compute, show/hide, etc.

10.2.4 AAR-A-UC3: Provide feedback on human-centered criteria to engineer (e.g. HVAC, fire safety, statics specialist) when updating the design

Use Case description

Normally the specialist would not be aware of how their changes to the building design directly impact human-centred aspects.

In this use case the specialist intends to make a change to the building, e.g. The Kitchen 2.0, by introducing a load-bearing pillar. The introduction of this building component changes the way the space is experienced (spaciousness, accessibility, etc.). Normally this change would go unaddressed, however now in the Probono decision support tool the specialist gets instant feedback on which experiences that were specifically design for are impacted.

User / Actor

- Architects:
 - o Domain / Scope: Building design
 - o Benefit: Can preserve designed-for human-centred requirements in a BIM model. In conflicts arise later in the building development process, the architect is brought into a dialogue and exchange with engineers after the initial design phase is completed.
- Engineers
 - o Domain / Scope: Detailed design
 - o Benefit: Gets verifying feedback on human-centred requirements.

User Scenario

1. The architect is working on their current design in Revit
2. They compute all spatial artefacts (as per AAR-A-UC2)
3. They select a subset of artefacts and mark them as “required”, with other reference details for traceability (e.g. architects name, etc.)
4. They export their ProBIM model into IFC format
5. The engineer imports the IFC design into Revit
6. The engineer activates the Probono human-centred analysis tool, and set the tool to “Compliance checking” mode; a floating window pops up for providing feedback to the engineer on human-centred aspects
7. They use their own specialized analysis tools to determine some changes to be made to their design
8. They start making changes to the design
9. When a design change impacts one of the spatial artefacts, an alert appears in the floating window; similarly the corresponding spatial artefact appears in the design in red
10. The engineer selects the spatial artefact to gather further information on the conflict, and seeks to consult the architect on solutions

10.2.5 AAR-A-UC4: Provide automated DGNB-specific assessment during design space exploration

Use Case description

The architect is working on a design. They would now like to consider a range of alternative design options, which we refer to as the **design space**. They would like to assess each candidate design against the green certification system DGNB.

The design space grows rapidly, due to high combinatorial nature of independent design actions.

The Probono decision support tool:

- Enables architects to precisely specify their design space
- Samples the design space in a systematic way (via coverage analysis)
- Assesses each sampled candidate design according to an extract of DGNB criteria
- Clusters the resulting sampled designs according to their similarity in terms of DGNB outcomes
- Visualises these clusters, giving the architect new insight into the structure of their (vast) design space
- Enables architects to sample the space under constraints, effectively enabling the architect to “zoom in” to a cluster to discover more designs (in their design space) that lie within their chosen cluster
- In the context of Digital Twins, derives high-performing configurations for BMS/EMS systems to achieve the desired outcomes in terms of DGNB indicators (e.g. automated HVAC systems etc.)

These design space exploration tools are part of the Renovation Domain Model (NovaDM).

Initially, using AAR-A-UC2 and AAR-A-UC3 as a foundation, the DGNB indicators that will be targeted will be air quality (within health and well-being category).

They specify the different possible actions that can be applied to their design as a so-called action tree. In action trees, “+” nodes mean that every child must be included, and “-” nodes mean that exactly one child must be included. For example, the following action tree defines six variations for a particular group of windows: either they have double or triple glazing (2 choices) and have an opening mechanism that is either fixed (can’t open), top-down, or sideways (3 choices).

Figure 36: Example of action tree for architectural element (window) design exploration [Schultz and Kamari 2021]

They can now get an automated assessment of how their design performs for the green certification system DGNB. The following figure illustrates the workflow:

Figure 37: The process of automated evaluation of design scenarios [Schultz and Kamari 2021]

User / Actor

- Architects:
 - o Domain / Scope: Building design
 - o Benefit: Gets feedback on how their design is performing in terms of the DGNB system, particularly in the health and well-being category. Can include broad configuration options for BMS/EMS systems to ensure human-centred qualities are realized during operation, in the case of automated HVAC systems etc. They benefit from automated design space exploration tools that help them to understand the structure of their design space with respect to DGNB criteria.

User Scenario

1. The architect is working on their current design in Revit
2. They export their BIM model as an IFC file
3. They import the IFC file into the Probono Design Space Explorer toolkit
4. They specify their action tree
5. They extend the action tree with alternative BMS/EMS configurations that are also to be explored
6. They click a button and the tool samples, assess, and clusters the design space
7. The architect sees the clusters as an interactive 2D/3D scatterplot
8. They click on a design in each cluster to view its DGNB score profile
9. They choose a cluster and re-sample within that cluster
10. They conduct **sensitivity analysis** to identify those actions that are rather similar, but result in designs with drastically different DGNB scores
11. They get an action profile of their preferred top 3 clusters (i.e., an action profile of a cluster is the set of design actions that tend to result in designs falling within the cluster)
12. They proceed with their design which now scores highly across DGNB indicators

10.3 AAR-B - High Level Need: Generating new knowledge for the design

10.3.1 Main objective

Generating new knowledge on whether (and to what degree) design rationale and intention was accurate in meeting its occupant experience, environmental, and cost criteria. This will be achieved by comparing the predictions in the design phase with reality during the operational phase. This new design knowledge will be fed back into the design process to inform subsequent renovation stages, and for future designs for green building neighbourhoods. Knowledge gained through the AU LL will be captured in the form of a process framework, so that the process can be repeated for other buildings in the AU Campus 2.0 programme

The benefit to the AU LL will be in generating new knowledge on whether (and to what degree) design rationale and intention was accurate in meeting its occupant experience, environmental, and cost criteria. This will be achieved by comparing the predictions in the design phase with reality during the operational phase. This new design knowledge will be fed back into the design process to inform subsequent renovation stages, and for future designs for green building neighbourhoods.

Knowledge gained through the AU LL will be captured in the form of a process framework, so that the process can be repeated for other buildings in the AU Campus 2.0 programme²⁴. Energy savings will be estimated following the International Performance Measurement and

Verification Protocol (IPMVP)²⁴ Option C (Whole Facilities, Table 30). The expected AU LL impacts are summarised in Table 31.

M&V (Measurement and Verification) option proposed based on IPMVP protocol	Comments
C (Whole facilities)	In progress of obtaining baseline data. Baseline data will be available for defining the reference model.

Table 30: Aarhus LL - Considered M&V option

Impact Category	Unit	LL Reference	LL Objective	PROBONO measures/technologies to be applied for impact achievement
I1. Primary energy savings	GWh/year	Flagship building energy demand: 2GWh/year	Flagship Building energy demand: 1.2 GWh/year Savings: 0.8 GWh/year GBN projection: 3 GWh/year	FB23 Danish energy regulations: 12 kg CO2 /m2/yr build bigger than 1000m2 from 2023.
I2. Investments in sustainable energy	million €	-	40 million € invested	
I3. Demonstration sites that go	-	Flagship building specific heating and cooling	Flagship building specific heating and cooling	In general:

²⁴ <https://evo-world.org/>

Impact Category	Unit	LL Reference	LL Objective	PROBONO measures/technologies to be applied for impact achievement
beyond NZEB performance		demand: 1.2 kWh/m2/year	demand: 0.7 kWh/m2/year Savings flagship building: 0.5 GWh/year GBN projection improvement 40%	demonstration of Attributional/Consequential LCA
I4. High energy performance	%	-	Achieve gold grade in the DGNB-DK certification system. Achieve Class 2 in the Danish voluntary energy regulation, FB23	DGNB Gold corresponds to: total performance index of 65% (aggregate across all major categories) and minimum 50% for each category. FB23 corresponds to: no more than 12 kg CO2 /m2/yr build bigger than 1000m2 from 2023.
I6. Reduction of the embodied energy in buildings	GJ or %	-	Achieve gold grade in the DGNB-DK certification system. Achieve Class 2 in the Danish voluntary energy regulation, FB23	As above.

Table 31: Aarhus LL - impacts

Once operational, the DT for The Kitchen 2.0 and BSS will be used to continually assess occupant experience and environmental impact in real time and predict the impact of taking various operational and BMS-based decisions, e.g., reconfiguring the automated HVAC and lighting system parameters.

10.3.2 AAR-B-UC1: Check design-stage predictions when the building is in operation

Use Case description

The designed building is now constructed and moves into the operational phase. A Digital Twin is used to check and assess LCA metrics, human-centred criteria, and DGNB indicator scores. The actual measurements are compared with what was predicted during the design stage.

Significant discrepancies between as-designed and actual assessments are bundled together to auto-generate "design knowledge item" delivered to key stakeholders (design team, occupants, building managers, facility managers).

This is intended to trigger dialogue on how to reconfigure the building (e.g. BMS/EMS etc.) to flexibly and dynamically improve occupant experience; this aspect does not necessarily happen automatically, improvements can also be achieved by reconfiguring settings, changing functional zones in the building, etc.

User / Actor

- Architects:
 - o Domain / Scope: Building design
 - o Benefit: New design knowledge, specifically on whether the human-centred principles that governed decision making during the design stage indeed play out as intended in reality. Input and insights in how the building can be configured during operation to achieve the intended human-centred criteria.
- Facility managers / Building owners:
 - o Domain / Scope: Operation phase
 - o Benefit: Further input in how the BMS/EMS can be configured to support human-centred criteria.

User Scenario

1. The architect (at the end of the design stage) delivers a ProBIM model that explicitly includes how human-centred requirements are met, in a formal way
2. After the building is constructed, specific air quality sensors are installed to collect data that will be used by the digital twin to assess human-centred criteria and DGNB indicators
3. While the building is in operation, data is collected and fed to the digital twin

4. The results are continuously compared to the scores that were predicted at end of the design stage – significant discrepancies are recorded and compiled into reports intended for architects, the design team, and other stakeholders
5. To the extent that the building is equipped with configurable automated systems (BMS/EMS), the DT has a range of alternative settings that it can assess and deploy (with close coordination with facility managers), ensuring that the DT enables adaptability and flexibility of the actual building based on incoming data

10.4 Data - Inventory and requirements

The Kitchen 1.0 is currently in operation. Energy usage and other metrics are available to inform the simulations of expected occupant behaviour and other operational patterns for The Kitchen 2.0.

The Kitchen 2.0 and BSS are currently in the design (deep renovation) phase. BIM models of the current designs are now available for use by Probono.

Given the initial focus on indoor air quality and thermal comfort, we will need to collect real-time data and install (virtual and real) sensors that can measure airflow, temperature, CO₂, and HVAC usage. Predictions made via the simulations will be checked against the actual sensor data readings once the buildings become operational. The remaining social indicators will be assessed in a static way based on a combination of the (digital) BIM model and facts gathered manually from the (physical) environment.²⁵

Linked use cases	Dataset name	Dataset content description	Data provider	Static or dynamic	Dataset availability
AAR-A AAR-B	3D model of buildings (BIM models)	both building projects (the Kitchen 2.0 and BSS, consisting of 3-4 buildings)	Aarhus university	static	yes
AAR-A AAR-B	LCA metrics and human-centred criteria	DGNB indicator scores, Air quality	Computed by WP5 DT	dynamic	Not yet

²⁵ For example, one aspect of both visual comfort and indoor quality is visual access to the exterior, and whether (indoor and outdoor) flora and greenery are visible in certain important locations. This can be determined in a static way by checking the geometry of the BIM model, and by physically visiting the building and confirming or denying whether such visual access is available. Photos and videos are collected as evidence for such arguments.

Linked use cases	Dataset name	Dataset content description	Data provider	Static or dynamic	Dataset availability
AAR-A AAR-B	Human-centred criteria	Thermal comfort	ITA simulation	dynamic	No yet
AAR-A AAR-B	Manually collected data	Facts gathered manually from the (physical) environment	Aarhus university	static	No yet
AAR-A	Dynamic collected data	Data from sensors and meters in the buildings (electricity, heating, room temperature and water consumption)	Aarhus university	dynamic	No yet

Table 32: Aarhus LL - Data inventory

10.5 Decision-making tools – Inventory and requirements

Tool name	Tool/model description	Tool provider	Input	Output
(Autodesk) Revit	Revit BIM-based design tool, the ongoing projects are designed in Revit, Architectural file (spacial) and Engineer file (structural). BIM models is provided for "Kitchen 2" 3500m2 (renovation) and BIM model for "BSS" project sum of 37000m2 building 1850, 1870(renovation) building 1790, 1791 (newbuild)	Aarhus university	BIM models, IFC models	BIM models, IFC, 2d drawings to FM system Dalux
3D model and ventilation simulation	BIM models will evolve to be exploited in ITAINNOVA's ventilation simulation software. integrated in the WP5 DT	ITA	BIM	thermal comfort
Model Identity Card (MIC)	The MIC is defined as the set of core information which appears to be useful to characterize most simulations models in most contexts integrated in the WP5 DT	IRT SystemX	Simulation models, models parameters	interoperable models

Tool name	Tool/model description	Tool provider	Input	Output
Functional Mockup Interface (FMI 2.0)	A co-simulation standard that will be used in case different simulation tools need to be executed on the BIM model in a unified way (e.g. air quality simulation combined with occupant behaviour simulator) integrated in the WP5 DT	FMI standard	Simulation models, models parameters	interoperable models

Table 33: Aarhus LL - Decision-making tool Inventory

10.6 Visualization tools – Inventory and requirements

Linked use cases	Tool name	Tool description	Tool provider
AAR	Autodesk Revit	Standard architecture design software includes BIM models of Aarhus living lab buildings	Aarhus University
AAR	QGIS27	Geographic information systems displaying GNB components	Free and open-source cross-platform developed by QGIS Development Team / Aarhus
AAR	Renovation Domain Model (NovaDM)	Help stakeholders explore the design space of renovation options	Aarhus University
AAR	ArchiCAD	Standard architecture design software includes BIM models of Aarhus living lab buildings	Aarhus University

Table 34: Aarhus LL - Visualization tools inventory

10.7 DT & external systems – Interoperability requirements

Interoperability Requirements	Concerned tool	Description
AAR-INTER-REQ-1: Interfaced with the WP5 DT	Dalux facility management system	Real-time sensor data management system, e.g. CO2 readings, electricity metering, etc.

Table 35: Aarhus LL - Interoperability requirements

11 PRG - Prague Living Lab

11.1 Living Lab Context

11.1.1 Location

Dejvice is an urban district and a cadastral territory of the Prague 6 district, located in the north-western part of the city. Major development happened mainly in the first quarter of the 20th century. It is home to several facilities of the Czech Technical University of Prague as well as the University of Chemistry and Technology.

The Prague Living Lab (hereafter referred to as “**Prague LL**”) encompasses a set of 4 buildings and their immediate areas are located on the yellow rectangle in the Figure 38: Prague LL - Top View of Dejvice, north-west of Prague below. The main interest of the Probono Living Lab is directed at the “Building B” which is delimited by the red rectangle. It has been built in the 1970s and should benefit from a ‘deep renovation’. Some green areas are located on the different sides of the building.

Figure 38: Prague LL - Top View of Dejvice, north-west of Prague

Figure 39: Prague LL - Top View of Building B (red) and the GBN (yellow) on the Czech Technical

11.1.2 Physical Twin Details

The Physical Twin (“PT”) represents a set of 4 buildings built in the 1970s which are interconnected by either staircases or bridges. The buildings (as shown on the Figure 9 below) differ greatly from each other, some details are provided hereafter:

- **Building A** is located in the north-east of the Green Building Neighbourhood (“GBN”). No modifications of this building are planned within the Probono project. Building A is connected to the Building C through its two bottom floors.
- **Building B** is located in the south of the GBN. This building is the main target of Probono program for the Prague LL as it will be fully retrofitted. Building B is connected to the Building C by its bottom two staircases and to the Building D by a bridge.
- **Building C** is located in the centre of the GBN. It is the main entrance of the GBN complex and is connected to the other buildings by common stairs (Building A and B) or by a bridge (Building D).
- **Building D** is located in the northwest of the GBN. This building is wider than the other, but only two stairs high. It is separated from the three other buildings by a small road but is connected to Building B and Building C by two different bridges.

All these buildings already exist and are in use. They house the Faculty of Civil Engineering which is a part of the Czech Technical University. With more than 17 thousand students (2020) the university ranks among the biggest ones in the Czech Republic.

Figure 40: Prague LL - Some picture of the GBN with the different building (source: Google street View)

Figure 41: Prague LL - Building B composition (Google Map 3D)

In the picture above: encircled part in pink belongs to building B, encircled area in purple too but it has already been retrofitted. The building in blue is not part of the Building B.

Figure 42: Prague LL - Building B composition (continued)

The building part circled in pink on this picture is part of building B. The green circle indicates the Building C. The electricity network of buildings B and C are interconnected through a single cable.

11.1.3 Physical Twin post-Probono expected status

Building B is going to be heavily retrofitted, it will impact the building C because of the strong interconnection between the two buildings due to their two common floors. The other buildings (A and D) will not be affected by the renovation operation, but they should be considered for the DT as part of the LL.

Building B will be equipped with an innovative south-eastern facade. This can include features such as energy production and thermic insulation regulation. The other facades will use high-level insulation materials for thermic energy saving. The roof will have energy production devices such as solar panels.

Building B will be equipped with ventilation systems with heat recovery feature (Mechanical Ventilation with Heat Recovery).

11.1.4 Digital Twin High Level Needs requested

This section presents the high-level needs of the DT linked to this LL.

High Level Need	Physical domain	Functional domain
PRG-A: Monitor and exploit energy systems	Whole GBN	Energy Management
PRG-B: Evaluate possible new design for roof and southern facade	Building B and Green Area	Building Design

Table 36: Prague LL - DT High Level Need list

11.2 PRG-A - High Level Need: Monitor and manage energy systems

11.2.1 Main objective

The DT is about the energy monitoring. This includes monitoring of electricity and internal air quality (directly with heat and indirectly for humidity)-

The Energy Management high-level need is an exploitation use case. The DT will provide data to different users (students, technical team or external public). The managed energy sources include electricity and heat flow (indoor heat, material heat ...). It will also include different interactions between electricity production, electricity consumption, heat energy production and heat loss.

By merging all energy data (electricity, heat) on one single tool, the Digital Twin will provide to user with clear view of interactions between the different energy systems.

In this high-level need, a technical / building exploitation team uses the DT to optimize energy management. By simulating all the energy flows (electricity and heat flow) and their comparison with real measures, this DT provides data needed to optimize the building exploitation.

For this High-Level need, the involved use cases are the following ones:

- **PRG-A-UC1:** Monitor electricity consumption and flow
- **PRG-A-UC2:** Monitor electricity production units
- **PRG-A-UC3:** Monitor air flow and internal climate
- **PRG-A-UC4:** Detect performance issue and alert technical team

11.2.2 PRG-A-UC1: Monitor electricity consumption and flow

The team in charge of the GBN exploitation will access the DT to get a global view of electrical consumption and electrical flow across the GBN. By flow, we mean electrical charge across each electrical cable. This UC applies for the whole building B. The other buildings of the GBN should be presented in a simpler way (Building C with interconnexion to Building B and building A and D to be defined). This use case with the PRG-A-UC2 represents a single feature consisting in monitoring electrical production units.

11.2.3 PRG-A-UC2: Monitor electricity production units

The team in charge of the GBN exploitation will access the DT presenting the global electrical map of the GBN with special focus on Building B. It will show the electrical flow from production of electricity, through its transfer to the various electrical devices and subsequent consumption levels. By consulting the DT, the team in charge of the GBN exploitation will have a direct and global view on the electricity network status.

The electrical power flow of each electrical device will be monitored in the DT, including each of the following devices:

- Roof solar panel / electricity production units
- South facade electrical production unit
- Air conditioning devices
- Air heating devices
- Ventilation devices
- Lighting
- Elevators.

The perimeter to consider is the following:

- Full electricity flows inside the buildings B as well as the electricity flow between and electrical exchanges across between those buildings
- Electricity exchange with the other GBN Buildings (Buildings A and Building D)
- Electricity production from agrovoltaics
- Electricity consumption of e-bike and e-car charging stations

User / Actor

The technical staff in charge of GBN exploitation.

Professors and students will also use the DT to some extent according to the content they will be granted.

11.2.4 PRG-A-UC3: Monitor air flow and internal climate

The actor will use the DT to view the whole building B internal spaces with dynamic internal climate status. The DT should include HVAC and ventilation systems:

- HVAC maintaining target temperature (central heating + air conditioning)
- Ventilation regulating humidity and air quality

Here, the DT should represent air flow and the data regarding the internal climate evolution, these data:

- Temperature
- Humidity
- CO2
- VOC

The actor will use the DT to visualize also the air flow exchange between the building B and the other GBN Buildings (Building A, building C and Building D).

User / Actor

Actors will be the technical staff in charge of GBN exploitation. Professors and students will also use the DT to some extent according to the content they will be granted.

11.2.5 PRG-A-UC4: Detect performance issue and alert technical team

The user will use the DT to be informed about equipment or areas which have unexpected behaviours such as underperformance or malfunction. For this, the DT detects situation where some simulation results and measured data from the physical twin sensors differ. Thus, the DT can alert the team in charge of the GBN exploitation, indicating area or equipment concerned by the anomalies.

User / Actor

The technical staff in charge of GBN exploitation.

Professors and students will also use the DT to some extent according to the content they will be granted.

11.3 PRG-B - High Level Need: Design and Material choice for Building B retrofit

11.3.1 Main objective

The main objective is to support the selection of best material and design for the Building B retrofit. The principle consists in testing different roof top and southern façade designs and study their impact on the whole GBN during its lifetime. The main simulated element will be the electrical network with all Building B electrical equipment and the internal air climate.

The DT will represent the GBN with a full detailed Building B and simplified model of buildings C, D and A. All hypotheses will use same Northern, eastern and western façade design for the Building B. The physical models will vary only on the roof top and the southern façade.

In particular, the southern facade can vary on solar panel implantation that can be more or less tilted. By being tilted, it will use more materials during retrofit. But it will benefit more electrical production, and this will have thermal effect on Southern windows

This design choice will affect several elements for CO2 and cost evaluation:

- The amount of material needed by the design
- The Solar panel efficiency
- The insulation regulation that it provides to the windows / glass surfaces on the façades.

11.3.2 PRG-B-UC1: Evaluate different roof and south facade design

The goal is to simulate the impact of roof top design and southern façade design on the whole GBN during the GBN life and including retrofit workshop.

We want to simulate electricity systems network and internal air climate evolution during the whole Building usage lifetime.

The DT parameters will be the following:

- The static part GBN model
- The forecasting weather during all the building usage lifetime, GBN room usages...
- The specific Roof Top and Southern Façade to test

The Southern Façade is composed of Windows, Solar panels and structure to support them. Following the different configuration, the solar panel will make an angle with the Façade. This has several implications:

- The solar panel efficiency will vary following the angle, time and season
- Windows will receive some insulation, making some thermal energy inside the Building B
- On some configuration, this angle will shadow parts of the windows following time and season
- The material used for the Southern Façade will contain embodied energy and carbon costs that has to be considered for the different calculations

The DT provides for each hypothesis simulation the following results regarding the GBN:

- energy performance,
- electricity global production,
- electricity consumption,
- forecasting of a calendar indicating:
 - o period with electrical surplus (from building B and agrovoltatics) to export to the other parts of the GBN,
 - o period with electrical needs of the Building B from the other parts of the GBN,
 - o internal climate evolution including temperature, humidity, CO2.
- CO2 emissions during the whole building lifetime,
 - o Material production
 - o Retrofit workshop
 - o Building day to day life (electricity from electrical network company and gas consumption)

With all these data, the project team can choose the design they want to apply for the Building B retrofit on the southern facade and the rooftop.

User Scenario

The user scenario is the following one:

1. The design team sets several design and material choice hypotheses for the Building B.

2. For each hypothesis, DT simulates the whole lifecycle of the building consisting in the information described in the list above

11.4 Data - Inventory and requirements

Linked use cases	Dataset name	Dataset content description	Data provider	Static or dynamic	Dataset availability
PRG-A	Measured Electricity	Current electricity consumption The current electricity meter serves for building A, B, C and D. The building B is connected to electricity supply system. The energy consumption is shared with other faculty buildings and is not sub-metered.	Prague LL	dynamic	now and future
PRG-A	Measured Heat	Current heat consumption The current heat meter serves for building A, B, C and D. The building B is connected to central heat supply system. The energy consumption is shared with other faculty buildings and is not sub-metered.	Prague LL	dynamic	now and maybe in future if it would not be fully replaced with heat pumps
PRG-B	Simulation result	Electricity consumption for lighting of building B	WP5 DT	Static	near future
PRG-B	Simulation result	Electricity consumption for heating of building B	WP5 DT	Static	near future
PRG-B	Simulation result	Electricity consumption for hot water of building B	WP5 DT	Static	near future
PRG-B	Simulation result	Electricity consumption for cooling of building B	WP5 DT	Static	near future
PRG-B	Simulation result	Electricity consumption for ventilation of building B	WP5 DT	Static	near future
PRG-B	Simulation result	PVs electricity production installed on or near by building B	WP5 DT	Static	near future
PRG-B	Simulation result	Total electricity consumption of building B including appliances	WP5 DT	Static	near future
PRG-B	Simulation result	Total energy consumption minus PVs production of building B	WP5 DT	Static	near future
PRG-B	Simulation result	Non-renewable energy consumption of building B	WP5 DT	Static	near future
PRG-B	Simulation result	CO2 emissions of building B	WP5 DT	Static	near future
PRG-B	Simulation result	Cooling demand and thermal comfort for every room in the building B	WP5 DT	Static	near future
PRG	Measured Weather data	weather station installed on-site	Prague LL	dynamic	future
PRG-A	Measured internal climate data	Each room of the building B is associated to a set of climate data: Temperature, Humidity, CO2, VOC.	Prague LL	dynamic for every room	future
PRG	Measured energy consumption	Measured energy consumption for heating after revitalization of the building B	Prague LL	dynamic	future
PRG	Calculated cost	Cost calculation of heating based on measured energy consumption in building B	Prague LL	dynamic	future
PRG	Measured energy consumption	Measured energy consumption of technology systems scalable from one appliance to all measured in building B	Prague LL	dynamic	future
PRG	Calculated cost	Cost calculation of energy linked to technology systems based on measured energy consumption in building B	Prague LL	dynamic	Not defined yet

Linked use cases	Dataset name	Dataset content description	Data provider	Static or dynamic	Dataset availability
PRG	Measured energy consumption	Measured energy consumption for lighting after revitalization of the building B	Prague LL	dynamic	future
PRG	Calculated cost	Cost calculation of lighting based on measured energy consumption in building B	Prague LL	dynamic	Not defined yet
PRG	Measured energy consumption	Measured energy consumption for cooling after revitalization of the building B	Prague LL	dynamic	future
PRG	Calculated cost	Cost calculation of cooling based on measured energy consumption in building B	Prague LL	dynamic	Not defined yet
PRG	Measured energy consumption	Measured energy production for PVs after revitalization of the building B	Prague LL	dynamic	future
PRG	Calculated income	Income calculation based on measured energy production in building B	Prague LL	dynamic	future
PRG	Occupancy information	number of people in the building A, B, C and D	Prague LL	dynamic	future
PRG	Open data	https://opendata.praha.eu/	Prague city	Static	yes

Table 37: Prague LL - Data inventory

11.5 Decision-making tools – Inventory and requirements

Req ID	Requirement description	Tool/model description	Tool provider	Input data	Output data
PRG-REQ-DSS-1	The DT shall produce some simulations about energy of building B. See details in the next columns.	AI forecast model	WP5 DT (to be confirmed)	Historical data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Electricity consumptions for lighting, heating, hot water, cooling, ventilation of building B. - PVs electricity production installed on or near by building B - total electricity consumption of building B including appliances - Total energy consumption minus PVs production of building B - non-renewable energy consumption of building B - CO2 emissions of building B - Cooling demand and thermal comfort for every room in the building B

Table 38: Prague LL - Decision-making tool requirements

11.6 Visualization tools – Inventory and requirements

Requirement id	Requirement Description
PRG-RQ-VIZ-1	<p>Single energy dashboard requirement</p> <p>The DT shall provide in a single dashboard all energy data (electricity, heat) so that user will have a clear view of interactions between the different energy systems.</p>
<p>DT integration with Augmented Reality tool requirements - Considering the integration between the Digital Twin and the Augmented Reality tool the following requirements are identified:</p>	
PRG-RQ-VIZ-DT1	<p>Efficient Communication: Digital twin shall provide a robust communication mechanism for seamless data transfer between the AR tool and the DT</p>
PRG-RQ-VIZ-DT2	<p>Continuous data flow: The data flow needs to be bidirectional between the AR component and the DT</p>
PRG-RQ-VIZ-DT3	<p>Data Handling: The digital twin should make data available to the AR considering the special characteristics each data type, e.g., if a 3D model should be sent to the AR tool, then the DT must provide specific metadata (location, orientation, etc.)</p>
PRG-RQ-VIZ-DT4	<p>BIM Visualization: The digital twin should be capable to transfer a BIM model along with the metadata (if need and if applicable) based on a specific location-dependent request from the AR tool</p>
PRG-RQ-VIZ-DT5	<p>Data Visualization: If there is a specific need for data visualization on top of a BIM model, the DT should be capable of transferring the data in an understandable form (e.g., ascii if it is text, etc.)</p>
PRG-RQ-VIZ-AR1	<p>Continuous, efficient, and accurate Scene Tracking & Understanding: To ensure proper and accurate visualization and contextualization of the DT data, the AR tool needs to identify specific elements and track efficiently the scene. The AR tool should provide proper navigation methods and should fall into one of the following methods: marker-based AR, marker-less AR, location-based AR, or projection-based AR.</p>
PRG-RQ-VIZ-AR2	<p>Adherence to physical constraints: The visualization and the alignment of the augmented objects need to respect and follow physical constraints & principles.</p>
PRG-RQ-VIZ-AR3	<p>Data handle: The AR tool should be able to handle the data sent from the Digital Twin.</p>
PRG-RQ-VIZ-AR4	<p>Augmented data should be visualized properly on the physical world</p>

Table 39: Prague LL - Visualisation requirements

11.7 DT & external systems - Interoperability requirements

Id	Title	Requirement description
PRG-RQ-INTX-1	Monitoring infrastructure	The DT shall be interfaced with the monitoring system providing data about user comfort and energy flows.
PRG RQ-INTX-2	Augmented Reality system	The DT shall be interfaced with the augmented reality system of Prague LL. See additional requirements in the ' Visualization tools – Inventory and requirements' section.

Table 40: Prague LL - Interconnexion requirements

12 WP3 digital solutions inventory and requirements

This chapter lists the simulation/DTs models identified by WP3, and which are candidate for implementation in GBN-DP.

WP3 Models inventory id	Model title	Description	Inputs	Outputs	DT Type
Model-WP3-1	High Evaporative Green Roofs (HEGR)	Network (grid) water management for irrigation - smart irrigation. Substrate moisture monitoring & weather forecast analysis before starting daily irrigation.	Moisture sensors. Network water connected actuator. Local weather forecast.	Irrigation Schedule/Actuator on/off. Water Consumption (Grid water savings for irrigation).	Optimization
Model-WP3-2	Cool Roofs Combined with Bi-facial PV	Cool Roof+ Bi-facial PV analysis of performance. Preventive maintenance / compare calculated production to real-production and identify faulty operation of the system.	Temperature sensor. Solar Irradiance W/m2. Solar Reflectance Index (SRI)/ (SR). Camera Visual.	PV energy generated. PV energy calculated. Summer comfort improvement (Cool Surface & shadow).	Simulation/PV Power Calculation
Model-WP3-3	Modular construction	LCA-based Optimization for GBN Environmental Performance Evaluation of Prefabricated Elements. Automatically or semi-automatically apply relevant LCA dataset to materials, construction parts and energy consumption in an already established BIM model. The environmental impact of the energy supply or production should be dynamically and continuously updated.	LCA Data (EPD or generic) on building elements. BIM/ Building Geometry. Energy Consumption/Production.	LCA Metrics Analysis. Enriched BIM Model.	LCA Metrics Calculation

Model-WP3-4	Robots in Construction	DT Model for 3D Visualization of the Construction Site from Data originated from Robots. Overview of materials or construction parts (prefabricated or not) in an existing building/GBN and coupling with visual data with material specific information.	Imagery scans based on reality capture mesh of the existing building/GBN.	BIM for visualization of the building materials in their accurate location and allowing for annotation as well as different analysis across the materials at hand.	Visualization & Analysis
Model-WP3-5	Smart Engineering Technologies and Materials applied to Pavements and Concrete Structures	DT Model for Tracking, Monitoring and Assessment of the Material use, and Embodied Emissions of the Whole Construction Process. Track material workflow from demolition, treatment, and reuse. Track environmental impacts related to the material upcycling. Database for utilization of secondary raw materials coming from demolition. Monitor environmental impacts of demolition activities.	Visual for the entire area of MNN with indication of buildings to be demolished. Their inventory information. Visual graphs for air pollution measurements.	Embodied Emissions of the Whole Construction Process	Monitoring & Analysis
Model-WP3-6	Mitigating Infection Risks by Controlling Air Quality	DT Model for Monitoring and Optimizing IEQ. Avoid spread of COVID-19 in closed spaces.	Air temperature. Relative humidity. CO2 concentration. Illumination. HVAC system data. HVAC system maintenance data.	IEQ Analytics (Thermal and visual comfort). HVAC Management.	Analysis and Control
Model-WP3-7	Controlling Disease Progression by Controlling People Flow	DT Model for Mobility Flows Representation and Simulation	Number of people entering the building. % of rejected people. Number of people attended per day. Number of people attended / resource x hour. Average waiting time.	Data analytics Real-time people flow simulation Assisted decision making	Visualization & Simulation
Model-WP3-8	Mitigating Infection Risks by Optimization of Sharing Information	DT Model for Optimization of Information Sharing	Number of confirmed disease cases. Measurement of users' body temperature. Social-distancing data. Information update of relevant websites and databases (number of disease cases, regulations, alerts etc.). Occupancy levels per sections & time spent. Cleanliness of individual spaces. Room temperatures, CO2 & humidity levels.	Information of specific spaces in relation to on-going, completed or planned sanitary procedures. Sensor-monitored occupancy levels and wayfinding signage to disperse the users into less occupied spaces. Contact tracing.	Monitoring, Analysis and Optimization

Table 41: WP3 model inventory

13 WP4 data collection

In WP4 - Energy monitoring and clean energy generation, storage and distribution, energy systems are optimized (T4.1), their operation monitored and optimized (T4.2) and roof utilisation options evaluated (T4.4), and the use of PV façades (T4.3), batteries (T4.5) and electric vehicles with intelligent charging management (T4.6) are designed and monitored in use. The data calculated for the design of the energy systems and installations can be made available to the Digital Twin and used as target values to monitor the achieved goals. Monitoring the operation of the technologies and plants continuously provides actual data that can be used to check performance. The most important information on data provision by task is listed below.

T4.1 Climate neutral energy system planning and design methodology	
What data will be provided	Optimal configurations of the energy system (generation, conversion and storage capacities, annual energy yields, forecast energy consumption data by sector, etc.), renewable energy potentials
Temporal resolution of the data	For each target energy system with the associated boundary conditions, the energy production and consumption data are provided sector-specifically for one year in hourly resolution for optimal operation
Time period to which the data refer	The calculation results refer to the expected operating data in the target year (after completion of the GBN, which is in full operation, e.g. in 2030).
Data availability	One-time calculation of projected generation.
Possible use in the digital twin	The data can be used as target values in the Digital Twin to validate the measured values.
T4.2 GBN demand and response platform	
What data will be provided	<p><u>Historic consumption profiles measured:</u> electricity, heating</p> <p><u>Profiles simulated:</u> electricity, heating and sanitary hot water demand, as well as heating (HeatPump, boilers, cogen, fuel cells,...) and electricity (PV, Battery, Grid, Storage,...) response to demand simulated</p> <p><u>Monitored data:</u> Electricity demand (LL Brussels: General Low Voltage, Lift, Lighting consumptions of classrooms) Heating demand (natural gas demand)</p>
Temporal resolution of the data	<p><u>Historic consumption profiles measured:</u> hourly on a normal week, daily on a normal year</p> <p><u>Demand profiles simulated:</u> hourly</p> <p><u>Monitored data:</u> 15 minutes</p>

Time period to which the data refer	<u>Historic consumption profiles measured:</u> Brussels LL: 2022, others: TBD <u>Demand profiles simulated:</u> Brussels LL: 2022, others: TBD <u>Monitored data:</u> LL Brussels: from Sept. 2023, other LLs: TBD
Data availability	<u>Historic consumption profiles measured:</u> available at once <u>Demand profiles simulated:</u> available at once <u>Monitored data:</u> collected continuously
Possible use in the digital twin	<u>Historic consumption profiles measured / Demand profiles simulated:</u> Approximate behaviour of the building without monitoring. Could be compared with monitored data later. <u>Monitored data:</u> show direct consumptions of the building
T4.3 Building Integrated Photovoltaics	
What data will be provided	Potential analysis for the installation of photovoltaic façades (installed capacity, solar power yield)
Temporal resolution of the data	hourly data of the generation profile over one year
Time period to which the data refer	Target year of the GBN
Data availability	One-time calculation of projected generation
Possible use in the digital twin	Presentation of possible generation variants
T4.4 PROBONO GB Positive Energy Package	
What data will be provided	Generation potential for different types of local solar energy use (system capacity and energy yields). Potential rainwater harvesting and other roof environment data.
Temporal resolution of the data	The solar power generation is provided for one year (reference year) in hourly resolution.
Time period to which the data refer	Possible future generation of solar electricity.
Data availability	One-time calculation of projected generation.
Possible use in the digital twin	The calculated solar power generation data can be provided for different types of systems and installations, and the graphics of the systems could be displayed for different renovation options.
T4.5 GBN Energy Storage	
What data will be provided	Technology data of energy storage systems (redox flow batteries (RFB) and second life batteries). Monitoring of operational data possible.
Temporal resolution of the data	Optimised operating behaviour in hourly resolution based on hourly energy generation and consumption profiles.

Time period to which the data refer	Simulations refer to the expected future operating behaviour, monitoring data to the measurement period.
Data availability	One-time simulation of the expected operating behaviour, continuous measurement as part of monitoring.
Possible use in the digital twin	Simulation results can be used as target data for comparison with the monitoring data.
T4.6 Integrated Infrastructure Mobility Energy	
What data will be provided	Simulation calculations for the operation of electric vehicles and charging processes, consideration of controlled charging. Resulting load profiles. Monitoring of operational data possible.
Temporal resolution of the data	Hourly data, possibly higher frequency.
Time period to which the data refer	Simulations refer to the expected future operating behaviour, monitoring data to the measurement period.
Data availability	One-time simulation of the expected operating behaviour, continuous measurement as part of monitoring.
Possible use in the digital twin	Simulation results can be used as target data for comparison with the monitoring data.

Table 42: WP4 data collection

14 WP6 KPIs production requirements

This section includes high-level needs defined by WP6 (Monitoring and Evaluation of the project's Living Labs) for WP5 in order to implement in the GBN digital platform the KPIs processing system.

High-level requirement id	High-level requirement	Description
HL-WP6-1	Data gathering and storage	Gathering and storage of all the data linked to the variables needed as inputs to calculate the assessment KPIs. Errors in the data collection process, such as an IoT device which stops sending data, should be recorded and user should receive an alarm.

		To be decided further: periodicity of the data collection, the needed data granularity.
HL-WP6-2	Data pre-processing	<p>Pre-processing (cleaning, filling gaps, normalization...) of the data gathered within each iteration of the previous high-level need. It should be done periodically or on-the-fly when the data are collected.</p> <p>To be decided further: pre-processing algorithms to be applied and periodicity of the data pre-processing tasks.</p>
HL-WP6-3	Data visualization / access	<p>Once stored, it should be necessary to access the monitoring data that has been gathered and stored to calculate the KPIs.</p> <p>Access to reporting and data access should be provided both a GUI for users and through an API for IT systems.</p> <p>Filtering options should be given to the user and to the IT system.</p>
HL-WP6-4	KPIs calculation	<p>Once all the variables needed to calculate the KPIs are available within a specific period, the different KPIs must be calculated.</p> <p>The periodicity of KPIs calculation could be daily, monthly, or even yearly and will depend on the calculated KPI.</p> <p>An “on-demand” KPI calculation should be developed to allow the user to calculate a KPI for a given time.</p> <p>This “on demand” KPI calculation should be available from a GUI and from an API for users and IT systems which need results of KPI calculations.</p> <p>To be decided further: list of KPIs to be calculated with their formula, the variables needed to calculate each KPI (variable for each demo-site). Periodicity of KPI calculation.</p>

HL-WP6-5	KPIs visualization and access	<p>This high-level need refers to the generation of reports about KPIs and the possibility of getting KPIs values for a given period.</p> <p>Reports and KPI should be accessible from a GUI for users and through an API for external IT systems.</p> <p>Filtering options such as by date, by KPI... should be available to the user and to the IT system.</p> <p>To be decided further: Content of the reports.</p>
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Table 43: High-level requirements linked to WP6 KPI calculation

15 Data security requirements

Data security refers to the protection of the data used by GBN-DP and GBN-DTs. This includes ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of the data and systems, as well as protecting them from unauthorized access and modification. The data and systems security measures should be designed to meet the specific security requirements of the digital twin and take into consideration the types of data being used, the potential risks associated with that data, and the importance of the data to the overall functioning of the digital twin. This includes the protection of sensitive data, such as personal information and intellectual property, as well as the secure integration and exchange of information between digital twins and other systems.

These objectives are broken down into the following high-level requirements which should be considered during the design of Probono systems:

High-level requirement id	Title	Description
HL-DS-1	Data classification	Data classification is the process of categorizing and labelling data based on its level of sensitivity, value, and criticality. This allows organizations to determine the appropriate level of protection required for each type of data and ensure that the

		data is handled in a consistent and secure manner.
HL-DS-2	Access Control	Access to the data collected should be restricted to authorized personnel only. This requires the implementation of robust access control mechanisms, such as user authentication and authorization, to ensure that only authorized users can access the data.
HL-DS-3	Encryption	Sensitive data stored in the digital twin should be encrypted to protect it against unauthorized access and theft. Encryption should be applied at rest, in transit, and in use to ensure end-to-end protection of the data.
HL-DS-4	Data Backup and Disaster Recovery	Regular backups of the data stored in the digital twin should be taken to ensure that it can be recovered in the event of a disaster, such as a data breach or hardware failure. The backup should be stored in a secure location that is accessible only to authorized personnel.
HL-DS-5	Physical Security	The servers and storage devices used for the digital twin should be protected against physical threats, such as theft or damage, by securing them in a secure location with restricted access.
HL-DS-6	Network Security	The network used should be secured against cyber threats, such as hacking, by implementing firewalls, intrusion detection and prevention systems, and network segmentation.
HL-DS-7	Data Privacy	The digital twin implementation should comply with data privacy regulations, such as GDPR, to ensure the privacy of building occupants and

		other stakeholders. This requires the implementation of robust privacy controls, such as data anonymization and pseudonymization, to protect the identity of the data subjects.
HL-DS-8	Risk Management	Continuously assessing and mitigating potential threats to information and systems.

Table 44: High-level data security requirements

16 Conclusions

D5.1 report provides an initial set of candidate requirements related to the need of digital twins from Probono living labs. It outlines seven digital twins including 21 high level needs and 50 use cases. These high-level needs cover a range of topics including Energy Management, Building Design, Environment Management, Material Management, Human Behaviour, and Mobility as it is shown in Figure 43: Mapping between high level needs and topics below. In addition to the use cases, lists of data sets, decision tools, and visualization tools have been compiled across the LLs. These elements can be needed to build the DTs. Moreover, external systems that might be required to use or to interface with the DTs have been identified, establishing additional requirements for the DTs. The requirements provided by LLs have been consolidated with needs from WP3, WP6 and some data security requirements. The data collection that WP4 could provide to be used by DTs has been described. This report provides inputs to T5.2, T5.3, T5.4 for the design and the development of the DTs and more generally the GBN-DP.

Building up on this initial work, a second version of this document named D5.2 will be produced by T5.1. It will contain, amongst other things, refined requirements and specifications for the use cases that will be selected for actual development, the description of generic functional architecture of GBN-DT, discussions on solution scalability, and deployment options.

Figure 43: Mapping between high level needs and topics

References

- Adu-Kankam, K. O., & Camarinha-Matos, L. M. (2022). A Framework for the Integration of IoT Components into the Household Digital Twins for Energy Communities. In L. M. Camarinha-Matos, L. Ribeiro, & L. Strous (Eds.). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Adu-Kankam, K. O., & Camarinha-Matos, L. M. (2022). Modelling Mutual Influence Towards Sustainable Energy Consumption. In L. M. Camarinha-Matos (Ed.). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Agouzoul, A., Tabaa, M., Chegari, B., Simeu, E., Dandache, A., & Alami, K. (2021). Towards a Digital Twin model for Building Energy Management: Case of Morocco. *Procedia Computer Science*, 184, pp. 404-410.
- Aguilar, J., Garces-Jimenez, A., R-Moreno, M. D., & Garcia, R. (2021, nov). A systematic literature review on the use of artificial intelligence in energy self-management in smart buildings. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 151, p. 111530.
- Cuneo, A., Quellec, P.-J. L., Choné, T., Comodi, G., Valalaki, K., Samari, K., & Medved, T. (2021, nov). Energy Communities: How Tools Can Facilitate Their Enhancement. *The 9th Annual Edition of Sustainable Places (SP 2021)* (p. 13). MDPI.
- Cuttle, C. (2008). *Lighting by Design*. London: Routledge.
- Flynn, J. E., & Spencer, T. J. (1977). The Effects of Light Source Color on User Impression and Satisfaction. *Journal of the Illuminating Engineering Society*, 167-179.
- Henzel, J., Wrobel, L., Fice, M., & Sikora, M. (2022, jun). Energy Consumption Forecasting for the Digital-Twin Model of the Building. *Energies*, 15(12), p. 4318.
- Kamari, A., & Schultz, C. (2022). How can LCA inform early-stage design to meet Danish regulations? The sustainability opportunity metric. *14th European Conference on Product & Process Modelling (ECPPM 2022)*.
- Kritzinger, W. e. (2018). Digital Twin in manufacturing: A categorical literature review and classification. *Ifac-PapersOnline*, 1016-1022.
- Lu, Q., Parlikad, A. K., Woodall, P., Don Ranasinghe, G., Xie, X., Liang, Z., . . . Schooling, J. (2020, may). Developing a Digital Twin at Building and City Levels: Case Study of West Cambridge Campus. *Journal of Management in Engineering*, 36(3), p. 05020004.

- Lu, Q., Xie, X., Parlikad, A. K., & Schooling, J. M. (2020, oct). Digital twin-enabled anomaly detection for built asset monitoring in operation and maintenance. *Automation in Construction*, *118*, p. 103277.
- Olszewski, R. (2018, jan). Solving a "Smart City" Transport Problems by Designing Carpooling Gamification Schemes with Multi-Agent Systems: The Case of the So-Called "Mordor of Warsaw". *Sensors*, *18*(2), p. 141.
- Onile, A. E., Machlev, R., Petlenkov, E., Levron, Y., & Belikov, J. (2021, nov). Uses of the digital twins concept for energy services, intelligent recommendation systems, and demand side management: A review. *Energy Reports*, *7*, pp. 997-1015.
- PROBONO Project . (2021). *PROPOSAL_101037075-PROBONO-H2020-LC-GD-2020-7-PART_B_Section_1*.
- Razmjoo, A., Nezhad, M. M., Kaigutha, L. G., Marzband, M., Mirjalili, S., Pazhoohesh, M., . . . Piras, G. (2021, jul). Investigating Smart City Development Based on Green Buildings, Electrical Vehicles and Feasible Indicators. *Sustainability*, *13*(14), p. 7808.
- Schultz, C., Amor, R., Lobb, B., & Guesgen, H. (2009). Qualitative design support for engineering and architecture. *Advanced Engineering Informatics*, 68-80. doi:10.1016/j.aei.2008.07.003
- Sepasgozar, S. M. (2020, jul). Digital Twin and Web-Based Virtual Gaming Technologies for Online Education: A Case of Construction Management and Engineering. *Applied Sciences*, *10*(13), p. 4678.
- Sepasgozar, S. M. (2021, apr). Differentiating Digital Twin from Digital Shadow: Elucidating a Paradigm Shift to Expedite a Smart, Sustainable Built Environment. *Buildings*, *11*(4), p. 151.
- Talei, H., Benhaddou, D., Gamarra, C., Benbrahim, H., & Essaaidi, M. (2021, sep). Smart Building Energy Inefficiencies Detection through Time Series Analysis and Unsupervised Machine Learning. *Energies*, *14*(19), p. 6042.
- Wang, W., Hu, H., Zhang, J. C., & Hu, Z. (2020, dec). Digital Twin-based Framework for Green Building Maintenance System. *2020 IEEE International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Engineering Management (IEEM)* (pp. 1301-1305). Singapore, Singapore: IEEE.

Xie, X., Lu, Q., Parlikad, A. K., & Schooling, J. M. (2020). Digital Twin Enabled Asset Anomaly Detection for Building Facility Management. *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, 53(3), pp. 380-385.

Yigitcanlar, T., Mehmood, R., & Corchado, J. M. (2021, aug). Green Artificial Intelligence: Towards an Efficient, Sustainable and Equitable Technology for Smart Cities and Futures. *Sustainability*, 13(16), p. 8952.

Zaballos, A.n., Briones, A., Massa, A., Centelles, P., & Caballero, V.c. (2020, nov). A smart campus' digital twin for sustainable comfort monitoring. *Sustainability*, 12(21), p. 9196.